

Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks for Tabular Data Synthesis

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Disclaimer

This version of the thesis is a first draft submitted for early sharing and feedback. It has not yet undergone full review by the academic advisors. Certain sections, such as the Dedication & Acknowledgements, are still in progress. These do not affect the technical content of the thesis.

Abstract

Synthetic data and its generation through classical statistical models have been studied since the 1990s. However, with the rise of deep learning, particularly models based on Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), the field has seen rapid advancements. More recently, the advent of Large Language Models (LLMs) and their data-hungry nature has made the development of high-quality synthetic data, especially tabular data, increasingly essential. Most deep learning-based generators for tabular data, including the widely used CTGAN and TVAE, rely on classical Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs) as their core architecture. In 2024, Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks were introduced as a promising alternative to MLPs, offering greater representational flexibility through learnable spline-based activations. This thesis explores whether replacing MLP components in CTGAN and TVAE with KANs can improve the generation of tabular synthetic data. To this end, six novel KAN-based models were developed and evaluated against their MLP-based counterparts (i.e., CTGAN and TVAE) using statistical fidelity, machine learning utility, and computational efficiency as the three standard benchmarks. The results demonstrate that in 6 out of 8 datasets, at least one of the KAN-based models outperformed their MLP counterparts in statistical fidelity, and achieved comparable or better results in all 8 datasets used to evaluate machine learning utility. These gains, however, come at the cost of increased training time and resource consumption. As part of this work, the models are made publicly available through the *KAN-synth* Python package, accessible at: https://github.com/cris1618/KAN_synth. This package allows practitioners to easily use or extend the models for their own use cases.

Dedication & Acknowledgments

*A voi che del sogno fate realtà:
del corpo siete porto e partenza;
dell'anima, casa ed accoglienza,
per sempre e oltre, nell'eternità.*

seconda quartina

prima terzina

seconda terzina

*To you, who turn dreams into reality:
of the body you are harbor and departure;
of the soul, home and welcoming embrace,
forever and beyond, into eternity.*

[TO BE COMPLETED]

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 A Brief History of Synthetic Data

Synthetic data, in the broadest sense, refers to data that is not directly measured from the real world. For example, when Galileo Galilei observed celestial bodies through his telescope, ending up challenging the geocentric model of the time, he was collecting real-world data. In contrast, synthetic data is generated, often artificially and for a specific purpose, to mimic or model various phenomena[1]. The practice of generating such data did not originate with the invention of the computer. Its roots extend much further back, embedded in humanity's enduring attempt to describe and simulate the world through what Galileo, in *The Assayer*[2], referred to as the language of the universe: mathematics.

In fact, the idea of synthetic data is closely related to simulation, particularly when the goal is to generate artificial data by modeling real-world processes or phenomena[3]. Simulations have historically served as tools for producing data when direct measurement is impractical or impossible, and this issue clearly existed well before the advent of computers[4]. Even in pre-modern science, researchers often relied on theoretical constructs and numerical experimentation to simulate outcomes under different conditions[5], laying the groundwork for what would later evolve into formal data synthesis.

For instance, during the Copernican revolution, Johannes Kepler used Tycho Brahe's extensive and highly accurate astronomical observations to formulate a model of planetary motion[6]. In particular, Kepler discovered that the orbit of Mars could not be explained by circular motion, as previously believed by both Copernicus and Brahe, but instead followed an elliptical path[7]. This conclusion did not arise from direct observation of Mars' movement alone, but rather through one of the earliest applications of mathematical modeling and simulation. By analyzing the discrepancy between predicted and observed positions over time, Kepler inferred that the planets trace ellipses with the Sun at one focus, a result later formalized in what became his First Law of Planetary Motion[8]. Using this mathematical model, he could generate future planetary

positions with high accuracy, effectively producing simulated data based on an underlying physical theory. Furthermore, in his *Astronomie Nova*[9]¹, Kepler speculated about a force emanating from the Sun that governed planetary motion, an insight that foreshadowed Newton’s law of universal gravitation[8].

The idea of simulation as a means to generate data takes a more explicit form in 1777 with the experiment proposed by the French naturalist and mathematician Georges-Louis Leclerc, Comte de Buffon². In what is now considered one of the earliest examples of a Monte Carlo method, Buffon devised a probabilistic experiment³ to estimate the value of π by repeatedly dropping a needle onto a ruled surface marked by parallel lines and recording how often the needle crossed one of them, assuming that the surface is sufficiently large to neglect boundary effects (i.e. the needle falling on a boundary)[13]. However, the spirit of Buffon’s experiment would remain largely dormant until almost two centuries later, when it re-emerged in a radically more powerful context during the Second World War. In the 1940s, amidst the Manhattan Project at Los Alamos, Stanislaw Ulam and John von Neumann formalized Buffon’s idea into what would officially become known as the Monte Carlo method[14, 15]⁴. The two mathematicians used early computers to simulate probabilistic processes, generating synthetic data to estimate integrals, solve differential equations, and model nuclear interactions[17]. The name “Monte Carlo” itself was coined as a nod to the famed casino, highlighting the central role of randomness in the method[18].

With the advancement of computational power and resources in the 20th century, we arrive at the modern concept of synthetic data, as described in the definition provided by Jordon et al.[1]:

“Synthetic data is data that has been generated using a purpose-built mathematical model or algorithm, with the aim of solving a (set of) data science task(s).”

The formal notion of synthetic data, derived by statistical approaches, is commonly attributed to the work of Donald Rubin[19] and Roderick Little[20], although related ideas had already been explored earlier by researchers such as Liew et al.[21]. Their approach emerged in the context of data privacy and survey methodology, particularly building upon earlier work on multiple imputation (MI) for handling nonresponse in surveys[22, 23]. Initially, Rubin and Little sought ways to avoid disclosing sensitive information when sharing survey data. Instead of simply imputing missing values, they proposed replacing sensitive or identifying values with synthetic ones generated from a statistical

¹For an in-depth analysis of the mathematical methods and numerical techniques used by Kepler, see [10]

²Buffon was an influential yet controversial figure of the Enlightenment. While his work foreshadowed modern simulation, his contemporaries often dismissed him as a popularizer rather than a rigorous thinker. See [11]

³The curious reader may find a detailed and accessible description of the experiment at [12]

⁴Refer to [16] for the full story of the method.

model⁵. Similarly to the MI method, the synthetic data approach involves generating multiple synthetic datasets to allow valid statistical inference. Even though it took another ten years before the methodology was fully developed and the first practical application started to emerge[25], this method was able to preserve key statistical properties of the original data while reducing the risk of privacy violations. As in the nonresponse setting, generating multiple synthetic versions of the data enabled accurate estimation of variability, capturing the uncertainty inherent in the synthetic data generation process[24, 26].

In parallel to the work of the statistical community, the computer science community has also made significant advances in synthetic data generation, particularly driven by privacy concerns[25, 27]. However, in contrast to the approach initiated by Rubin and Little, much of the research in computer science has rarely focused on ensuring valid statistical inference, for example, properly quantifying the uncertainty in estimates derived from synthetic data. As Drechsler et al.[25] point out, the primary motivation in computer science has often been to facilitate easier access to data for training machine learning models. Nonetheless, both the statistical and computer science communities share a common core goal in synthetic data generation: ideally, any analysis performed on synthetic data should yield results approximately equivalent to those obtained using the original dataset. In other words, synthetic data should preserve not only the statistical properties of the real data but also its underlying utility⁶. In the context of computer science, the utility is frequently assessed in terms of predictive performance, how well machine learning models trained on synthetic data generalize when compared to those trained on the original data. This evaluation framework is often referred to as *Train on Synthetic, Test on Real*(TSTR)[29, 30, 31, 28, 32, 33] (this aspect will be explored further in the literature review and method sections).

Thanks to these advances in synthetic data research, synthetic data has found applications across a wide range of domains in recent years, including official statistics, healthcare, education, finance, economics, and, increasingly, machine learning. The following overview of applications is largely informed by the work of Drechsler et al.[25], who provide a detailed survey of synthetic data use in practice.

One of the first real-world applications of synthetic data emerged in 1997, when the U.S. Federal Reserve Board chose to replace certain sensitive monetary values in the Survey of Consumer Finances with synthetic counterparts to reduce disclosure risk[34]. A few years later, Abowd and Woodcock[35, 36] further demonstrated the potential of synthetic data for protecting confidential-

⁵Rubin and later Reiter typically used parametric Bayesian models, such as multivariate normal or regression-based models, to generate synthetic values. These models are estimated from the observed data, and then synthetic values are drawn from the posterior predictive distribution. The choice of model depends on the type of data (continuous, categorical, etc.) and the relationships one aims to preserve. See [19] and [24] for detailed discussions.

⁶Interestingly, a study by Xu et al.[28] shows that the distribution of synthetic data does not necessarily need to closely match the real one in order to ensure consistent model performance, challenging the intuitive assumption that higher statistical similarity always implies greater utility.

ity in complex longitudinal and linked datasets⁷, using data from the French National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies (INSEE). A notable milestone followed in 2007, when the U.S. Census Bureau released the SIPP Synthetic Beta[38], which is a large-scale synthetic dataset generated from the Survey of Income and Program Participation (SIPP), combined with administrative records from the Social Security Administration and the Internal Revenue Service. Impressively, nearly all of the 600 variables in this longitudinal dataset were synthesized.

Another noteworthy early application of synthetic data was OntheMap, an interactive tool developed to visualize commuting patterns across the United States. Introduced by Machanavajjhala et al.[39], this platform was groundbreaking not only in its functionality but also because it was the first to provide formal privacy guarantees based on the concept of (ϵ, δ) -probabilistic differential privacy, a relaxed form of the original privacy framework introduced by Dwork et al.[40]⁸ A few years later, the U.S. Census Bureau expanded its use of synthetic data with the release of the Synthetic Longitudinal Business Database[42, 43]. This dataset, partially synthetic, is based on the original Longitudinal Business Database, which compiles administrative data covering all U.S. businesses. Similarly, the Census Bureau has also leveraged synthetic data techniques to safeguard sensitive records in the American Community Survey (ACS)[44]. At the state level, the Maryland Longitudinal Data System Center (MLDSC) represents another significant example. This center maintains a comprehensive educational data infrastructure for the state of Maryland, drawing from a variety of administrative sources. In 2016, with support from the Institute of Education Sciences, MLDSC launched the Synthetic Data Project, aiming to increase accessibility to this rich but sensitive dataset[45, 46].

Outside of the United States, synthetic data has also gained traction in national statistical offices and research institutions. Statistics New Zealand was among the first to adopt the approach, releasing Synthetic Unit Record Files (SURFs)[47, 48] for teaching purposes and later applying them to microsimulation for language⁹ policy scenarios. In Europe, the German Institute of Employment Research released a partially synthetic wave of its Establishment Panel in 2011[50], and the Scottish Longitudinal Study adopted synthetic datasets to allow researchers preliminary access to highly sensitive linked data[51]. This initiative also led to the development of the now widely used R package *synth-*

⁷A *longitudinal dataset* is a collection of data where the same units, such as individuals, households, or institutions, are observed repeatedly over time. While longitudinal data involves repeated observations, it is not the same as a time series, which typically tracks a single variable or unit across continuous time intervals. For a more detailed comparison between longitudinal and time series data, see [37].

⁸For an in-depth overview of differential privacy, including its foundational principles, mechanisms, and real-world applications, see [41].

⁹The microsimulation model aimed to support policies promoting the revitalization of Te Reo Māori, the Indigenous language of the Māori people in New Zealand. It was used to estimate future fluency and uptake under various interventions, helping guide language planning efforts. See [49].

*pop*¹⁰[53]. Statistics Netherlands contributed to the field by generating synthetic public-use files for the EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SLIC) in 2015[54], mostly for training and code development prior to accessing restricted datasets¹¹.

Other ongoing efforts include projects by the Urban Institute, which is trying to develop synthetic tax data for the IRS[56, 57], and the Australian Bureau of Statistics, currently evaluating synthetic data as a secure method for disseminating microdata[58].

With the rise of machine learning, and deep learning in particular, synthetic data generation has experienced rapid progress in recent years. These advancements have laid the groundwork for increasingly sophisticated generative models and a growing number of real-world applications. But why should we use synthetic data in the first place?

1.2 Why Synthetic Data?

As noted in the previous section, synthetic data is being employed to address a variety of problems across various domains. In the specific context of machine learning, four key motivations for using synthetic data, either as a replacement or augmentation of real data, stand out, building on those outlined by Jordon et al.[1]: (i) Privacy and Compliance, (ii) Cost-Effectiveness, (iii) Testing and Evaluation, and (iv) Addressing Data Scarcity. While this list is not exhaustive, it offers a representative overview of the most common and impactful use cases, and helps explain the growing interest in synthetic data in recent years. Each of these motivations is discussed in detail below.

1.2.1 Privacy and Compliance

In many real-world datasets, particularly in sensitive domains such as healthcare[59] and finance[60], the presence of personally identifiable information (PII) often makes data access and analysis challenging for researchers and developers. This, in turn, can slow the pace of experimentation and delay progress in a typical machine learning workflow¹². The primary reason for these constraints is given by the growing number of data protection regulations that limit how and for what purposes personal data can be used and shared[62]. One of the most influential regulations is the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), introduced by the European Union in 2016[63]. GDPR aims to safeguard the privacy rights of individuals within the European Economic Area (EEA) by giving them greater control over their personal data. It applies not only to organizations based in the EU but also to any entity processing data from EU residents, regardless of

¹⁰For a concise and technical explanation on how to use the package in R, see [52].

¹¹The data are available at the Eurostat website, see [55].

¹²Data collection and processing is one of the most important and time-consuming steps in the entire machine learning workflow. For this reason, having access to high-quality data is essential for well-functioning models. See [61] for more details.

its location. The regulation includes strict penalties for non-compliance, up to 4% of global annual turnover for the most serious violations. For large corporations such as Amazon, for instance, this can translate into fines worth billions of dollars. In the United States, a comparable example is the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA)[64], a federal law passed in 1996. HIPAA establishes standards for the protection of sensitive medical information and aims to both ensure the secure handling of patient data and facilitate smoother transitions between healthcare providers and insurance plans.

These regulations create substantial barriers to accessing and working with high-quality real-world datasets, especially in sensitive domains. As a result, data-driven research and development efforts can be significantly delayed or constrained. Synthetic data offers a promising alternative, as it enables researchers and practitioners to work with data that, in principle, retains the statistical properties of the original datasets while mitigating privacy risks. Therefore, synthetic datasets can facilitate data sharing and model training without compromising individual confidentiality or violating legal constraints. For example, Beaulieu-Jones et al.[65] demonstrated the use of generative adversarial networks (GANs)(An extensive review of such methods will be given in the Literature Review section) to create synthetic electronic health records that retained key statistical properties of the original data, but significantly reduced the risk of patient re-identification. Their approach allowed researchers to train machine learning models on synthetic data with minimal loss in predictive performance compared to real data, while preserving patient privacy in accordance with regulatory constraints.

However, it’s important to note that synthetic data is not automatically private or safe from disclosure risk[1]. In fact, it is well-known that machine learning models, and most of all neural networks, have the capacity to memorize their training data[66, 67]. Consequently, if a Synthetic Data Generator (SDG) is not carefully designed with privacy in mind, there is a non-negligible risk that the synthetic data it produces may inadvertently leak sensitive information about individuals in the original dataset. Since the primary focus of this thesis is not on privacy-preserving synthetic data generation, I’ll not explore in detail the extensive literature on this topic. Nonetheless, it is important to briefly introduce one of the most foundational and widely adopted mathematical frameworks for enabling privacy in synthetic data: Differential Privacy (DP)[68, 69].

In the context of synthetic data, differential privacy can be seen as an additional property enforced on the output of the algorithm used to generate the data. Informally, this means that noise has been introduced during the training of the generative model (e.g., GANs, TVAEs, etc.), making it extremely difficult to infer individual records from the synthetic output. More formally, (ϵ, δ) -DP ensures that the output of a randomized mechanism¹³ \mathcal{M} is statistically close

¹³A *randomized mechanism* is a function or algorithm that maps an input dataset to an output distribution rather than a single deterministic output. In the context of differential privacy, randomness is typically introduced via noise sampled from Laplace or Gaussian distributions.

whether or not a single individual’s data is included in the input. That is, for any two adjacent datasets \mathcal{D} and \mathcal{D}' (differing in only one record), and for any possible set of outputs \mathcal{E} , the following condition holds:

$$\Pr[\mathcal{M}(\mathcal{D}) \in \mathcal{E}] \leq e^\varepsilon \Pr[\mathcal{M}(\mathcal{D}') \in \mathcal{E}] + \delta \quad (1.1)$$

where $\varepsilon \geq 0$ is the *privacy loss parameter*, and $\delta \geq 0$ is the *failure probability* that the mechanism may exceed this bound. When $\delta = 0$, \mathcal{M} is said to be *pure ε -differentially private*. Furthermore, arbitrary post-processing of the output of an (ε, δ) -DP mechanism does not increase privacy loss, thanks to the *post-processing property*.¹⁴ In simpler terms, even if a possible attacker has access to both the mechanism and its output, they cannot confidently infer whether any individual record was included in the input. This provides strong privacy protection for individuals, even in adversarial settings[40, 70].

Differential privacy, however, is not without limitations. One key challenge lies in the choice of the parameters ε and δ [1]. The privacy guarantees provided by a differentially private mechanism depend on these parameters, but choosing appropriate values is notoriously difficult¹⁵, and heavily depends on the specific application context[72, 73, 74]. Another fundamental limitation is the inherent tradeoff between privacy and utility. In practice, differential privacy mechanisms inject noise into the output to mask the influence of individual data points. While this noise enhances privacy, it can significantly degrade the utility of the resulting synthetic data, particularly for tasks like training machine learning models, which may rely on fine-grained patterns that are easily disrupted by added noise.

1.2.2 Cost-Effectiveness

Accessing real-world data can be highly expensive, both in terms of financial cost and time. In the healthcare sector, for example, accessing actual patient data for clinical research involves significant logistical and regulatory obstacles. Retrospective studies, which analyze existing patient records, can cost around \$80,000, while prospective studies, where new data is collected over time, may exceed \$2 million, especially when data acquisition is critical to study outcomes[75]. On top of the monetary burden, the fragmented and siloed nature of healthcare data systems often results in delays in data collection and subsequent cleaning and integration. In many cases, researchers must wait weeks or even months to gain access to usable datasets[76, 77, 78]. Therefore, it contributes to slowing down innovation and early-stage research. Again, synthetic data provides a promising alternative to mitigate these challenges. Since

¹⁴If a mechanism \mathcal{M} satisfies (ε, δ) -DP, then any function f applied to its output, i.e. $f(\mathcal{M}(\mathcal{D}))$, remains (ε, δ) -DP. This means privacy guarantees are preserved even after further computations.

¹⁵Selecting values for ε and δ is challenging because there is no universally accepted threshold for what constitutes "private enough." Smaller values offer stronger privacy but often reduce data utility, while larger values weaken privacy guarantees. Moreover, ε has an exponential impact on privacy loss, yet its practical meaning is often unclear to practitioners. For a deeper discussion, see [71].

synthetic data is procedurally generated, the primary cost involved lies in producing it through a Synthetic Data Generator (SDG). Even though this process can be computationally intensive, depending on the size of the dataset to be generated, it remains significantly less expensive than collecting and securing real-world data.

One illustrative example is the study by Meeker et al.[79], which evaluated the use of *Synthea*, an open-source synthetic patient data generator, for simulation studies in healthcare. The study showed that *Synthea* could successfully replicate the initial conditions and simulation endpoints of a published cost-effectiveness analysis comparing levofloxacin prophylaxis¹⁶ to usual care for leukemia patients. As a result, the researchers were able to simulate real-world clinical scenarios without accessing actual patient data, thereby reducing potential costs associated with data acquisition and ethical approvals. However, it is important to recognize that these approaches are still in their early stages, and further research is needed to assess how comprehensively, if possible, synthetic data can substitute for real-world data in healthcare and in various other contexts.

Another interesting application of synthetic data for cost reduction can be found in the research and development of autonomous driving systems. Labeling data to train deep neural networks in this domain is particularly labor-intensive and expensive. Real-world data collection typically requires deploying autonomous vehicle prototypes, which introduces logistical complexity and potential mechanical failures, involving unexpected incidents during driving[81]. In a recent study, Ozeren and Bhowmick[82] evaluated the impact of synthetic data on object detection tasks in autonomous driving. They conducted controlled experiments using several real-world datasets in combination with a synthetic dataset generated by BIT Technology Solutions GmbH¹⁷. Their findings suggest that integrating synthetic data alongside real-world data improves the robustness and generalization of object detection models, showing the potential of using synthetic data to reduce development costs while maintaining model performance.

1.2.3 Testing and Evaluation

In the software development sector, testing and evaluating software prior to deployment is essential for identifying and fixing potential bugs and reliability issues. This process typically requires large amounts of production-like test data

¹⁶Levofloxacin prophylaxis refers to the preventive use of the antibiotic levofloxacin to reduce the risk of infection in vulnerable patient populations, such as those undergoing chemotherapy for leukemia. Since this thesis does not delve into clinical treatments and I am far from an expert in this domain, the curious reader is encouraged to refer to [80] for a more detailed discussion.

¹⁷BIT Technology Solutions GmbH is a German company specializing in artificial intelligence and computer vision systems, including synthetic data generation platforms for autonomous driving applications.

for both system-level testing and User Acceptance Testing (UAT)¹⁸. As noted in previous sections, accessing real data for this purpose can be challenging due to regulatory constraints such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). In this context, synthetic data could potentially save significant time and effort in the development lifecycle. As emphasized by Jordon et al.[1], for software testing purposes, synthetic data must be semantically correct, meaning that it should reflect the structure and constraints of the real data, but it need not be statistically accurate. Mathematically, this means that the synthetic data should capture the *support* of the distribution and relevant structural dependencies (e.g., sequences in time-series data or repeated measurements in longitudinal datasets), without necessarily replicating the true underlying data distribution. This is one of the design principles of the OpenSAFELY platform, which allows epidemiological research on patient health data without exposing real records. Practitioners first develop and test their analytic pipelines using structurally realistic synthetic data. Once verified, the code is executed in a secure environment on the real, sensitive data just once[84].

Synthetic data also provides a practical means to evaluate and compare machine learning models in controlled settings. As discussed earlier, real data is often scarce or access-restricted, making synthetic data valuable surrogates for testing model robustness and evaluating performance metrics prior to deployment. In this context, the goal is not necessarily to obtain identical results to those derived from real data, but rather to reach the same conclusions. For instance, if a developer compares two models on synthetic data and determines that Model A outperforms Model B for a given task, the same conclusion should ideally hold when evaluated on the real dataset, even if the exact performance metrics differ[1]. This requires that the synthetic data preserves the key statistical properties of the original data distribution, at least to the extent necessary to support reliable model selection and evaluation. In addition to model evaluation, synthetic data can also be used for stress testing and addressing class imbalance. In many supervised machine learning tasks, the training dataset is imbalanced, meaning that certain classes have significantly more examples than others[85]. As a concrete example, in the task of predicting diseases from patient features, most samples may involve common illnesses like fever, while very few involve rare conditions. Thus, the model may learn to ignore rare cases, since there are not enough training labels for it to detect these patterns reliably. By artificially generating samples that represent rare or adversarial scenarios, developers can test how models behave under edge-case conditions and mitigate issues arising from imbalanced data distribution[86, 87].

1.2.4 Addressing Data Scarcity

In recent years, we have experienced what I consider to be one of the greatest revolutions in the history of humankind, one that we have yet to fully com-

¹⁸UAT is often the final testing stage before the software is released to the market, and refers to the phase in which the software is tested by its intended users to ensure it meets their needs and requirements. See [83] for more details.

prehend (if we ever will): the commercialization of Large Language Models (LLMs) and the overall advancement of artificial intelligence (AI). This rapid advancement has led to an insatiable demand for vast and high-quality datasets to train and fine-tune these models[88]. In fact, the performance of LLMs, and of machine learning models in general, is highly dependent on the quality and volume of the data they are trained on[89, 90, 91]. However, real-world data is not unlimited. Even though data is being generated constantly at a massive scale¹⁹, access to high-quality labeled data remains limited, due to various factors explored in previous sections, such as privacy regulations, legal constraints, and the significant cost associated with data annotation²⁰.

Given the recent nature of this phenomenon, the use of synthetic data to train LLMs remains an open and rapidly evolving area of research and development. Traditional data augmentation techniques, such as image rotation, cropping, and flipping, have long been employed to combat data scarcity in machine learning tasks[94, 95]. Although these methods enhance data diversity and somewhat tackle data scarcity, they still have difficulty completely reflecting the complex distributions of real-world data.[96]. One of the most active areas of research involves using LLMs themselves to generate data for their own training. For example, the prompt-based technique consists of giving a large language model a carefully crafted textual prompt describing a task or scenario (e.g., "Generate five statement-labeled customer reviews"), and the model's outputs are then used as synthetic data for training or fine-tuning[97]. In contrast, synthetic QA pair generation focuses on generating plausible question-answer pairs, often in the context of information retrieval or reading comprehension tasks[98].

Not only do LLMs suffer from data scarcity, but many organizations across domains also struggle to access high-quality, real-world data that is both structured and analysis-ready[99, 100]. In this context, *structured* typically means data is already organized in a tabular format, rows and columns with clear semantics, which can be readily used for analysis and modeling. This stands in contrast to *unstructured* data, such as raw text and images, which often require significant preprocessing and transformation before they can yield useful insight. For this reason, since the seminal contributions by Rubin and Little in the early 1990s[19, 20] (see the section *A Brief History of Synthetic Data* above), research on the generation of synthetic structured, or tabular, data has grown rapidly. Initially dominated by statistical methods, this field has seen a significant shift in recent years with the rise of the machine learning community, leading to the development of several deep learning-based approaches to tabular data synthesis. These methods, along with an overview of tabular data itself, will be the focus of the section. A deeper technical and mathematical exploration of models and techniques will follow in the *Literature Review* chapter.

¹⁹To give the reader a sense of the magnitude of this phenomenon, it was estimated in 2024 that approximately 402.74 million terabytes of data are generated globally each day. For additional statistics on global data generation, see [92].

²⁰Labeling large-scale datasets often requires expert annotators, making the process slow and expensive. See [93] for more details.

1.3 Tabular Data and Methods for Tabular Synthesis

So far, synthetic data has been discussed in a broad sense, encompassing various modalities such as text, images, and tabular data. The focus of the following sections and chapters will now narrow to synthetic tabular data, which is the primary concern of this thesis.

Tabular data refers to structured data organized in rows and columns, where each row represents an individual sample, and each column corresponds to a specific feature or variable. This format simplifies data entry, retrieval, and analysis, making it one of the most widely used data structures in business intelligence, scientific research, and machine learning[101]. Popular tools for working with tabular data include platforms such as Tableau and Power BI, and programming languages like Python and R. In Python, the *pandas* library[102] is extensively used for tabular data manipulation, while in R, base functions are enough, but also packages including *dplyr*[103] and *ggplot2*[104] from the tidyverse ecosystem support advanced operations and visualizations. One defining characteristic of tabular data is its heterogeneity. In fact, columns can contain different data types, including numerical values, categorical variables, dates, and boolean flags. For example, a census might include columns for age (numerical), marital status (categorical), income (numerical), and gender (binary). This versatility makes tabular data extremely valuable, and many organizations aspire to structure their data in this way to enable efficient analytics[105].

Given these values, the ability to generate synthetic tabular data that replicates the structure and utility of real-world datasets has become increasingly appealing, particularly in domains where real data is scarce, sensitive, or expensive to collect. Nonetheless, tabular data is among the most challenging data formats to synthesize, due to both its inherent structure and the way it is typically collected in real-world settings[106]. Real tabular datasets are often limited in size, and as with any machine learning task, scarce training data can hinder the model’s ability to learn and generate reliable synthetic samples. Another common complication is the presence of missing values. Since a Synthetic Data Generator (SDG) must learn the underlying distribution of the dataset, missing entries increase the difficulty of accurately capturing that distribution. Class imbalance further complicates the task. In many real-world classification problems, some categories or labels are far less represented than others. Revisiting an earlier example, in the task of predicting diseases from patient features, most samples might pertain to common conditions such as fever, while only a few represent rare or complex illnesses. Thus, the SDG may become biased toward generating samples from the dominant class, reducing its effectiveness in simulating the complete data space.

Further complications arise from the structural characteristics of tabular data. Its heterogeneity, i.e., the coexistence of numerical, categorical, and ordinal variables, makes it difficult for generative models to learn a coherent joint distribution. Because the goal of the SDG is to capture the intra- and inter-

column dependencies, complex and often sparse feature correlations pose additional obstacles. Not all features are strongly correlated, and the patterns of dependence are rarely uniform. For instance, income and age may exhibit a statistical relationship, whereas age and gender might not. Lastly, many traditional statistical methods rely on the assumption that data is normally (i.e., Gaussian) distributed, for its mathematical tractability and the prevalence of "Gaussianity" in natural processes²¹. In practice, numerical variables in tabular datasets frequently violate this assumption, exhibiting skewed or multimodal distributions that are harder for SDGs to capture accurately.

To address these challenges, various techniques have been proposed over the past few decades. In what follows, and consistently throughout this thesis, I will distinguish four major types of Synthetic Data Generators (SDGs): statistical methods, deep learning-based models, diffusion models, and the more recent approaches based on Large Language Models (LLMs).

One of the earliest families of approaches adopted for synthetic data generation were statistical methods. Among the most popular and effective are copulas[108], which are based on *Sklar's Theorem*. This theorem states that any multivariate distribution, such as the one describing a dataset, can be decomposed into its marginal distributions (i.e., the distributions of individual columns) and a *copula* function that captures the dependence structure between variables. This separation of marginal and dependencies allows for flexible modeling of complex multivariate distributions[109]. Another widely used statistical technique is the Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM)[110], which represents the data distribution as a mixture of multiple Gaussian components. By learning the parameters of these components (i.e., means, covariances, and mixing weights), the GMM tries to capture the underlying structure of the data and enables the generation of new synthetic samples from the learned distribution. A third prominent example is the Bayesian Network[111, 112], a probabilistic graphical model that encodes the conditional dependencies among variables using a *directed acyclic graph* (DAG). In this representation, each node corresponds to a variable, and directed edges indicate probabilistic dependencies.

Even though statistical methods perform relatively well in generating synthetic tabular data, the advent of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), introduced by Goodfellow et al.[113], marked a turning point in the field. Since their introduction, GANs have become one of the most influential deep learning frameworks for generative modeling[25]. A GAN consists of two neural networks, typically implemented as plain Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs) in the case of tabular data, that compete in a two-player minimax game. The two players are the generator, which learns to produce synthetic samples that resemble the data, and the discriminator, which learns to distinguish between real and synthetic examples. These two networks are trained simultaneously in the

²¹This is one of the many fascinations of mathematics. Its beauty lies in the unknown, in the mystery of why the Gaussian distribution is so ubiquitous. While the Central Limit Theorem is often cited as the explanation, it merely shifts the "why" one level deeper, and in many cases, the CLT does not apply at all. For further insight and alternative explanations, such as the Maximum Entropy principle, see [107].

two opposite tasks. In fact, the generator improves its outputs to better fool the discriminator, and on the other hand, the discriminator becomes increasingly skilled at detecting fake data. More formally, the generator $G(z; \theta_g)$ maps a random noise vector $z \sim p_z(z)$ (drawn from a prior distribution such as Gaussian or uniform) to the data space, and the discriminator $D(x; \theta_d)$ estimates the probability that a given input x originates from the real data distribution. The overall objective is to solve the following minmax optimization problem:

$$\min_G \max_D V(D, G) = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p_{\text{data}}(x)} [\log D(x)] + \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_z(z)} [\log(1 - D(G(z)))] \quad (1.2)$$

where $p_{\text{data}}(x)$ is the distribution of real data and $p_z(z)$ is the prior distribution over the latent space. At equilibrium, the generator ideally produces samples that the discriminator cannot distinguish from real ones, meaning $D(G(z)) \approx 0.5$. A graphical and intuitive explanation is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1.1: A simple GAN architecture where both the Generator and Discriminator are MLPs.

Initially, GANs proved enormously powerful for tasks like image synthesis, speech generation, and even natural language applications[114, 115, 116]. Quickly after, researchers adapted the same adversarial framework to tabular data, introducing many variants of the original GAN architecture, in order to tackle their unique challenges, as discussed above.

Another important breakthrough for deep learning-based models came with the introduction of the Variational Autoencoder (VAE)[117]. The idea is similar to that of GANs, but instead of a generator and a discriminator, a VAE is composed of an encoder, which maps each real data point x into a distribution over a low-dimensional latent space (parametrized by a mean vector $\mu(x)$ and a diagonal covariance $\sigma^2(x)$), and a decoder, which attempts to reconstruct x by sampling $z \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu(x), \sigma^2(x))$ and passing it through a second network. During training, the VAE jointly optimizes two objectives, aiming to improve both encoder and decoder performances on their tasks. The first is a reconstruction loss,

typically the expected negative log-likelihood $\mathbb{E}_{q(z|x)} [-\log p(x|z)]$, which pushes the decoder to accurately recreate its inputs. The second is a latent regularization term, represented by the Kullback-Leibler divergence²² $KL(q(z|x)||p(z))$, that encourages the encoder’s approximate posterior $q(z|x)$ to stay close to a simple prior $p(z)$, usually a standard Gaussian. Altogether, the VAE minimizes

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{VAE}} = \mathbb{E}_{q_\phi(z|x)} [-\log p_\theta(x|z)] + \text{KL}(q_\phi(z|x) \| p(z)) \quad (1.3)$$

commonly known as the negative Evidence Lower Bound (ELBO), where ϕ and θ denote the encoder and decoder parameters, respectively. At inference time, one can sample $z \sim p(z)$ and pass it through the encoder alone to generate entirely new examples that capture the broad structure of the training set. See Figure 2 for a graphical illustration.

Figure 1.2: A simple VAE architecture where both the Generator and Discriminator are MLPs, as in GANs.

In addition to traditional deep learning based methods based on variations of GANs and VAEs, recent advances have introduced generative models for tabular data based on diffusion processes and Large Language Models (LLMs)[120, 121]. Diffusion models are likelihood-based generative frameworks that synthesize data by learning to reverse a gradual corruption process. They model data generation as a Markovian process²³, consisting of two stages: a forward (diffu-

²²The KL divergence quantifies how much one probability distribution differs from a second, reference distribution. In VAEs, it acts as a regularizer to keep the latent space close to the prior. For an intuitive explanation of the Kullback–Leibler divergence, see Adian Liusie’s video: [118], and for a more technical and detailed description, see [119].

²³A Markovian process is a stochastic process in which the future state of a system depends only on the present state, and not on the sequence of events that preceded it.

sion) process that incrementally adds noise to the data, and a reverse (denoising) process that learns to reconstruct clean samples from pure noise[106].

However, all the methods discussed so far typically focus on learning the statistical distribution of the data without incorporating domain-specific knowledge, something that can be critical in sensitive fields like healthcare and finance. In these domains, knowledge beyond simple statistical processes (e.g., age cannot be negative) may be necessary. To address this, recent research has explored generating synthetic tabular data using extensively pre-trained LLMs (e.g, GPT-4, Claude, Grok), which can, in principle, encode rich, domain-specific semantics acquired during pre-training. These LLM-based approaches generally fall into two categories: prompt-based methods, where the model is guided to produce synthetic samples through carefully engineered natural language prompts[122], and fine-tuning methods, where the LLM itself is adapted using real tabular data to better align with the specific tasks or distributions[123]. All the strategies for synthetic tabular data generation discussed so far, from statistical models to LLM-based approaches, will be explored in greater depth in the Literature Review. This section was intended to provide a general introduction and contextual foundation for the techniques presented throughout the thesis.

While recent advancements such as diffusion models and LLM-based approaches show considerable promise, much of the practical progress in synthetic tabular data generation has been driven by tailored adoptions of GANs and VAEs. In particular, this thesis will focus on two representative models: CTGAN and TVAE, which will be discussed next.

1.3.1 CTGAN and TVAE

Conditional Tabular GAN (CTGAN) and Tabular Variational Autoencoder (TVAE) were first introduced by Xu et al.[124] to address specific challenges in synthetic tabular data generation. Specifically, they were designed to handle the presence of multi-modal distributions in continuous columns, something that earlier models often failed to capture, as well as the common issue of class imbalance in discrete columns, which can hinder accurate modeling.

Lei Xu et al. introduce three key technical innovations in the CTGAN framework: Mode-Specific Normalization, a Conditional Generator, and a Training-by-Sampling strategy. Mode-Specific Normalization refers to CTGAN’s use of Variational Gaussian Mixture Models (VGM) to preprocess continuous columns. Rather than employing simple min-max scaling, as often seen in classic GAN implementations, each continuous column is modeled as a mixture of Gaussians. Each value is normalized according to the “mode” (Gaussian component) it most likely belongs to. For each continuous column C_i , the use of a VGM helps to estimate the number of modes m_i and fits a mixture of Gaussians to the data. The learned distribution is then expressed as

$$\mathcal{P}_{C_i}(c_{i,j}) = \sum_{k=1}^{m_i} \mu_k \mathcal{N}(c_{i,j}; \eta_k, \phi_k), \quad (1.4)$$

where μ_k , η_k and ϕ_k are the weight, mean and standard deviation of the k -th Gaussian component, respectively. For each value $c_{i,j}$, CTGAN computes the likelihood p_k that it belongs to each component, samples a mode according to this distribution, and normalizes the value with respect to the selected mode. The result is encoded as a concatenation of a one-hot vector $\beta_{i,j}$ indicating the sampled mode, and a scalar $\alpha_{i,j} = \frac{c_{i,j} - \eta_k}{4\phi_k}$ representing the position of the value within the mode.

Another significant innovation of CTGAN is the Conditional Generator, designed to address the class imbalance issue commonly found in tabular datasets. Unlike traditional GANs that generate rows unconditionally, CTGAN generates data conditioned on specific values of discrete columns. For example, suppose a table includes a categorical column labeled "Education" with categories such as "High School", "Bachelor", and "Master". CTGAN may fix a specific category, say "Master", during certain training iterations and condition the generator to produce rows with this attribute. Formally, let D_i be the i -th discrete columns and $D_{i^*} = k^*$ be the selected condition. The generator is then trained to match the conditional distribution $P_G(row|D_{i^*} = k^*)$ to the real data distribution $P(row|D_{i^*} = k^*)$. To implement this conditioning, CTGAN appends a *conditional vector* to the generator's input, which is a binary mask vector constructed from the one-hot encoding of the discrete columns. The mask vector $m(k)$ activates only when both the column index i and the category k match the selected condition. All the mask vectors for a row are concatenated to form the conditional vector *cond*. During training, the generator aims to reconstruct the target mask d_{i^*} (i.e., the one-hot vector indicating the condition) by minimizing the cross-entropy between the generated \hat{d}_{i^*} and the true mask m_{i^*} . This approach not only ensures that the generator faithfully reproduces the conditioned attribute, but also enables the model to learn the conditional distribution of the remaining features given $D_{i^*} = k^*$, resulting in improved fidelity and diversity, particularly in underrepresented categories.

Accompanying the conditional generator, CTGAN introduces a Training-by-Sampling strategy to ensure balanced and effective training across all discrete categories. In traditional GAN training, if data is sampled uniformly at random, rare categories in discrete columns may be underrepresented, leading to poor generation quality for those categories. To mitigate this, CTGAN selectively conditions the generator on a category k^* from a randomly chosen discrete column D_{i^*} , and subsequently draws only real samples matching that condition to update the discriminator. The procedure involves constructing a probability mass function (PMF) over the categories in the chosen column D_{i^*} , where the PMF is proportional to the logarithm of each category's frequency, ensuring exploration of rare categories while still accounting for data distribution. Once a category k^* is sampled according to the PMF, a binary mask vector m_{i^*} is created, with the k^* -th component set to one, and all others to zero. Similarly to what happens for the conditional generator described above, these masks across all discrete columns are concatenated to form the conditional vector *cond*. During training, both the generator and the discriminator use *cond*,

with the generator producing rows conditioned on $D_{i^*} = k^*$, and the discriminator updated using real rows that satisfy the same condition.

Regarding its architecture, CTGAN employs the Wasserstein GAN objective with gradient penalty (WGAN-GP)[125] to ensure stable training, and incorporates PacGAN[126], which modifies the discriminator to jointly evaluate multiple samples, thereby further mitigating mode collapse. The generator receives as input a noise vector z concatenated with the previously described condition vector, and produces synthetic rows accordingly. The discriminator then attempts to distinguish between real and synthetic data. Thanks to mode-specific normalization, the generator’s outputs for continuous features can be accurately mapped back to the original data space, preserving the true distributions. The exact architecture, adapted and implemented for the purpose of this thesis, will be presented in greater detail in the method section.

In the same paper where CTGAN was introduced, Xu et al.[124] also proposed the Tabular Variational Autoencoder (TVAE), a generative model that adapts the VAE framework to handle specific challenges of tabular data. TVAЕ employs the same preprocessing pipeline used in CTGAN: categorical columns are one-hot encoded, and continuous columns are transformed using Mode-Specific Normalization. The encoder maps these preprocessed inputs to a latent representation z , and the decoder reconstructs the original row by outputting either distribution parameters or logits, depending on the column type. For continuous variables, the decoder typically predicts the parameters of a Gaussian distribution, and for categorical variables, it outputs softmax logits corresponding to the one-hot encoded classes.

TVAЕ is trained by maximizing the Evidence Lower Bound (ELBO), balancing a reconstruction loss with a KL divergence regularization term that encourages the posterior $q_\phi(z|x)$ to stay as close to the prior $p(z)$. This loss formulation allows the model to learn a joint representation of mixed-type features within a coherent latent space. One practical advantage of TVAЕ over adversarial approaches like CTGAN lies in its stability during training. In fact, VAEs don’t require balancing a generator and a discriminator, making convergence more reliable. Despite its relative simplicity, Xu et al.[124] showed that TVAЕ can be competitive with GAN-based models for generating high-fidelity synthetic tabular data when properly tuned.

As described above, both the generator and discriminator in CTGAN, as well as the encoder and decoder in TVAЕ, are implemented using standard feedforward neural networks, commonly referred to as Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs)[127]. MLPs have long been a foundational architecture in deep learning, characterized by layers of interconnected nodes (neurons). In this framework, the activation functions, such as ReLU or sigmoid, are fixed and applied at the nodes, while the learnable parameters are the weights assigned to the edges between layers.

Recently, Liu et al.[128] introduced a novel architecture called Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs), which ”reverses”, in a certain sense, the MLPs paradigm. In KANs, the activation functions are no longer fixed at the nodes but are instead replaced by learnable univariate activation functions placed on the edges.

This simple change in structure led to improved performance and interpretability across a range of tasks compared to traditional MLPs. Despite their promising results, KANs remain a recent innovation, and their application in the context of synthetic tabular data generation is still underexplored. In light of this, the following section will take a closer look at the key properties of KANs, laying the groundwork for the experimental aims and scope of this thesis.

1.4 Enter KANs

Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs) are motivated by a foundational result in functional representation theory, the *Kolmogorov-Arnold representation theorem*, which provides a mathematically sound and elegant basis for their architectural design. This contrasts with classical MLPs, whose theoretical foundation lies in the *Universal Approximation Theorem*,²⁴ which guarantees the ability to approximate functions arbitrarily well, but not exactly or constructively, as KAN are theoretically capable of doing.

The Kolmogorov-Arnold representation theorem is as follows:

Kolmogorov–Arnold Representation Theorem. *If f is a multivariate continuous function on a bounded domain, then it can be written as a finite composition of continuous functions of a single variable and the binary operation of addition. More specifically, for a smooth $f : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$,*

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = f(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{q=1}^{2n+1} \Phi_q \left(\sum_{p=1}^n \phi_{q,p}(x_p) \right), \quad (1.5)$$

where $\phi_{q,p} : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\Phi_q : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

In more intuitive terms, Equation 1.5 expresses the function f as a composition of two layers. The inner layer consists of univariate functions $\phi_{q,p}(x_p)$ applied to each input dimension x_p , followed by summation across p . The outer layer consists of univariate functions Φ_q applied to these intermediate results (i.e., summation across p) and summed across q . When considering tabular data, the input vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ can be interpreted as a row in a dataset, and each x_p corresponds to a column feature. Thus, the inner summation effectively encodes a transformation across the columns, and the outer summation aggregates the resulting features.

Liu et al. 1.5 corresponds to a two-layer KAN. Specifically, the inner summation forms a KAN layer with $n_{in} = n$ and $n_{out} = 2n + 1$, while the outer summation corresponds to a KAN layer with $n_{in} = 2n + 1$ and $n_{out} = 1$. Although the classical Kolmogorov-Arnold theorem guarantees representation using only

²⁴The *Universal Approximation Theorem* states that a feedforward neural network with a single hidden layer containing a finite number of neurons can approximate any continuous function on compact subsets of \mathbb{R}^n , under mild assumptions on the activation function. However, it guarantees only an approximation, not an exact or constructive representation. For a deeper discussion, see [129, 130].

two such layers, it does not suggest how to extend this architecture to deeper and wider networks. Liu et al. addressed this using an analogy with MLPs. In fact, to generalize KANs beyond the scope of the original theorem, one can simply stack multiple KAN layers, just as MLPs achieve expressive power through depth. A schematic illustration of a two-input KAN architecture is provided in 1.3.

Figure 1.3: A schematic of a KAN with two input variables and stacked KAN layers.

In contrast to MLPs, where the computation at each layer is typically expressed as a matrix-vector product followed by a fixed nonlinearity (e.g. sigmoid, ReLU, Tanh, etc.) applied element-wise, KANs replace these fixed nonlinearities with learnable univariate functions located on the edges of the network. To make this distinction more concrete, we can represent the functional transformation at a layer of a KAN as a matrix where each element is a function applied to one input coordinate. More precisely, given an input vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d)$ the transformation at a given layer can be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \phi_{1,1}(x_1) & \phi_{1,2}(x_2) & \dots & \phi_{1,d}(x_d) \\ \phi_{2,1}(x_1) & \phi_{2,2}(x_2) & \dots & \phi_{2,d}(x_d) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \phi_{m,1}(x_1) & \phi_{m,2}(x_2) & \dots & \phi_{m,d}(x_d) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.6)$$

here, each row i corresponds to one output neuron in the current layer, and each column j corresponds to one input feature x_j . Each entry $\phi_{i,j}(x_j)$ is a learnable activation function, which serves as the counterpart to the scalar weights $w_{i,j}$ in traditional MLPs. Thus, instead of computing weighted sums of the inputs as in MLPs, each output neuron in a KAN aggregates the values of

these univariate function evaluations via a simple summation (e.g., a node):

$$y_i = \sum_{j=1}^d \phi_{i,j}(x_j) \quad (1.7)$$

Importantly, each learnable function $\phi_{i,j}$ in a KAN is represented as a B-spline. In simple terms, B-splines (short for Basis splines) are piecewise polynomial functions composed of lower-degree polynomial segments smoothly joined together. These functions are defined over a sequence of intervals, called knots, and are controlled by a set of coefficients or control points.

Liu et al. chose B-splines due to several advantageous properties that make them well-suited for the KAN framework. First, B-splines offer excellent approximation capability in low-dimensional settings, which aligns with the fact that each $\phi_{i,j}$ in a KAN is a univariate function. Second, they provide local control, meaning that changing one control point affects only a limited region of the function, enabling localized adjustments and improving interpretability. Unlike MLPs, where changes in weights often affect the entire function globally. Finally, and most importantly for deep learning, B-splines are continuous and differentiable, ensuring that the backpropagation algorithm remains valid and efficient.

Mathematically, the B-spline basis functions $N_{i,j}(t)$ are defined recursively as follows:

$$N_{i,0}(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } t_i \leq t < t_{i+1}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (1.8)$$

$$N_{i,j}(t) = \frac{t - t_i}{t_{i+j} - t_i} N_{i,j-1}(t) + \frac{t_{i+j+1} - t}{t_{i+j+1} - t_{i+1}} N_{i+1,j-1}(t), \quad (1.9)$$

where $j = 1, 2, \dots, p$ and t_i are the knot values. Then, the B-spline curve is defined as:

$$\mathbf{C}(t) = \sum_{i=0}^n \mathbf{P}_i N_{i,p}(t), \quad (1.10)$$

where \mathbf{P}_i are the control points and $N_{i,p}(t)$ are the basis functions of degree p . This formulation yields a continuous and differentiable function ideal for learning in neural architectures like KANs.

Thus, the training process for KANs follows the same structural workflow as that of MLPs, with the key difference being that the learnable parameters are the B-spline functions on edges rather than scalar weights:

Figure 1.4: KAN training process: structurally identical to MLPs but with B-spline-based learnable functions.

Despite sharing a similar training framework with MLPs, KANs exhibit unique architectural characteristics that present both opportunities and challenges, especially in view of their potential integration into tabular generative models, which is the central theme of this thesis. KANs have shown particular strength in tasks involving moderately sized input dimensions, largely due to their use of learnable univariate B-spline functions on the edges. These functions allow for highly flexible and localized representations, making KANs promising candidates for synthetic tabular data generation, where achieving accurate reconstruction of specific categorical or continuous features is crucial, and the number of features remains within a manageable range. Moreover, KANs are naturally interpretable. Each univariate function can be individually visualized and analyzed, offering a level of transparency that is especially valuable in high-stakes fields such as healthcare and finance, where the interpretability of synthetic data generators can be as important as their performance.

Nevertheless, these same design choices also introduce certain drawbacks. The reliance on spline-based functions increases the number of learnable parameters and often necessitates more careful hyperparameter tuning. This typically results in longer training times compared to standard MLPs, although KANs tend to require fewer layers to achieve comparable performance, potentially off-

setting this disadvantage. It is important to notice, however, that KANs are a recent development, and their application to tasks traditionally dominated by MLPs is still largely underexplored. For instance, in the previous sections, we reviewed the architectures of GANs and VAEs, noting that both typically rely on plain MLPs for their generator-discriminator and encoder-decoder components, respectively. In the context of tabular data generation, CTGAN and TVAE, as introduced by Xu et al.[124], represent two prominent examples where MLPs are used in carefully adapted forms to address unique challenges of tabular data. This naturally raises a question: What happens if we replace these MLPs with KANs in the CTGAN and TVAE architectures? This question is the heart of this thesis, and will be outlined in more detail in the following, final section of this introductory chapter.

1.5 Research Aims and Scope

As discussed in previous sections, GAN-based and VAE-based models such as CTGAN and TVAE have demonstrated strong performance in the generation of synthetic tabular data. However, these models rely on Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs), the most commonly used neural network architecture in machine learning to date. With the recent introduction of Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs), this longstanding paradigm may be challenged. Yet, due to their novelty, KANs have not been extensively studied in the context of synthetic tabular data generation.

Motivated by this gap, and by the author’s personal curiosity, this thesis aims to investigate whether replacing MLPs with KANs in the generator-discriminator framework of CTGAN and the encoder-decoder structure of TVAE can lead to improvements in the quality of synthetic tabular data. "Quality" is an ambiguous term in the context of synthetic data, and in this context it refers to two key criteria: fidelity and utility. Fidelity measures how closely the statistical properties of synthetic data resemble those of real data, and utility evaluates how well the synthetic data can replace real data for downstream machine learning tasks.

This investigation is guided by the following key research questions:

1. Do KAN-based variants of CTGAN and TVAE retain or improve fidelity and utility compared to their MLP-based counterparts?
2. Can KANs effectively model the complex joint distributions characteristic of real-world tabular datasets?
3. What trade-offs arise in terms of training time, stability, and architectural complexity when using KANs instead of MLPs?

To address these questions, the KAN-based models will be benchmarked using the same evaluation metrics proposed by Xu et al. in their introduction of CTGAN and TAVE[124]. Furthermore, this thesis will introduce two custom

metrics: one for evaluating fidelity through statistical comparison, and another for assessing utility via the Train-on-Synthetic-Test-on-Real (TSTR) framework. Full details of these evaluation methods are provided in the Methods chapter.

Importantly, the scope of this thesis does not include altering the core architectures of CTGAN and TVAE beyond substituting MLPs with KANs. Nor does it aim to exhaustively optimize hyperparameters or perform extensive tuning for peak KAN performance. Rather, standard parameters from the reference KAN implementation are used to evaluate performance in a fair and reproducible manner.

Upon completion, the modified KAN-based models will be made publicly available as a Python package, easily installable with the *pip* command, along with basic usage tutorials to encourage further research and adoption.

The next chapter, the Literature Review, provides a more detailed overview of synthetic tabular data generation techniques, including statistical models, deep learning approaches, and emerging frameworks. Readers primarily interested in the experimental work may skip to the Methods chapter on page 69.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

Since the advent of computing and the foundational contributions by Rubin and Little in the early 1990s[19, 20], the research and development of techniques for synthetic data generation have advanced significantly. Among those, the generation of synthetic tabular data, data structured in a row-column format, has attracted particular attention across various sectors such as healthcare, finance, and social sciences, where access to structured, high-quality real-world data is often restricted[131].

As of today, four major categories of approaches can be identified in the literature: (i) statistical models, (ii) deep learning-based models, (iii) diffusion-based models, and (iv) large language models (LLM)-based techniques.

This chapter explores representative and influential models within each of these four categories. Due to the fast-paced evolution and breadth of the field, this should not be considered a comprehensive review. Rather, the goal is to provide a focused examination of important methods that have shaped synthetic tabular data generation, with particular attention to those relevant to the goals of this thesis. A final section is dedicated to reviewing the primary evaluation metrics and benchmarks used to assess synthetic data quality in the course of the years.

2.1 Statistical Models

Before the advent of deep learning, statistical models were among the first and most widely adopted approaches for synthetic data generation in classical machine learning. These methods rely on explicit parametrization and estimation of joint probability distributions to model data[132]. In the context of tabular data, three foundational statistical techniques are particularly noteworthy: Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs), Copulas, and Bayesian Networks. These were briefly introduced in the previous chapter and will now be discussed in greater detail. Additionally, specialized resampling techniques such as the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE)[87], which employ

interpolation-based strategies, will be reviewed at the end of this section. The following review of statistical methods for synthetic data generation draws significantly from the comprehensive survey by Bauer et al.[133], which provides an excellent overview of foundational approaches in the field.

2.1.1 Gaussian Mixture Models

Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) are a class of density estimation algorithms¹ traditionally used for unsupervised clustering tasks, but they can also serve as generative probabilistic models, as for instance, in the generation of synthetic tabular data. A GMM models the data as a weighted sum of N Gaussian distributions, also known as components. Each Gaussian component is defined by its own mean μ_i and covariance ρ_i and is associated with a mixing coefficient π_i that represents the probability of a data point being drawn from that component. These mixing coefficients satisfy the constraint $\sum_{i=1}^N \pi_i = 1$, ensuring that the model represents a valid probability distribution.

For univariate (one-dimensional) data (Fig.2.1), the parameters μ_i and ρ_i are scalar values. In the multivariate case, which is more relevant to tabular data, μ_i becomes a vector representing the mean of each feature, and ρ_i is a covariance matrix capturing feature dependencies. The probability that a given data point d belongs to the i -th Gaussian component is given by $P(d = i) = \pi_i$ and the likelihood of observing d under this component is $P(d | d = i, \mu_i, \rho_i) = \mathcal{N}(d | \mu_i, \rho_i)$, where $\mathcal{N}(\cdot)$ denotes the multivariate Gaussian density function. The visualization below is taken from the comprehensive survey by Bauer et al. [133].

Figure 2.1: Illustration of a one-dimensional Gaussian Mixture Model with three components

The parameters of a GMM are typically estimated using the Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm, which iteratively refines the model to maximize

¹A density estimation algorithm refers to a statistical technique used to estimate the probability density function (PDF) of a continuous random variable based on a finite set of observed data points. In simpler terms, it models how likely different values are to occur in a dataset.

the likelihood of the observed data:

- **Initialization:** Randomly initialize the mean μ_i , covariance ρ_i , and mixing coefficients π_i for each component.
- **Repeat until convergence:**
 - (i) **E-step (Expectation):** Compute the membership probability for each data point with respect to each component, effectively assigning soft cluster memberships.
 - (ii) **M-step (Maximization):** Update the parameters μ_i , ρ_i , and π_i based on the membership probabilities to maximize the overall data likelihood.

To mitigate the risk of convergence to suboptimal local maxima², it is common practice to train multiple GMMs with different random initializations and select the best-performing model based on log-likelihood[134]. This strategy is similar to that used in other unsupervised methods, such as K-Means clustering, where the optimal number of clusters is not known a priori and must be empirically determined[135].

Gaussian Mixture Models have been employed for various generative tasks, including image generation and speech synthesis[136, 137]. In the context of synthetic tabular data synthesis, one notable application is provided by YData, a widely recognized (though not fully open-source) synthetic data platform[138]. Their Python library includes a GMM-based synthesizer that enables users to generate tabular data[139]. In their implementation, once the GMM is trained using the Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm as described earlier, synthetic samples are generated by randomly selecting a component according to its learned mixing weights and drawing a sample from the corresponding Gaussian distribution. This process allows each synthetic record (i.e., a row in the dataset) to be sampled from the overall learned distribution, ensuring that the generated data mimics the statistical characteristics of the original dataset. However, an important limitation in their implementation is the need to manually specify which features are categorical and which are continuous before training the model. This preprocessing step is necessary because the model does not natively support mixed-type tabular inputs. While manageable in small datasets, this becomes impractical when the number of columns is large, requiring either manual inspection or additional scripting to identify and label feature types correctly. Furthermore, YData recommends that the input data be approximately Gaussian for optimal performance, which stems from the underlying assumption of GMMs, and so that the data is well modeled by a mixture of Gaussian distributions. In practice, however, real-world tabular datasets often deviate significantly from this assumption, and users typically lack prior knowledge about the distributional properties of their data, therefore limiting the effectiveness

²Notice that, unlike many machine learning algorithms that minimize a loss function, the EM algorithm for GMMs maximizes the likelihood of the observed data.

and applicability of this implementation of GMMs for general-purpose tabular data synthesis.

An alternative and hybrid approach has been proposed by Apellàiz et al.[140], who introduce a VAE-based architecture that incorporates a Bayesian Gaussian Mixture model (BGM)³ as part of the latent space. Their method is specifically designed to overcome the limitations of standard GMMs, which, as described above, often assume the data distribution to be strictly Gaussian. Without going into much detail, by using a BGM, their approach allows for a more expressive and flexible latent representation, capable of modeling continuous and categorical variables more effectively. The model demonstrated (on their benchmarks) superior performance to CTGAN and TVAE in terms of fidelity and utility, particularly in healthcare datasets. This study highlighted the potential of GMM-based methods when integrated within contemporary generative architectures, but further research is needed in this area to validate these findings.

2.1.2 Copulas

Copula-based methods model the joint distribution of multivariate tabular data by decoupling marginal distributions from their dependence structure[143]. The theoretical foundation of this approach is Sklar’s Theorem[108], which states that any multivariate cumulative distribution function (CDF) $F(z_1, \dots, z_d)$ can be expressed in terms of its univariate marginal CDFs $F_i(z_i)$ and a copula function C that captures the dependence among variables:

$$F(z_1, \dots, z_d) = C(F_1(z_1), \dots, F_d(z_d)). \quad (2.1)$$

Here, the copula C is a multivariate function that couples the marginals into a full joint distribution, enabling the modeling of complex dependencies independent of the marginal behavior. In practice, the process of generating synthetic data using copulas typically involves the following steps[144]:

1. **Marginal estimation:** Estimate the marginal CDF \hat{F}_i for each column i of the real data.
2. **Transformation to copula space:** Transform the data into a uniform latent space using $U_i = \hat{F}_i(Z_i)$, where $U_i \in [0, 1]$.
3. **Dependence modeling:** Fit a copula \hat{C} to the transformed uniform data to capture inter-variable dependencies.
4. **Sampling and inverse transformation:** Generate synthetic samples $(U_1, \dots, U_d) \sim \hat{C}$, then map each back to the original space by applying the inverse transform $Z_i = \hat{F}_i^{-1}(U_i)$.

³A Bayesian Gaussian Mixture model (BGM) extends the classical GMM by placing prior distributions over its parameters (means, covariances, and mixture weights), allowing the model to capture uncertainty and improve robustness, especially with limited or complex data. For a more comprehensive overview, see [141, 142].

This approach allows the marginals to remain flexible (e.g., non-parametric or empirical), while using copulas to model a wide range of dependency structures. Various families of copulas exist (e.g., Gaussian, Clayton, Gumbel, Frank), each with different characteristics regarding tail dependencies and symmetry⁴

The Gaussian copula is one of the most widely used and implemented approaches for synthetic tabular data modeling. Notably, Patki et al.[145] introduced the open-source package Synthetic Data Vault (SDV), which also employs Gaussian copulas to model inter-column dependencies in tabular data[146]. In their approach, each column is first transformed to a standard normal distribution to neutralize the influence of its original distributional shape. Subsequently, the covariance matrix of the resulting joint Gaussian copula is estimated. Synthetic rows are then generated by sampling from this multivariate normal distribution and applying the inverse transformation to map the values back to the original data space. One notable limitation of this method, shared with Gaussian Mixture Models, is that purely categorical fields cannot be directly processed, as the Gaussian copula operates in a continuous domain. To overcome this, the SDV framework encodes categorical values as ordinal numbers within the $[0,1]$ range, allowing them to be treated as continuous features within the copula framework.

Other notable applications of copula-based models for the generation of synthetic tabular data have emerged over the years. For instance, Houssou et al.[147] introduced a robust algorithm for metadata-informed synthesis of mixed continuous and categorical variables. Their approach successfully generates synthetic datasets that preserve both marginal distributions and inter-variable dependencies, outperforming methods like SMOTE (which will be explored in a later subsection) and autoencoders on their benchmarks. Similarly, Jutras-Dubé et al.[148] proposed a copula-based model to synthesize population-level survey data, achieving superior alignment with marginal distributions and complex joint dependencies compared to simpler methods such as Iterative Proportional Fitting⁵. In another application, Meyer et al.[149] demonstrated that copula-generated synthetic weather-climate data can enhance the performance of machine learning emulators, reducing the mean absolute error (MAE) by up to 62% in climate prediction tasks.

2.1.3 Bayesian Networks

Bayesian Networks (BNs) are a type of probabilistic graphical model where dependencies among variables are represented using a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG). In this structure, each node corresponds to a random variable, and each directed edge indicates a probabilistic dependency from a parent variable to its

⁴*Tail dependence* refers to the amount of dependence in the extreme values (tails) of the distributions (i.e., how likely it is for variables to jointly take on extreme high or low values.). *Symmetry* refers to whether the copulas treats upper and lower tails equally.

⁵Iterative Proportional Fitting (IPF) is a classical statistical method used to adjust multidimensional contingency tables to match known marginal totals.

child. These directed relationships capture how the value of a variable may be influenced by others. Each node is associated with a probability distribution, which can be either discrete or continuous, depending on the nature of the variable. A simple and widely used illustration of a Bayesian Network is provided in 2.2, which depicts the "Sprinkler" example, taken from [133].

Figure 2.2: Bayesian network with conditional probability tables for the classic "Sprinkler" example.

More formally, let $\mathbf{V} = \{V_j : j \in \{1, \dots, N\}\}$ represent the set of random variables in the network (i.e., nodes). For each variable V_j , let \mathbf{Pa}_j denote its parent nodes in the DAG, and $p(V_j | \mathbf{Pa}_j)$ its conditional probability distribution. Then, the joint distribution over all variables factorizes as

$$p(\mathbf{V}) = p(V_1, \dots, V_N) = \prod_{j=1}^N p(V_j | \mathbf{Pa}_j). \quad (2.2)$$

In practice, however, the structure of a Bayesian Network is often not known a priori and must be learned from the data. This presents two key challenges:

1. Defining a suitable metric to compare potential BN structures, and
2. Searching the space of possible structures in an efficient manner.

A common solution to the first challenge is to use the joint probability $p(D, S^h)$ of the data D and a hypothesized structure S^h , defined as:

$$\log p(D, S^h) = \log p(D | S^h) + \log p(S^h), \quad (2.3)$$

where $p(D | S^h)$ is the data likelihood given the structure, and $p(S^h)$ is the prior over structures. The Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC)[150] is often used to approximate the likelihood term $\log p(D | S^h)$, while prior knowledge or structure simplicity can guide the prior term $\log p(S^h)$. The second challenge, structure search, is an Nondeterministic Polynomial (NP)-hard⁶ problem due to the combinatorially large space of DAGs[152, 153]. Therefore, heuristic search strategies are typically used, such as greedy algorithms that iteratively add, remove, or reverse edges to improve the score until a local maximum is reached.

Bayesian Networks have found diverse applications in the generation of synthetic tabular data, particularly for their effectiveness in preserving the privacy of the original datasets, especially when combined with Differential Privacy techniques[154]. A prominent contribution in this area is PrivBayes, proposed by Zhang et al.[155], which introduces a differentially private mechanism for releasing high-dimensional data. The method begins by constructing a Bayesian Network N from a real dataset D , which serves as a compact representation of the attribute correlations in D . This network enables the approximation of the full data distribution using a set P of low-dimensional marginals derived from D . To ensure differential privacy, noise is then injected into these marginals rather than the full high-dimensional data. Using both the perturbed marginals and the structure of the Bayesian Network, PrivBayes reconstructs an approximate data distribution from which it samples synthetic records. By injecting noise into the low-dimensional marginals in P , rather than directly in the high-dimensional dataset D , Zhang et al. managed to effectively mitigate the well-known challenge in machine learning of the *curse of dimensionality*⁷. Empirical evaluations at the time of publication, in 2017, showed that PrivBayes significantly outperformed existing approaches in terms of data utility and accuracy across several real datasets.

In the healthcare domain, Tucker et al.[157] applied Bayesian Networks for synthetic patient tabular data generation, focusing on producing datasets that preserve both privacy and utility. In their study, they modeled heterogeneous medical data, comprising both continuous and discrete variables, using a probabilistic graphical model (i.e., a Bayesian Network). A key and particularly interesting contribution of their work lies in how they addressed the presence of missing data. To this end, they evaluated three strategies: omitting incomplete records, encoding missing values directly into the network structure, and using the Fast Causal Inference (FCI) algorithm[158] to impute missing values.

⁶A problem is said to be in the class NP (nondeterministic polynomial time) if a proposed solution can be verified in polynomial time. An NP-hard problem is at least as hard as the hardest problems in NP. This means that no known algorithm can solve all NP-hard problems efficiently (i.e., in polynomial time), and structure learning for Bayesian Networks falls into this category due to the enormous number of possible directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) that need to be evaluated. For readers intrigued by the deeper implications of such problems, and perhaps motivated by the \$1 million prize, see the Clay Mathematics Institute’s formulation of the P vs. NP Millennium Prize Problem [151].

⁷The Curse of Dimensionality (CoD) refers to the exponential increase in data sparsity and computational complexity as the number of dimensions (i.e., features) grows. See [156] for more details about the CoD.

Their results demonstrate that Bayesian Networks were able to generate synthetic datasets with high fidelity to the original data while minimizing the risk of patient re-identification.

In more recent years, Martins et al.[159] proposed a fully Bayesian framework for modeling and generating synthetic tabular data. Their approach makes use of the posterior predictive distribution to produce synthetic data samples, allowing for a principled form of uncertainty quantification⁸. This method, in fact, considers the full distributional uncertainty associated with the data generation process. To make this computationally feasible, they devise an efficient algorithm based on Monte Carlo techniques (See the Introduction chapter), which is used to approximate the posterior predictive distribution through repeated sampling. A central component of their methodology is the introduction of a flexible class of penalizing priors, designed to avoid overly complex Bayesian network structures, an issue previously discussed in this section. The framework was empirically evaluated on both simulated datasets and real-world applications, demonstrating the method’s practical utility and its ability to capture essential statistical properties of the original data in a controlled and interpretable manner.

2.1.4 Resampling Methods: SMOTE

A persistent problem in synthetic tabular data generation, as discussed in the introduction, is class imbalance, a scenario where some classes in the real dataset are significantly underrepresented. To continue with the previous example, this could correspond to rare diseases in a patient dataset. One of the most widely adopted techniques to address this issue by generating synthetic samples for the minority class is the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE).

Introduced by Chawla et al.[87], SMOTE addresses class imbalance by generating synthetic instances through interpolation between existing minority class samples. Unlike traditional oversampling, which often merely replicates existing minority instances and may lead to overfitting[160], SMOTE enhances variability by synthesizing new data points along the line segments connecting randomly selected pairs of minority class examples. Formally, given a minority instance x_i and one of its k nearest neighbors x_{zi} (also from the minority class), a new synthetic sample x_{new} is generated as:

$$x_{new} = x_i + \delta \cdot (x_{zi} - x_i), \tag{2.4}$$

where $\delta \in [0, 1]$ is a random scalar. This simple equation ensures that the generated point lies somewhere on the straight line segment between x_i and x_{zi} , thereby enriching the representation of the minority class in the feature space without introducing exact duplicates[161]. A 2D illustration of this interpolation is provided in Figure 2.3, Source: [162].

⁸*Uncertainty quantification* in this context refers to the process of estimating the degree of confidence or variability in model outputs. In Bayesian frameworks, this is typically achieved by sampling from the posterior predictive distribution, which captures the full range of plausible synthetic values given the uncertainty in model parameters and the observed data.

Figure 2.3: Illustration of SMOTE: the synthetic point x_{new} is interpolated between a minority class sample x_i and one of its nearest neighbors x_{z_i} in feature space.

After the introduction of SMOTE, numerous variants have been developed to address some of the limitations associated with the original algorithm[161]. Among the most notable is Borderline-SMOTE[163], which generates synthetic samples only in the "borderline" regions, i.e., areas where minority class instances are most vulnerable to misclassification. This focused oversampling helps improve classifier performance by reinforcing decision boundaries. Another important extension is SMOTE with Tomek Links[164]. In this method, synthetic instances are first generated using SMOTE, and then Tomek Links are applied to clean the dataset. A Tomek Link is a pair of instances from opposite classes that are each other's nearest neighbor. The presence of such pairs indicates potential overlap or noise near the decision boundary. Removing them improves class separability and reduces ambiguity. Similarly, SMOTE-ENN (Edited Nearest Neighbors)[165] combines SMOTE with a cleaning step where any instance (majority or minority) that is misclassified by its k -nearest neighbor is removed. This technique helps reduce overlapping regions and noise and can better isolate the minority class, especially in highly imbalanced datasets.

Other variants and applications of the techniques described above have been employed across various domains to address the issue of class imbalance. For instance, Kosolwattana et al.[166] introduced SASMOTE (Self-inspected Adaptive SMOTE), which leverages an adaptive nearest neighborhood selection algorithm to identify "visible" neighbors, those most likely to contribute to minority class boundaries. These are then used to generate new synthetic samples. The algorithm also incorporates an uncertainty elimination mechanism via self-

inspection to enhance the reliability of the generated instances. SASMOTE was applied to real-world healthcare datasets, including risk gene discovery and fatal congenital heart disease prediction (a setting analogous to the class imbalance example discussed earlier), showing improved performance metrics, such as the F1-score⁹, compared to traditional SMOTE-based methods.

In the financial sector, credit card fraud detection presents a significant challenge due to the extreme rarity of fraudulent transactions. To tackle this, Zhu et al.[167] proposed a hybrid approach combining SMOTE and Neural Networks (NN). They applied SMOTE to balance the training dataset by generating synthetic examples of the minority (fraudulent) class and then trained a feedforward neural network on the augmented data. The results showed that the NN trained with SMOTE significantly outperformed conventional models, achieving higher precision, recall, and F1-scores. Lastly, in the educational domain, another field affected by class imbalance, Sahlaoui et al.[168] conducted an empirical evaluation of SMOTE variants in predicting student academic performance. By combining different SMOTE techniques with classification algorithms such as Random Forests, they found that SMOTE-ENN yielded the best performance among the variants tested. Specifically, Random Forest models trained with SMOTE-ENN achieved superior accuracy, precision, and F1-scores.

These studies collectively highlight the effectiveness and adaptability of SMOTE and resampling techniques in diverse domains. They also underscore the practical advantages of statistical models in general, such as computational efficiency and interpretability. Nonetheless, these methods come with inherent limitations, which will be discussed in the next subsection.

2.1.5 Limitations of Statistical Models

All the statistical models discussed so far, Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs), Copulas, Bayesian Networks, and SMOTE, have proven to be valuable tools for generating synthetic tabular data, particularly for their well-known mathematical foundations, which offer greater interpretability and transparency. However, each of these models exhibits limitations that may hinder their effectiveness in handling complex, real-world datasets.

Starting with GMMs, the models assume that data points are generated from a mixture of several Gaussian distributions. This assumption greatly simplifies the modeling process, but it also introduces several challenges. First of all, the assumption of normality may not hold in real-world scenarios where the data exhibit non-Gaussian characteristics. GMMs are also sensitive to outliers. In fact, the presence of extreme data points can significantly distort the estimation of the means and covariances[169, 170, 171]. Like many other classical statistical models (e.g., Copulas), GMMs are inherently designed for continuous data and struggle to accurately represent categorical variables[140]. Furthermore, determining the optimal number of mixture components is a non-trivial task,

⁹The F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, defined as $F1 = \frac{2 \cdot \text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$.

often requiring prior domain knowledge or model selection techniques such as the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC)[150], which can be computationally intensive[172].

Similar to GMMs, copula-based models also present several limitations when applied to synthetic tabular data generation. One notable drawback shared with GMMs is their inability to natively handle categorical features. Therefore, additional preprocessing or hybrid approaches are typically required to accommodate such data types effectively, as implemented in the Open-Source SDV Python package[145, 146]. Moreover, Traditional copula models often assume a static dependence structure, which may fail to capture dynamic or time-varying relationships, particularly relevant in time-series datasets[173]. Gaussian copulas, which, as previously stated, are among the most widely used, face specific challenges as well. In particular, they struggle to capture tail dependencies accurately, limiting their effectiveness in domains such as risk management and finance, where modeling extreme events is critical[174]. Finally, the estimation and construction of high-dimensional copulas becomes increasingly computationally demanding as the number of variables grows. This scalability issue can lead to overfitting or model misspecification in large datasets[175].

Like the other statistical models discussed so far, Bayesian Networks (BNs) also exhibit important limitations. As highlighted in the section above, a central challenge in working with BNs is the complexity of structure learning. Determining the optimal structure of a BN is a Nondeterministic Polynomial (NP)-hard problem, making exact solutions computationally infeasible, especially as the number of variables increases[152, 153, 176]. Additionally, the performance of BNs is sensitive to data quality, particularly for accurate estimation of both structure and parameters. In many real-world scenarios, datasets often contain missing values or measurement errors, all of which could degrade the model’s performance[177].

To conclude this brief exploration of the limitations of statistical models, it is worth noting that the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE), while not a generative model per se, but rather a technique used in preprocessing for machine learning, also presents its own set of challenges. By generating synthetic samples close to existing minority class instances, SMOTE can increase the risk of overfitting, most of all when the minority class is poorly represented[178]. Furthermore, as SMOTE is typically applied feature-wise, it does not account for potential correlations between features, which can be crucial in various learning tasks. Lastly, in high-dimensional spaces, the concept of nearest neighbors becomes less meaningful due to the curse of dimensionality[179], diminishing the overall effectiveness of this approach[180].

In light of these limitations, and driven in part by the growing interest surrounding deep learning, the last decade has seen the emergence of a new generation of synthetic tabular data generators based on neural network architectures. The next section will focus on these deep-learning-based models, highlighting their contributions and methodologies.

2.2 Deep Learning Models

The vast majority of deep learning models aimed at generating synthetic tabular data have emerged in the past decade, largely inspired by the introduction of Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) and Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) as foundational generative frameworks[113]. Following the taxonomy proposed by Shi et al.[106], these models can be broadly categorized into four classes: (i) VAE-based models, (ii) Traditional GANs, (iii) Conditional GANs, and (iv) Differentially Private GANs. In the remainder of this section, each of these categories will be examined, giving a detailed overview of the deep learning models that have contributed to advancing the field of synthetic tabular data generation.

2.2.1 VAE-Based Models

As introduced in Chapter 1, Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) aim to learn a compact latent representation of the data by optimizing the negative Evidence Lower Bound (ELBO), defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{VAE}} = \mathbb{E}_{q_{\phi}(z|x)} [-\log p_{\theta}(x|z)] + \text{KL}(q_{\phi}(z|x) \| p(z)) \quad (2.5)$$

where $q_{\phi}(z|x)$ is the encoder network, $p_{\theta}(x|z)$ is the decoder network, and KL denotes the Kullback-Leibler divergence. For further details, refer back to Equation 1.3 in the introduction.

Chronologically, the first important, and still one of the most influential, VAE-based models for synthetic tabular data generation is the Tabular Variational Autoencoder (TVAE), introduced by Xu et al. in 2019[124]. The TVAЕ adapts the general VAE architecture to handle tabular data by tailoring the decoder’s output according to the column type, either continuous or categorical. A more detailed explanation of the general TVAЕ framework can be found again in Chapter 1.

Another approach to tackling the inherent heterogeneity of real-world tabular datasets was proposed by Ma et al.[181], who introduced VAEM. In this model, to properly handle mixed-type data with heterogeneous marginals, they proposed a two-stage modeling process. In the first stage, a separate VAE is trained independently for each data dimension x_{nd} , resulting in D models referred to as *marginal VAEs*. To capture inter-variable dependencies, a second-stage model, called the *dependency network*, is trained on top of the latent representations obtained from the first-stage encoders. Here, D denotes the number of features, N the number of samples, with x_{nd} being the value of the d -th feature for the n -th data point. This architecture enables VAEM to better handle heterogeneous data distributions and also missing values, while maintaining scalability in high-dimensional settings. Below is a graphical comparison between the standard VAE architecture and the VAEM model, as proposed by Ma et al.[181]. Since the mathematical formulation of VAEM falls outside the main scope of this thesis, those details are omitted. Readers interested in

a deeper understanding of the model and its training procedure are encouraged to consult the original paper [181].

Figure 2.4: Graphical representation of (a) a standard VAE and (b) the proposed VAEM model. Dashed arrows represent encoders and solid arrows represent decoders. Image reproduced from the original paper by Ma et al.

More recently, Liu et al.[182] introduced GOGGLE, a generative model designed to learn a graph-based relational structure to capture dependencies among features in tabular data, with VAEs as part of its learning framework. They hypothesize that sparse dependencies in tabular datasets can be more accurately modeled through an underlying relational structure, rather than conventional MLP-based approaches. To this end, they proposed a novel *message passing* scheme that operates over a learned graph, enabling the model to better capture heterogeneous variable relationships. This graph-based representation also allows for the injection of prior knowledge and regularization via the adjacency matrix. Since the underlying structure of real-world datasets is rarely known a priori, GOGGLE adopts an end-to-end architecture where the graph structure and the functional relationships are learned jointly. In fact, for this purpose, VAEs are employed to model the marginal distributions of individual variables while aligning them through a learned relational graph, thereby integrating structure learning into the generative process.

Although VAEs have demonstrated strong capabilities in modeling synthetic tabular data, much of the literature over the past decade has focused more on Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs). I hypothesize that this interest stems not only from the compelling results GANs have achieved in related generative domains such as image synthesis, but also from their more intuitive adversarial training framework, which may appeal particularly to the computer science research community.

2.2.2 Traditional GANs

After the introduction of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) by Goodfellow et al. in 2014[113], research in synthetic data generation accelerated

significantly. This momentum extends to the specific domain of tabular data, where researchers began adapting vanilla GANs to address the unique challenges posed by tabular data. In the years following GAN’s emergence, several model were proposed to adapt their architecture for tabular data generation.

One of the earliest models to adapt the vanilla GAN architecture for tabular data generation was TGAN, introduced by Xu et al.[183]. In this model, the generator employs a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)¹⁰ network to generate each column of a data row, aiming to effectively capture dependencies between features. The discriminator is implemented as a standard multi-layer perceptron (MLP), consistent with the original GAN formulation. A central challenge addressed by TGAN is the heterogeneous nature of tabular data. To manage this, the authors introduced specific preprocessing strategies for the different data types in a possible dataset. Continuous variables are modeled using Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs), more details about GMMs can be found in the previous section, to capture multimodal distributions before being transformed into a generator-compatible format. Categorical variables, on the other hand, are one-hot encoded to align with the MLP architecture used throughout the model. Xu et al. evaluated TGAN on several real-world datasets, demonstrating that, at that time, it outperformed traditional statistical approaches in preserving data utility. However, the model also presented limitations. In fact, the sequential column-wise generation via LSTMs can be computationally expensive, and one-hot encoding may lead to high-dimensional, non-scalable parameters, especially when handling high-cardinality categorical features (i.e., columns with several classes).

In the same year TGAN was introduced, another significant early contribution to GAN-based tabular data synthesis was proposed by Park et al.[185], under the name of table-GAN. The core innovation of this approach lies in the use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to model feature dependencies, drawing inspiration from the field of computer vision and, in particular, from the Deep Convolutional GAN (DCGAN) architecture[186]. To enable this, the authors proposed treating tabular data as a 2D "image-like" structure, thereby allowing CNNs to be employed in both the generator and discriminator networks. In table-GAN, each row of the dataset is reshaped into a 2D matrix so it can be processed by convolutional layers. This design enables the model to capture spatial correlations among features, which the authors argue can be advantageous when modeling structured tabular datasets. The generator learns to produce such matrix-shaped synthetic samples, and the discriminator is trained to distinguish between real matrices, constructed from actual data, and synthetic ones, following the standard adversarial learning framework. One of table-GAN’s key contributions is the inclusion of an *information loss* term in the GAN objective function (Equation 1.2). This term encourages the generator to produce data samples that preserve the semantic properties of the original dataset. To enforce this, the model incorporates an auxiliary classifier

¹⁰LSTMs are a class of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) capable of learning long-range dependencies in sequential data. See [184] for more details.

trained to predict the class labels (when available) of both real and synthetic data, ensuring label-consistent generation. Park et al. evaluated table-GAN on multiple datasets using the *Train on Synthetic, Test on Real* (TSTR) framework, a methodology that will be discussed in greater detail in Chapter 3. The results showed that machine learning models trained on synthetic data generated by table-GAN achieved comparable performance to those trained on real data, indicating high utility of the synthetic samples. Despite the promising results, reshaping tabular data into image-like matrices introduces certain limitations. The spatial inductive bias¹¹ inherent to CNNs may not align well with the unordered nature of tabular features. Consequently, the reshaping process can lead to reduced interpretability and potential distortion of inter-feature relationships.

The problem of accuracy is not the only concern when generating synthetic tabular data. In fact, some studies have focused not only on preserving the fidelity and utility of the original dataset, but also on ensuring *fairness*¹². On this end, Rajabi et al.[187] proposed TabFairGAN, with the goal of designing a GAN-based framework capable of generating synthetic data that is both accurate and fair. TabFairGAN introduces a two-phase training process. In the first phase, a standard GAN setup is used to learn the distribution of the real data and generate realistic synthetic samples. Then, in the second phase, the training objective is modified by introducing fairness constraints into the loss function (mathematical details are omitted here, as they fall outside the scope of this thesis). In simple terms, these constraints penalize the generator when the synthetic data encodes biased correlations between sensitive attributes and target outcomes. The model was evaluated on datasets such as the UCI Adult Income dataset and demonstrated strong performance in improving fairness metrics (e.g., demographic parity) without significantly compromising accuracy. This makes TabFairGAN one of the earliest attempts to incorporate fairness into tabular data generation.

A more recent advancement addressing the challenge of capturing inter-feature dependencies in tabular data was proposed by Zhao et al.[188], who introduced Fourier Conditional Tabular GAN (FCT-GAN). This model presents several architectural innovations over traditional GAN-based models for structured data. One of the core contributions is the use of feature tokenization, which transforms tabular data into a sequence of token-like embeddings. This approach was inspired by the seminal work of Vaswani et al.[189] on Transformers. In particular, FCT-GAN draws inspiration from its application in Natural Language Processing (NLP), where each token typically represents a word or a subword unit¹³. In the context of FCT-GAN, each token corresponds to a

¹¹A *spatial inductive bias* refers to the assumption that nearby elements in the input data are more strongly related (e.g., pixels in an image), which is generally true for images but in arbitrarily ordered tabular features.

¹²Fairness in this context refers to the absence of bias in the synthetic data with respect to sensitive attributes such as race, gender, or age. This means that models trained on synthetic data should not produce discriminatory outcomes when evaluated on these groups.

¹³Various tokenization techniques exist in NLP, see [190] for a broad overview.

tabular feature (i.e., a column in the dataset), allowing the model to process tabular data as a sequence and to capture inter-feature dependencies in a way analogous to how Transformers capture contextual relationships between words in a sentence. Furthermore, instead of using standard MLPs as a generator and a discriminator for the GAN, FCT-GAN uses Fourier networks[191]. Thanks to the use of Fourier feature mappings to encode positional information and enrich the representations of feature interactions, the model manages to capture complex dependencies that are often present in real-world tabular datasets. The generator utilizes these Fourier-based transformations to produce more expressive synthetic samples, while the discriminator evaluates the authenticity of these samples in a conditional manner, integrating label information into the adversarial process.

Indeed, another distinguishing feature of FCT-GAN is its conditional training framework, which enables the generation of data conditioned on specific feature values. Empirical evaluations demonstrate that FCT-GAN outperforms earlier approaches across a variety of tabular datasets, particularly in preserving inter-feature dependencies. Nonetheless, this architectural complexity, due to the incorporation of tokenization and Fourier layers, may also introduce greater computational overhead during training compared to earlier models like TGAN and table-GAN.

While FCT-GAN utilizes conditional training to improve tabular synthesis, the concept of *conditional GANs* itself predates this model and will be discussed in the next subsection.

2.2.3 Conditional GANs

One of the main limitations of traditional statistical models (e.g., Copulas) and many early GAN-based approaches lies in their ability to control or guide the generation process according to specific attributes in the data. In particular, they cannot easily enforce desired values for certain columns, such as generating samples belonging to a specific class, making them less suitable for tasks involving highly imbalanced datasets or class-conditional generation. To address this limitation, the Conditional GAN (cGAN) framework was proposed by Mirza et al.[192], and further explored in tabular data generation in works such as [193, 194]. This framework augments both the generator and the discriminator with a conditional vector c , allowing the model to generate data conditioned on specific external information, as for example, class labels or feature subsets. In the cGAN setting, the original GAN loss function (see Equation 1.2) is extended to include the conditional vector as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_G \max_D V(D, G) = & \mathbb{E}_{x, c \sim p_{\text{data}}(x, c)} [\log D(x, c)] \\ & + \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_z(z), c \sim p(c)} [\log(1 - D(G(z, c), c))] \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

Here, x represents real data samples, z is the random noise vector sampled from a prior $p_z(z)$, and $c \in C$ is the conditional vector sampled from the label distribution $p(c)$. The discriminator receives both the data (real or synthetic)

and the conditional vector c , and must decide whether the input is real or fake. The generator, on the other hand, learns to produce samples $G(z, c)$ that not only look realistic to the discriminator, but also align with the condition c .

The loss function described above, however, might sometimes struggle to converge properly, especially when the discriminator becomes too dominant early in training[195]. This can lead to unstable gradients and hinder the generator’s ability to learn. To tackle this challenge, early cGAN-based models explored alternative formulations of the loss function. For example, Yu et al.[196] proposed cWGAN, which integrates the Wasserstein distance¹⁴ into the conditional GAN framework. The key idea of cWGAN is to replace the original loss with a formulation based on the Wasserstein-1 distance, aiming to provide a more stable and informative training signal. This method demonstrated to mitigate problems such as mode collapse¹⁵ and poor convergence behavior. In cWGAN, the generator and discriminator both receive conditional information as in a classic cGAN. Experimental results exhibit that cWGAN was able to generate synthetic data with improved diversity and fidelity compared to previous GAN-based approaches.

While cWGAN addressed training instability by introducing the Wasserstein loss into the conditional GAN framework, other researchers explored different strategies to improve tabular synthesis quality. Among these, Zhao et al.[198] proposed CTAB-GAN, which introduces the information loss and classification loss to the conditional GAN objective to better capture feature distributions and label consistency. The information loss penalizes deviations between the marginal distributions of real and synthetic features, thereby guiding the generator to produce samples that closely reflect the original data’s distribution characteristics. The classification loss, on the other hand, encourages the generator to produce synthetic samples that are semantically consistent with their associated label (i.e., the condition c in a classical cGAN). This is achieved by introducing an auxiliary classifier trained on real data, which is then used to evaluate whether the generated samples yield the correct label predictions. By penalizing discrepancies between the assigned and predicted labels, the classification loss enforces a stronger coupling between features and target variables during training. As already seen in the introduction (Chapter 1), when discussing the CTGAN model[124], CTAB-GAN also applies the mode-specific normalization to preprocess continuous features according to their modality. Moreover, the authors design a novel conditional vector that efficiently encodes both categorical and continuous columns, while also accounting for skewed feature distributions. In their empirical evaluations, Zhao et al. demonstrated that CTAB-GAN outperforms earlier GAN-based models such as table-GAN[185]

¹⁴The Wasserstein distance (also known as Earth Mover’s Distance) measures how much “effort” it takes to move probability mass from one distribution to match another. In the context of GANs, it provides a more stable and smooth measure of how different the real and generated data distributions are, which helps avoid issues like vanishing gradients during training. For a more rigorous explanation, see [197].

¹⁵Mode collapse in Generative Adversarial Networks refers to a situation where the generator produces a limited range of outputs (close to the modes), failing to capture the full diversity of the training data’s distribution.

across multiple benchmark datasets. The model achieves superior results in both statistical fidelity and downstream machine learning utility, as measured by the previously mentioned Train on Synthetic, Test on Real (TSTR) evaluation framework.

So far, the discussion of these models has focused on single-table generation. However, even if not the core of this thesis, it is important to mention the presence of models that generate multi-table data (i.e., relational databases). In this sense, RC-TGAN, proposed by Gueye et al.[199], represents one of the earliest attempts to extend conditional GANs to the multi-table setting. The model is specifically designed to generate relational data by taking into account both entity and foreign key relationships. To achieve this, RC-TGAN employs a hierarchical conditional generation strategy, in which synthetic data for child tables is generated conditionally on the synthetic records of their parent tables, ensuring referential integrity and consistency across related tables. A key innovation in RC-TGAN is the extension of conditional information to include ancestor features, ranging from parent to, optionally, grandparent tables, during the generation of child table rows. This design allows the generator to preserve the structural dependencies and statistical correlations that exist across different levels of the relational schema. The experimental results presented by the authors show that RC-TGAN generates synthetic relational databases that are more consistent and useful for downstream tasks compared to baseline methods, particularly in preserving foreign key relationships and realistic inter-table correlations.

Many other models have adopted the cGAN framework for generating conditional synthetic tabular data, such as OCT-GAN[200], which will not be discussed in further detail. Furthermore, the CTGAN[124] model, since it constitutes a core topic of this thesis, has already been introduced extensively in Chapter 1 and will not be reiterated here.

At the time of writing, the integration of KANs into GAN frameworks remains largely underexplored. Only a few preliminary attempts can be found in the literature or publicly available GitHub repository[201, 202, 203], and these efforts are still in the early stages. Even more notably, I was not able to identify any implementations of KAN-based architectures applied to synthetic tabular data generation. For this reason, the present section does not include a discussion on KAN-GAN models. As stated in Chapter 1, this gap in the literature represents one of the key motivations for the present thesis, which focuses on the implementation of KAN within the CTGAN and TVAE frameworks (See Chapter 1).

The remainder of this section will now turn to models whose primary objective is to preserve data privacy, specifically through the use of a technique briefly introduced in the previous chapter: Differential Privacy (DP).

2.2.4 Differentially Private GANs

The core idea behind Differential Privacy (DP) is to ensure that the presence or absence of any single individual in the training dataset has a negligible impact

on the output of the algorithm. In the context of synthetic data generation, this is typically achieved by adding a carefully calibrated amount of noise during the training process, so that the synthetic data produced remains statistically useful while preventing the disclosure of information specific to any individual data point. In many recent applications of deep learning models for synthetic tabular data generation, the Differentially Private Stochastic Gradient Descent (DP-SGD) algorithm[204, 106] has become a widely adopted mechanism to enforce formal privacy guarantees during training. The central idea behind DP-SGD is to limit the contribution of individual data points to each training step by first applying gradient clipping to the gradient and then adding calibrated Gaussian noise. Formally, during each iteration t , the gradient g_t^i computed for each individual training example is first clipped using an ℓ_2 -norm threshold C to ensure bounded sensitivity:

$$\text{clip}(g_t^i, C) = g_t^i \cdot \min\left(1, \frac{C}{\|g_t^i\|_2}\right). \quad (2.7)$$

The clipped gradients are then averaged across the minibatch and perturbed with Gaussian noise drawn from $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2 C^2 \mathbf{I})$:

$$\bar{g}_t = \frac{1}{L} \left(\sum_{i=1}^L \text{clip}(g_t^i, C) \right) + \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2 C^2 \mathbf{I}). \quad (2.8)$$

Here, σ controls the scale of the noise and thus determines the trade-off between privacy and utility, also mentioned in Chapter 1. The identity matrix \mathbf{I} ensures that the added noise is isotropic¹⁶, thereby treating all gradient components equally. This procedure guarantees that the impact of any single data sample on the model’s parameter is statistically limited, which is the basis for achieving differential privacy.

The model that first applied this algorithm (DP-SGD) to the original GAN architecture is DPGAN[204]. Xie et al. designed this framework to enforce Differential privacy during training by injecting Gaussian noise into the gradients of the discriminator network. More specifically, during each training iteration, the per-sample gradients are first clipped using an ℓ_2 -norm threshold to ensure bounded sensitivity, and then perturbed by calibrated Gaussian noise before being used to update the model parameters, exactly as described in Equation 2.8. By applying this mechanism, DPGAN ensures that the influence of any individual data point on the discriminator’s updates is limited, thus providing a Differential Privacy guarantee. As for what concerns the generator, it does not directly incorporate noise during training, and its updates are influenced only indirectly via feedback from the differentially private discriminator. In this way, DPGAN could, in principle, maintain the fidelity of the generated samples while still satisfying the overall privacy constraints. Experimental evaluations conducted by the authors demonstrate that DPGAN is capable of generating with

¹⁶Isotropic noise refers to noise that has the same variance in all directions, ensuring that no particular parameter or gradient direction is disproportionately affected.

reasonable quality across a variety of datasets, including MNIST¹⁷ and MIMIC-III (electronic health records). Nonetheless, since DPGAN was not specifically designed for tabular data, its performance on high-dimensional, mixed-type data remains limited compared to more recent tabular-specific models.

Other algorithms besides DP-SGD have also been implemented for the generation of tabular synthetic data. A notable example can be found in PATE-GAN[205], which introduces a fundamentally different approach to differential privacy by adopting the Private Aggregation of Teacher Ensembles (PATE) framework[206]. Instead of perturbing gradients during training, as in DP-SGD, PATE-GAN achieves privacy by replacing the GAN discriminator with a voting-based ensemble of teacher discriminators trained on disjoint subsets of the sensitive data. Each teacher classifies generated samples as real or fake, and their vote is aggregated with Laplacian noise¹⁸ to protect individual data contributions. The key innovation of PATE-GAN, however, is the introduction of a student discriminator, which learns to approximate the teacher’s consensus labels. In fact, unlike in standard GANs, where the generator is trained adversarially against a single discriminator, in PATE-GAN, the generator is updated based on feedback from the student, who, in turn, is trained on noisy labels derived from the teacher ensemble. This decouples the generator’s learning signal from direct exposure to private data and enables a more flexible privacy-preserving training scheme. To test the model, Jordon et al. employed the moments accountant method[206] to rigorously track the cumulative privacy budget¹⁹, and demonstrate empirically that their model achieves both strong differential privacy guarantees and competitive synthetic data utility, particularly on classification tasks.

However, a very recent study by Ganey et al.[207] revisits the original results reported by Jordon et al.[205] in the PATE-GAN paper, with the aim of reproducing both the utility and privacy guarantees. The authors analyze six open-source implementations of PATE-GAN and find substantial architectural discrepancies among them. Surprisingly, none of the implementations were able to replicate the high utility scores reported in the original work. Furthermore, Ganey et al. conduct an in-depth privacy evaluation, including formal DP auditing, and reveal that all six implementations leak significantly more private information than intended. The authors identify 19 distinct privacy violations and 5 critical bugs across the evaluated implementations. These findings highlight the broader concern in the field of synthetic data generation: the repro-

¹⁷The MNIST dataset consists of 70,000 grayscale images of handwritten digits (0–9), each of size 28×28 pixels. It is commonly used as a benchmark in computer vision and generative modeling tasks.

¹⁸Laplacian noise is sampled from the Laplace distribution and is commonly used in differential privacy when applying the *Laplace mechanism*, particularly for functions with bounded sensitivity.

¹⁹The moments accountant is a privacy accounting method which provides tighter bounds on cumulative privacy loss compared to traditional composition theorems. It tracks the privacy cost of multiple queries by analyzing higher-order moments of the privacy loss random variable, allowing for a more accurate estimation of the total (ϵ, δ) differential privacy guarantee over the course of training.

ducibility of benchmark results and the reliability of utility evaluations. As will be discussed in the next sections, this remains an open research problem, and developing more robust, transparent, and standardized evaluation pipelines is essential for the advancement of the field.

Continuing the exploration of differentially private GAN implementations, another notable model is CTAB-GAN+, an extension of the previously discussed CTAB-GAN architecture. This model was introduced by the same authors, Zhao et al.[208], with the goal of integrating formal differential privacy guarantees while maintaining strong performance on tabular data synthesis tasks. In CTAB-GAN+, the authors adopted another DP algorithm, called the Rényi Differential Privacy (RDP), in conjunction with the moments accountant framework. The Rényi Differential Privacy (RDP), introduced by Mironov[209], is a relaxation of classical differential privacy based on Rényi divergence, a generalization of Kullback-Leibler divergence. RDP provides a more flexible and tighter way to track privacy loss under composition, especially across multiple training steps. The conjunction with the moments accountant method allows for deriving an overall (ϵ, δ) at the end of training, thereby improving the privacy-utility trade-off when compared to earlier models such as DPGAN[204]. Moreover, CTAB-GAN+ replaces the traditional GAN loss (See Equation 1.2) with a Wasserstein loss combined with a gradient penalty term (WGAN-GP)²⁰. This modification not only enhances training stability but also intrinsically constrains the gradient norm of the discriminator, reducing the reliance on weight clipping and improving compatibility with differential privacy constraints. Unlike models such as the previously described PATE-GAN[205], which requires an ensemble of teacher discriminators and a student module, CTAB-GAN+ maintains a simpler single-discriminator architecture. Empirical evaluations conducted by the authors demonstrate that CTAB-GAN+ achieves good performance across several real-world datasets. The most important result was that under equivalent privacy budgets, the model consistently outperforms prior differentially private GAN frameworks in the tabular domain.

In recent years, several novel approaches to synthetic tabular data generation have emerged, entering a space that was previously dominated by GAN- and VAE-based models. These newer methods include: (i) Diffusion Models, which aim to address the longstanding challenges associated with GANs and VAEs, such as training instability, mode collapse, and poor representation of multimodal distributions[106], and (ii) Large Language Model (LLM) based methods, which have gained traction due to the rapid progress in generative AI and the relative simplicity of their implementations compared to previous architectures. These two classes of methods, even though not at the core of this thesis, represent promising directions in the field and will be discussed in the following section.

²⁰WGAN-GP is a variant of the Wasserstein GAN that improves training stability by replacing weight clipping with a gradient penalty. This technique encourages smoother discriminator behavior and better convergence. For more mathematical details, see Gulrajani et al.[125].

2.3 Diffusion Models and LLMs

Continuing with the taxonomy proposed by Shi et al.[106], diffusion-based approaches can be further divided into two categories: (i) *Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models* (DDPM-based methods), and (ii) *Score-based methods*. Similarly, LLM-based methods for synthetic tabular data generation can be classified into: (i) *Prompt-based methods*, which rely on textual input formatting, and (ii) *Fine-tuning methods*, where language models are adapted through supervised learning on structured data tasks.

2.3.1 DDPM-based Methods

Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models (DDPMs), originally proposed by Ho et al.[210], were first introduced for high-quality image synthesis but have since been extended to other domains, including tabular data. These models define a generative process by learning how to reverse a progressive corruption of the data, rather than generating samples directly. The forward process gradually adds Gaussian noise to a real data point x_0 , resulting in a sequence of increasingly noisy latent variables x_1, \dots, x_T , modeled as a Markov chain²¹ with transitions $q(x_t | x_{t-1})$:

$$q(x_{1:T} | x_0) = \prod_{t=1}^T q(x_t | x_{t-1}), \quad (2.9)$$

The goal of training is to learn a parametrized reverse process $p_\theta(x_{t-1} | x_t)$ that can iteratively denoise the latent variables and recover clean samples:

$$p_\theta(x_{0:T}) = \prod_{t=1}^T p_\theta(x_{t-1} | x_t), \quad (2.10)$$

The parameters θ are optimized by minimizing a surrogate loss based on a variational bound of the data log-likelihood, similar to that of VAE-based models (See Equation 1.3, referred to as Evidence Lower Bound (ELBO)):

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{q(x_{0:T})} & \left[-\log p_\theta(x_0 | x_1) + \text{KL}(q(x_T | x_0) \| p(x_T)) \right. \\ & \left. + \sum_{t=2}^T \text{KL}(q(x_{t-1} | x_t, x_0) \| p_\theta(x_{t-1} | x_t)) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

While DDPMs have shown impressive results in domains such as image and audio synthesis[210, 211], their direct application to tabular data has remained more challenging, primarily for the heterogeneous nature of tabular datasets,

²¹A Markov chain is a stochastic process describing a sequence of possible events in which the probability of each event depends only on the state attained in the previous event.

which contain a mix of numerical and categorical features with complex dependencies. Thus, recent work has focused on adapting the DDPM framework to better suit the structural characteristics of tabular data.

One of the first adoptions of DDPMs to tabular data is given by TabDDPM[212]. This model extends the standard Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Model framework to effectively handle the challenges posed by tabular data discussed above. To do so, TabDDPM introduces a tailored preprocessing pipeline that separately encodes continuous and categorical features. Continuous variables are normalized and modeled directly in the diffusion process, while categorical variables are embedded in a continuous space using learnable embeddings. After the reverse diffusion process, categorical features are decoded using an argmax operation over the embedding space, thus allowing the model to reconstruct valid discrete values. The authors report that, using metrics such as machine learning utility, TabDDPM consistently outperforms established GAN- and VAE-based baselines, including CTGAN and TVAE.

Motivated by these promising results, subsequent research has aimed to advance the state of the art by developing new diffusion-based architectures tailored for tabular data generation. One such model, developed by Shi et al.[213], is TabDiff, which proposes various innovations to approach the challenges of mixed-type data in tabular domains. First of all, TabDiff introduces a multimodal diffusion process that jointly models continuous and categorical features within a single unified framework. Unlike TabDDPM[212], which employs separate treatment and post-hoc decoding for categorical features, TabDiff diffuses all features together in a shared latent space. However, to effectively model the diverse statistical properties of each feature, the authors implement feature-wise learnable diffusion schedules, allowing the noise level to adapt dynamically across columns. To further improve generative quality, TabDiff adopts a transformer-based architecture capable of attending across features and samples. During sampling, it employs a mixed-type stochastic sampler to mitigate decoding inconsistencies and reduce the accumulation of generation errors, especially for categorical variables. TabDiff also integrates classifier-free guidance for conditional generation tasks, such as missing value imputation, enabling more accurate and stable output without reliance on an external classifier. Empirically²², TabDiff demonstrates strong performance across a wide range of datasets. The authors report a 22.5% improvement in pairwise column correlation estimation compared to previous state-of-the-art models.

Other approaches to tackling the challenge of generating synthetic tabular data have involved modifying DDPMs to create better-suited models. One such approach is introduced by Suh et al.[215], whose model Autodiff combines an

²²Throughout this literature review, the term *empirically* has been frequently used. Deriving from the Greek *empeiria* (εμπειρία), meaning "experience", it reminds us that many generative models are primarily evaluated through experimental results rather than formal proofs. As Immanuel Kant noted in his *Critique of Pure Reason*[214], experience, while necessary, can also be "the mother of illusion". This underscores the importance, but also the limitation, of empirical evaluation in generative modeling, where rigorous mathematical guarantees remain rare due to the complexity of the task.

autoencoder with a diffusion process in a unified network. In AutoDiff, an autoencoder is first employed to project the original tabular data into a structured latent space, where both numerical and categorical features are embedded into a unified continuous representation. The denoising diffusion process is then applied within this latent space, instead of the original data domain. This strategy allows the diffusion model to operate in a more tractable space, avoiding the complexities associated with handling discrete variables and structural correlations directly. Once the diffusion model completes the generation in the latent space, the decoder reconstructs the synthetic data back into the original tabular format (See Figure 2.5). Experimental evaluations on different benchmark datasets show that AutoDiff not only improves the fidelity and diversity of generated data, but also demonstrates strong performance on downstream tasks such as classification. Below is a schematic representation of the AutoDiff architecture, reproduced exactly from the original paper by Suh et al.[215], which illustrates the integration of an autoencoder with a diffusion model for tabular data generation.

Figure 2.5: Original architecture diagram of AutoDiff, showing how the input data x^{Proc} is encoded into latent space, processed by a diffusion model, and then decoded to produce synthetic tabular samples.

Many other examples of DDPM-based generative models have been proposed, but will not be discussed in greater detail in this literature review. Among these, notable contributions include CoDi[216] and CTSyn[217], both designed to handle mixed-type tabular data. Furthermore, domain-specific applications have emerged, such as the model by Kuo et al.[218] for generating synthetic longitudinal health records, and FinDiff[219] introduced by Sattarov et al. for

high-quality financial tabular data synthesis.

2.3.2 Score-based Methods

Note: The following mathematical formulation and notation for score-based diffusion models draws heavily from the exposition provided by Shi et al.[106], which offers a detailed overview of this class of generative models.

Score-based generative models represent an alternative to traditional DDPMs by directly modeling the score function, defined as the gradient of the log-density of the data distribution. Instead of optimizing a variational lower bound or relying on discrete-time Markov chains (See Equation 2.11 and 2.9), these models operate in continuous time using Stochastic Differential Equations (SDEs)[220, 221]. The forward process adds noise to the data through the following SDE:

$$dx = f(x, t)dt + g(t)dw, \quad (2.12)$$

where $f(x, t)$ is the drift term, $g(t)$ is a (typically scalar) diffusion coefficient, and w denotes a standard Wiener process²³.

In the reverse-time process, noise is progressively removed. The corresponding reverse SDE is:

$$dx = [f(x, t) - g(t)^2 \nabla_x \log p_t(x)] dt + g(t)dw, \quad (2.13)$$

where $\nabla_x \log p_t(x)$ is the score function of the data distribution at time t . Since the exact log-density is intractable, a neural network $s_\theta(x, t)$ is trained to approximate this score. This is typically done using denoising score matching, a loss function of the form:

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{t \sim \mathcal{U}(0, T)} \lambda(t) \mathbb{E}_{x_0, x(t)} \left[\left\| s_\theta(x(t), t) - \nabla_x \log p_t(x(t) | x_0) \right\|_2^2 \right] \quad (2.14)$$

Here, $\lambda(t)$ is a time-dependent weighting function, $x_0 \sim p_{data}$ is a clean sample, and $x(t)$ is its noisy version. Once the model is trained, sample generation is performed by numerically solving the reverse SDE, starting from a Gaussian noise vector $x(T) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$ and integrating backward to obtain synthetic data.

The first score-based model that was customized for generating synthetic tabular data was introduced by Kim et al., under the name of Score-based Over-Sampling (SOS)[222]. Unlike general-purpose score-based diffusion models, SOS specifically targets oversampling minority classes in imbalanced datasets, similarly to statistical methods discussed earlier, such as SMOTE [180]. To adapt score-based generative modeling to the tabular domain, Kim et al. incorporated class-conditional score networks, training separate score functions for each class. This setup enables SOS to generate synthetic samples conditioned on specific

²³Also known as Brownian motion, a continuous-time stochastic process with independent, normally distributed increments.

class labels, allowing targeted augmentation of underrepresented classes. In the benchmarking section, the authors demonstrated that the SOS method enhanced downstream classification performance on datasets with significant class imbalance, surpassing traditional oversampling techniques like the aforementioned SMOTE.

One recurrent challenge in synthetic tabular data generation is the presence of missing values. Commonly, generative models address this by either discarding incomplete records or imputing missing entries using simple heuristics, such as the mean for continuous variables or the mode for categorical ones. However, such strategies often fail to reflect the underlying structure and distribution of the data, potentially leading to biased or unrealistic synthetic samples. To address this limitation, Ouyang et al.[223] proposed MissDiff, a score-based diffusion model specifically designed to handle incomplete tabular data during both training and generation. MissDiff introduces a unified diffusion-based framework capable of learning directly from data with missing values. Central to this approach is a masked regression loss applied during the denoising score matching phase, which enables the model to focus on reconstructing only the observed components of the data while ignoring the missing ones. This design allows MissDiff to learn robust data distribution under various missingness mechanisms, including MCAR, MAR, and MNAR²⁴. At generation time, the reverse-time stochastic differential equation is solved while conditioning on the observed entries, thereby imputing realistic values for the missing parts in a principled way. Thanks to this approach, MissDiff has demonstrated great improvements not only in imputation accuracy but also in enhancing fidelity and diversity in datasets with a high proportion of missing values.

Another interesting approach was proposed by Zhang et al.[225], who introduced TABSYN, a hybrid generative framework that combines a score-based diffusion model with a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) to generate synthetic tabular data. This model is motivated by the complementary strengths of both components. In fact, as shown in previous sections, VAEs are effective at learning latent representations in complex data, and, on the other hand, diffusion models provide stable and high-fidelity sample generation through iterative denoising. In TABSYN, the VAE acts as a feature extractor that encodes heterogeneous tabular data into a shared latent space. Here, both encoder and decoder are implemented using Transformer architectures, allowing the model to capture inter-column relationships and obtain token-level representations. Once encoded, the diffusion model is applied in this latent space, rather than the original data domain. During generation, the model samples latent variables using the reverse diffusion process, which are then decoded back into the original data space using the VAE decoder. Experimental results presented by the authors show that TABSYN outperforms several baseline methods in terms of both statistical similarity and machine learning utility.

So far, the discussion of generative models has focused on architectures de-

²⁴Missing Completely At Random, Missing At Random, and Missing Not At Random, respectively. For a clear and intuitive explanation of these types of missing values, see [224].

signed specifically for synthetic tabular data generation, including statistical models, VAEs, GANs, and diffusion models. However, the recent rise and public availability of powerful multimodal Large Language Models (LLMs), such as ChatGPT, has prompted researchers to explore how this new paradigm might reshape the field. These models, capable of producing diverse outputs, including tabular data, from natural language prompts, have opened up new avenues for data synthesis. In the following subsections, the two primary approaches for using LLMs in this context will be discussed: Prompt-based Methods and Fine-tuning Methods.

2.3.3 Prompt-based Methods

One of the notable emergent abilities²⁵ of modern Large Language Models (LLMs) is their capacity for in-context learning (ICL)[227]. This refers to the model’s ability to learn and adapt to new tasks based solely on input-output examples provided within the prompt, without any explicit modification of its internal parameters. ICL enables LLMs to perform tasks by interpreting and generalizing from the context given. The rise of this emergent property with the increase of LLMs scale (i.e., number of internal parameters), has introduced opportunities for utilizing LLMs in synthetic tabular data generation. By carefully designing prompts that include context from the original dataset, LLMs can generate synthetic data that mirrors the statistical properties of the real data, all without undergoing additional training or fine-tuning[106].

One of the first approaches utilizing prompt-based methods with LLMs for tabular data generation is EPIC (Effective Prompting for Imbalanced-Class), introduced by Kim et al.[122]. EPIC tries to address the challenge of class imbalance in tabular datasets by taking advantage of the aforementioned in-context learning capabilities (ICL) of LLMs, and specifically using three models: GPT 3.5, Mistral-7b-v0.1, and Llama-2-7b. To guide the model effectively, the authors designed prompt templates that included column names, example values from the dataset, and the class label for which they wished to generate new samples. During the generation process, these prompts were formatted as synthetic table rows, where the model completed the row in a semantically coherent manner. EPIC also integrates a careful curation step where generated samples are validated and filtered to improve consistency and utility. Their empirical evaluations demonstrated that training classification models on real data augmented with EPIC-generated samples led to improved predictive performance, illustrating the practical benefits of this new method of generating synthetic tabular data.

Another significant advantage of LLMs is their extensive prior knowledge across various domains, acquired through large-scale pretraining. Leveraging this capability, Seedat et al.[228] introduced Curated LLM (CLLM), a framework designed for augmenting tabular data, particularly in low-data regimes

²⁵Emergent abilities are capabilities that are not present in smaller models but appear in larger models, often unpredictably, as a result of scaling up the model’s size and training data. See [226] for more details.

where the available data is insufficient for effective machine learning model training. CLLM operates in two primary stages. Initially, it employs in-context learning (ICL) to prompt an LLM to generate synthetic tabular data²⁶. This simple process utilizes the LLM’s preexisting knowledge to create data samples that resemble the limited available data. However, recognizing that not all generated data will be beneficial, CLLM incorporates a subsequent curation phase. This phase involves evaluating the generated samples using metrics such as predictive confidence and uncertainty estimates to filter out low-quality or uninformative data points. The experiments conducted by the authors using real-world datasets demonstrated that CLLM traditional synthetic data generators in low-data settings, enhancing the performance of downstream machine learning models.

As seen in the EPIC[122], another oversampling method that harnesses the capabilities of LLMs is LITO[229], which, like previously discussed frameworks, addresses the issue of imbalanced class distributions in tabular data. The core idea behind LITO (Language-Interfaced Tabular Oversampling) is to progressively transform majority class examples into minority-like samples. This is achieved by masking informative attributes of majority class instances and prompting the LLMs²⁷ to impute them toward the minority class distribution, thereby exploiting the language model’s extensive prior knowledge of the distribution to produce contextually appropriate synthetic samples. Unlike CLLM[228] and EPIC[122], which don’t rely on the LLM to validate the generated samples, LITO includes a self-authentication mechanism. Here, the LLM itself is tasked with validating the authenticity of its outputs by re-labeling the synthetic samples it has generated, and only the samples for which the LLM confidently predicts the minority class are retained. Empirical evaluation in the original paper[229] demonstrated that LITO successfully generates reliable minority samples to boost the performance of machine learning classifiers, even under heavy imbalance ratios.

2.3.4 Fine-tuning Methods

One major limitation of Large Language Models (LLMs) with billions or even trillions of parameters is one of their ”emergent properties” that, in this case, manifests in a negative sense: hallucinations. Hallucination, meaning producing outputs that are syntactically correct but factually inaccurate, remains a persistent and actively researched issue[230]. For this reason, generating tabular data solely by prompting general-purpose LLMs, as discussed in the previous subsection on prompt-based methods, may result in misleading or unreliable outputs. To address this, fine-tuning LLMs specifically for tabular data generation has emerged as a promising alternative.

The first attempt to leverage table pre-training to empower LLM models to generate accurate tabular data was introduced by Zhang et al.[231], with the

²⁶In their study, Seedat et al.[228] used specifically GPT-4 and GPT-3.5.

²⁷In particular, Distill-GPT-2 and GPT-3.5.

so-called TAPTAP model. In this implementation, TAPTAP is trained on a large corpus of real-world tabular datasets, allowing the model to internalize structural and semantic patterns that are common across a wide range of tabular formats. Once pre-trained, the model demonstrated the ability to generate high-quality synthetic tables capable of supporting a wide array of downstream tasks, such as many of the ones discussed so far, including privacy protection, low-resource learning, missing value imputation, and imbalanced classification. TAPTAP was shown to outperform 16 baseline models across 12 datasets. Importantly, the model is compatible with diverse backbone architectures such as LightGBM, Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs), and transformers, which makes it particularly versatile. With these results, Zhang et al. [231] opened the door to the use of fine-tuning methods, which will then be perfected in subsequent research.

One such advancement is represented by HARMONIC[232], a framework for tabular data generation and evaluation that, unlike previous small-scale LLM-based methods relying on continued pre-training (e.g., TAPTAP[231]), explores large-scale LLMs fine-tuned specifically for structured data synthesis and privacy preservation. In particular, HARMONIC introduces an instruction-based fine-tuning dataset built on the principle of k -nearest neighbors algorithm, which enables the model to discover and retain meaningful inter-row relationships rather than memorizing specific data points. Through this approach, the fine-tuned LLM is trained to reproduce the structural and statistical properties of tabular data while minimizing the risk of privacy leakage. In the data generation phase, the LLM is conditioned to remember the format and connections among the data entries, rather than raw content, thus aiming to enhance privacy guarantees. To assess the quality and safety of the synthetic data, HARMONIC also contributes two novel evaluation tools: (i) Data Leakage Test (DLT), a metric designed to quantify privacy risks in generated outputs, and (ii) LLM Effectiveness (LLE), a performance evaluation metric tailored to downstream tabular learning tasks. Their empirical evaluations across multiple datasets show that HARMONIC achieves performance on par with state-of-the-art baselines in terms of predictive utility, while improving privacy scores under DLT.

To close the circle of synthetic tabular data generative models, and conclude this section with a method that symbolically ties together LLMs and the major generative paradigm discussed in this literature review, GANs, Yang et al.[233] proposed Proximal Table Augmentation (P-TA). This framework aims to take advantage of both the strengths of GANs and LLMs by employing Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) to guide the generation of synthetic data. P-TA addresses the limitations of traditional GAN-based methods, which often produce samples with common-sense errors due to the lack of external knowledge, and LLM-based approaches, which may struggle to capture disparities between synthesized and actual data distributions. In their approach, P-TA fine-tunes an LLM to generate new data in textual form by first transforming tabular records into natural language using schema-guided templates. Then, as in a classical adversarial framework, a discriminator is trained to distinguish between real and generated samples. The discriminator’s outputs are used as rewards to further

optimize the LLM through the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm. PPO, a reinforcement learning method, updates the model’s parameters by balancing performance improvement with stability. This algorithm avoids overly large updates by clipping the objective function, ensuring that the LLM’s behaviour changes gradually during training. This method enables the LLM to receive feedback from the discriminator, effectively integrating the adversarial training mechanism of GANs. Empirical results demonstrated that P-TA achieves approximately a 4% improvement in the accuracy of models trained on synthetically generated data compared to other state-of-the-art methods across three real-world datasets.

Throughout the discussion of all these generative models, various techniques have been employed to evaluate the fidelity and utility of the synthetic tabular data they produce. These evaluation strategies try to assess the true effectiveness of synthetic data, and will be the focus of the next and final section of this literature review.

2.4 Benchmarking Synthetic Data

The inherently heterogeneous and multidimensional nature of synthetic tabular data makes it difficult to rely on a single metric to assess its overall quality in comparison to real data. In fact, the suitability of synthetic data must first be evaluated in light of the specific tasks it is meant to support[234]. For instance, in sensitive domains like healthcare or finance, the primary concern may be the degree to which patient or client privacy is preserved. In contrast, in machine learning research, the key question might be whether models trained on synthetic data perform comparably to those trained on real data[133]. With this task-specific perspective in mind, the research community has developed a wide range of evaluation metrics over the past decade, ranging from basic statistical similarities between individual features to more complex assessments of fairness and constraints adherence. For the purpose of this literature review, I focus on seven core evaluation dimensions that have emerged as particularly influential in the benchmarking of synthetic tabular data generators: (i) Statistical Fidelity (i.e., fidelity or similarity), (ii) Machine Learning Utility (i.e., utility or usability), (iii) Computational Efficiency, (iv) Privacy and Disclosure Risk, (v) Diversity and Novelty, (vi) Alignment with Domain Knowledge and Constraints, (vii) Fairness. These seven domains form a comprehensive umbrella under which most modern evaluations of synthetic tabular data fall. Each of them will be discussed in more detail next. **Note:** While this section provides a broad overview of the main techniques used to evaluate synthetic tabular data, not all seven benchmarking dimensions will be applied in the experimental evaluation of the KAN-based models discussed in this thesis. For details on the specific evaluation techniques adopted, please refer to Chapter 3.

2.4.1 Statistical Fidelity

Probably the most commonly used and straightforward metric for benchmarking synthetic tabular data is statistical fidelity, often referred to simply as fidelity or similarity[198, 208, 188, 205, 124, 120]. It measures how closely synthetic data replicates the statistical properties and distributional patterns of the real data, and can be evaluated at multiple levels of granularity.

At the univariate level, fidelity focuses on individual feature (i.e., column) distributions. Typical measures include the Wasserstein distance and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for continuous variables and the Jensen-Shannon or Total Variation Distance (TVD) for categorical variables²⁸. These scores usually fall in the range [0,1], with values closer to 1 indicating stronger alignment in terms of means, variances, or category frequencies between single columns of the synthetic and real data.

Moving beyond single features, bivariate fidelity assesses whether pairwise relationships between features are maintained. This is often evaluated using Pearson correlation to capture linear associations, and Spearman correlation for monotonic trends[235]. Finally, multivariate fidelity considers the similarity of the joint distribution across all features. This broader view is typically assessed using multivariate distance metrics and coverage scores[236], which estimate whether the synthetic data spans the real data’s range without omitting or hallucinating major modes.

Despite its importance, statistical fidelity alone offers an incomplete picture. High fidelity does not necessarily imply that the synthetic data will be useful for downstream tasks like machine learning training. In fact, strong alignment in marginal distributions may still fail to preserve important latent relationships[106]. For this reason, it is considered best practice to complement fidelity assessments with other criteria, most notably, machine learning utility.

2.4.2 Machine learning Utility

To explain the principle behind machine learning utility (also known as downstream utility), it is useful to begin with an analogy. Imagine two students preparing for the same exam, assuming both possess identical cognitive abilities. If they study from the same material under the same conditions, they are expected to perform similarly. Now, consider each student as a machine learning model (e.g., Logistic Regression). One model is trained on synthetic data, the other on real data, and both are evaluated on the same real test set, this evaluation is analogous to taking the exam. If their performances are comparable, it suggests that the two training datasets (real and synthetic) are similar in quality and informational content (i.e., they have similar distributions).

Formally, this approach is known as Train on Synthetic, Test on Real (TSTR)[237]. In this protocol, a model is trained using synthetic data and evaluated on a held-out real test set. Its performance is then compared to the same model architecture trained on real data. High quality implies that synthetic data is

²⁸For a more detailed mathematical explanation of these measures, see Chapter 3

a reliable substitute for real data in machine learning tasks. Below is a visual depiction of the TSTR framework.

Figure 2.6: Schematic representation of the TSTR (Train on Synthetic, Test on Real) framework.

2.4.3 Computational Efficiency

Depending on the application, computational efficiency may be a critical or secondary concern, but it remains an intrinsic property of any synthetic data generation model. Computational efficiency encompasses both the training time required to fit the generative model and the time needed to sample synthetic data. It also includes a model’s resource intensity, referred to by Vallevik et al.[234] as “carbon footprint”. This definition emphasizes the environmental and infrastructural costs associated with training large-scale models, particularly deep generative models like GANs or transformer-based LLMs discussed above, often requiring powerful hardware (e.g., GPUs, TPUs²⁹) and long training cycles.

Measuring a model’s resource intensiveness may involve recording wall-clock time (i.e., the actual time in seconds for training or inference), monitoring memory usage (e.g., RAM or GPU VRAM consumption), computing the number of floating-point operations (FLOPs), or even tracking energy consumption in kilowatt-hours (kWh). In recent years, more advanced tools have been developed to estimate the carbon emissions directly associated with training machine learning models. Among the most notable are CodeCarbon[239] and

²⁹The rise of machine learning in the last decade brought Google to create Tensor Processing Units (TPUs), which are specifically designed to accelerate machine learning workloads, especially those involving neural networks, thanks to their specialized focus on tensor operations, typical of ML applications. For an in-depth analysis, see [238].

CarbonTracker[240], which provide automatic tracking of energy usage and environmental impact.

These metrics not only inform the researchers about a model’s scalability and deployability in real-world settings but also highlight increasing concerns regarding the sustainability of machine learning systems. Nonetheless, computational efficiency remains a sparsely reported dimension in current benchmarking practices within synthetic tabular data generation research[234].

2.4.4 Privacy and disclosure Risk

If computational efficiency is one of the least reported metrics, privacy and disclosure risk is arguably one of the most studied properties of synthetic tabular data generation (see Section 2.2.4). In certain domains, such as the often-discussed healthcare and finance, preserving the privacy of the original data is essential. This means that synthetic data must be generated in a way that avoids inadvertently leaking information about any specific individual in the original dataset. To assess these privacy concerns, several metrics have been developed to quantify the extent to which real individuals can be re-identified or inferred from the synthetic data. Following the taxonomy provided by Shi et al.[106], three primary evaluation techniques have emerged: (i) Distance to Closest Record (DCR), (ii) Membership Inference Attacks (MIA), and (iii) Attribute Inference Attacks (AIA).

In Distance to Closest Record (DCR), the distance from each synthetic record to its nearest neighbor in the real dataset is computed. If synthetic records are nearly identical to real ones (i.e., exhibit low DCR), this may indicate that the model has memorized and reproduced real data, thus posing a privacy risk. Higher average DCR values are preferable, as they suggest that synthetic samples are sufficiently distinct from real individuals.

Membership Inference Attacks (MIA) aim to evaluate whether an adversary can determine if a particular record was part of the real dataset used to train the generator. By analyzing the synthetic data, the attacker attempts to infer membership status. A high success rate in such attacks indicates that the synthetic data closely reflects its training set, implying poor privacy due to overfitting and potential information leakage.

In Attribute Inference Attacks (AIA), the adversary has partial knowledge of an individual and attempts to infer unknown sensitive attributes by exploiting patterns in the synthetic data. For example, given a person’s demographic information, can one predict a hidden health condition using the synthetic dataset? If the synthetic data enables such accurate inference, it implies that sensitive correlations from the real data have been preserved closely, again signaling a privacy breach.

These techniques provide a rough but informative quantification of privacy risks in synthetic tabular data. As previously discussed, when the primary objective is to generate highly accurate data (in terms of fidelity and utility), enforcing strict privacy constraints can degrade performance. This reflects the well-known privacy-utility trade-off. However, in domains where privacy is cru-

cial, models that can strike a balance between utility and privacy may prove more valuable than those that simply maximize fidelity or predictive performance.

2.4.5 Diversity and Novelty

In the extreme case, the goal were merely to produce data that closely resembles the original, there would be little need for a synthetic data generator at all. In practice, however, synthetic data is expected to introduce a certain degree of diversity and novelty relative to the real data. Novelty (or diversity) refers to how original and varied synthetic samples are, while still remaining plausible within the distribution of the source data. High diversity ensures that the synthetic dataset is not merely a collection of real records copied or slightly perturbed, but instead spans a broad space of legitimate variants. As argued by Sidorenko et al.[241], a robust generative model should balance fidelity and novelty. If a model focuses exclusively on fidelity, it risks memorizing the training data, generating synthetic samples that are statistically similar but contain no new information, and may compromise privacy. On the other hand, maximizing novelty without constraint can lead to unrealistic or incoherent outputs that deviate significantly from the true data distributions.

To quantify novelty, that is, how distinct synthetic samples are from real ones, a common strategy is to compare synthetic samples against a holdout set of real data that was not seen during training. Ideally, the synthetic data should be as close to this unseen real data as the original training data is, but not closer[241]. In other words, each synthetic sample should resemble the general characteristics of the overall population while avoiding overlap with any specific training instance, which would suggest overfitting.

A practical metric to assess this property is an average nearest-neighbor distance, such as the Distance to Closest Record (DCR) described in the previous subsection. When contextualized through comparison with real-real and synthetic-real distances, DCR can reveal whether the synthetic generator is producing samples that are both plausible and novel. If the distance distributions are similar, this indicates that the generator is achieving a reasonable trade-off between fidelity and novelty.

2.4.6 Alignment with Domain Knowledge and Constraints

In Section 2.3, when discussing LLM-based methods for synthetic tabular data generation, the importance of prior and domain knowledge emerged as a key advantage, thanks to the extensive training corpora used to develop these models. Building upon this notion, a recently emphasized dimension in the evaluation of synthetic tabular data is its alignment with domain-specific knowledge and logical constraints. In essence, the synthetic data should make sense within the context of the application domain and must not violate rules or relationships that are inherently true in the real data.

For instance, in the healthcare domain, a synthetic patient record should not contain impossible combinations, such as a male patient being marked as "pregnant", or chronological inconsistencies, such as treatment dates that precede a patient's birth date. These types of violations significantly reduce the realism and utility of the synthetic data, even though the fidelity could be preserved. This is particularly important in regulated or high-stakes domains.

To measure such alignment, one typically defines a set of domain-specific constraints or invariants, and then evaluates how well the synthetic data adheres to them. As identified by Shi et al.[106], one of the most widely used metrics is the Constraint Violation Rate (CVR), which represents the percentage of synthetic records that violate at least one predefined rule. A lower CVR indicates a higher degree of logical consistency in the synthetic dataset. Another useful metric is Constraint Violation Coverage (CVC), which measures how many unique constraints are violated at least once across the entire synthetic dataset, thus offering a more granular view of systematic issues.

These alignment checks are particularly crucial when expert knowledge or regulatory standards must be preserved, as is the case in sectors such as healthcare, finance, and law. As noted by Vallevik et al.[234], incorporating such evaluations helps ensure that synthetic data is not only statistically and functionally similar to real data, but also semantically valid within the intended domain.

2.4.7 Fairness

Another emerging dimension that has often been overlooked in prior studies is fairness[234], largely due to the ambiguity of its definition and the difficulty of quantitative assessment. In general terms, fairness evaluation asks whether the data preserves, mitigates, or amplifies the biases already present in the original data. For instance, if a real dataset contains class imbalance or underrepresentation of minority subgroups, a good synthetic data generator should ideally avoid exacerbating these disparities, or even correct them. As seen in earlier sections, one recurring problem among deep learning-based generative models (e.g., CTGAN[124]) is mode collapse toward the majority class. In such cases, a naive generator might reinforce systemic bias if not properly addressed.

Fairness metrics for synthetic data vary, but commonly include assessments of statistical parity across sensitive groups when models are trained on synthetic versus real data, or comparisons of group-level distributional shifts[242]. However, in practice, fairness often boils down to heuristic analyses. Measuring distributional similarity alone may not capture systemic bias, and more importantly, bias itself is socially and contextually defined. What one domain considers a fairness violation, another may not, depending on the specific task. This subjectivity makes fairness a difficult component to evaluate. In fact, it remains underreported in most benchmarking efforts to date.

Many metrics have been discussed so far. Now it's time to implement a subset of them for the purpose of this thesis: evaluating new generative models that replace MLPs with Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs) in the CTGAN

and TVAE architectures. In the next chapter, all models will be discussed in detail, along with the specific benchmarking techniques used to compare them with the classical counterparts.

Chapter 3

Methods

3.1 Models Architecture

The primary objective of this thesis is to evaluate the impact of modifying the CTGAN and TVAE frameworks proposed by Xu et al.[124] by replacing their multilayer perceptrons (MLPs) with Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks (KANs). The overall architectures of the two models remain unchanged, what changes is that the standard MLP blocks used in the generator–discriminator (CTGAN) and encoder–decoder (TVAE) components are substituted with KANs, a recently introduced neural architecture[128] that replaces linear weights with learnable function-based connections (i.e., functions on the edges of the network). This modification, proposed by Liu et al.[128] in the original KAN paper, aims to improve expressiveness and function approximation capabilities, though at the cost of increased computational overhead. Further details on KANs are provided in Section 1.4.

To achieve this objective, six KAN-based variants were developed and benchmarked against the original CTGAN and TVAE: (i) KAN-CTGAN, (ii) KAN-TVAE, (iii) Hybrid-CTGAN, (iv) Hybrid-TVAE, (v) GenKAN-CTGAN, and (vi) DiscKAN-CTGAN.

The remainder of this section details the differences and implementation choices for each of these variants.

3.1.1 KAN-CTGAN

KAN-CTGAN replaces all multilayer perceptrons (MLPs) and residual connections in both the generator and discriminator of CTGAN with KAN-based components. The heuristic motivation for this architectural modification is to enable the model to learn more granular structures and capture complex dependencies in the data. This should be achieved through the use of B-spline learnable functions in each KAN layer, instead of the usual linear weights in MLPs. Thanks to their control-point structure, these functions allow the network to adapt locally during training. Therefore, the idea is that a synthetic

data generator using KAN layers should be more flexible and expressive. However, this should be tested experimentally, which is exactly the scope of this thesis.

The overall structure of the model remains unchanged from the original CTGAN. The generator and the discriminator consist of two hidden layers, now implemented using KANLinear[243] (more details to follow). In the generator, the classical residual blocks have been replaced with KAN-based residual blocks (See Appendix A for the code), which include batch normalization and the SiLU activation function (Sigmoid Linear Unit). SiLU is used here, instead of ReLU, as originally proposed by Liu et al.[128], due to its smoothness and full differentiability.

Following the two hidden layers, the synthetic row representation is produced using activation functions tailored to the column type. Continuous features are generated via \tanh activation, yielding scalar values α_i , while discrete features are synthesized using the Gumbel-Softmax function¹, producing both the mode indicator β_i and the final discrete outputs \mathbf{d}_i . This notation, as well as the subsequent notations used in this section, will adhere precisely to the conventions established by Xu et al.[124] in their original paper. This approach ensures comparability and facilitates evaluation and benchmarking.

A schematic comparison between the original CTGAN generator (top) and the modified KAN-CTGAN generator (bottom) is shown below in Figure 3.1, and the corresponding code can be found in Appendix A.

To clarify the notation, \oplus denotes concatenation between vectors, z is the input latent vector, and $cond$ is the conditional vector that guides the generation process. ReLU and SiLU refer to the respective activation functions, while BN stands for batch normalization. The notation $FC_{u \rightarrow v}(x)$ indicates a fully connected layer (i.e., a linear transformation) from a u -dimensional input to a v -dimensional output. Conversely, $KAN_{u \rightarrow v}(x)$ represents the same transformation performed via a KANLinear layer.

The output variables follow the original CTGAN design. $\hat{\alpha}_i$ represents the scalar output for the i -th continuous column, $\hat{\beta}_i$ is an internal latent indicator that selects which mode to sample from each continuous feature², and $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_i$ is the final discrete vector for the i -th discrete column.

m_i is the number of modes found via Gaussian Mixture Modeling (GMM) for continuous feature i , and D_i is the number of categories for discrete feature i . Finally, N_c and N_d are the number of continuous and discrete columns in the dataset, respectively.

The discriminator in KAN-CTGAN follows the same design principles adopted for the generator. Specifically, the architecture of the original CTGAN discriminator (referred to as *critic* by Xu et al[124]) is preserved, with the primary modification being the replacement of all MLP-based layers with KANLinear layers.

¹The Gumbel-Softmax function is used to generate a differentiable approximation of a one-hot encoded vector, allowing backpropagation through discrete variables during training. See [244] for a more detailed explanation.

²See the explanation of *Mode specific normalization* in Section 1.3.1 for more details.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} h_0 = z \oplus \text{cond} \\ h_1 = h_0 \oplus \text{ReLU}(\text{BN}(\text{FC}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|\rightarrow 256}(h_0))) \\ h_2 = h_1 \oplus \text{ReLU}(\text{BN}(\text{FC}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|\rightarrow 256}(h_1))) \\ \hat{\alpha}_i = \tanh(\text{FC}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|+512\rightarrow 1}(h_2)) \quad 1 \leq i \leq N_c \\ \hat{\beta}_i = \text{gumbel}_{0.2}(\text{FC}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|+512\rightarrow m_i}(h_2)) \quad 1 \leq i \leq N_c \\ \hat{\mathbf{d}}_i = \text{gumbel}_{0.2}(\text{FC}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|+512\rightarrow D_i}(h_2)) \quad 1 \leq i \leq N_d \end{array} \right.$$

Original CTGAN Generator

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} h_0 = z \oplus \text{cond} \\ h_1 = h_0 \oplus \text{SiLU}(\text{BN}(\text{KAN}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|\rightarrow 256}(h_0))) \\ h_2 = h_1 \oplus \text{SiLU}(\text{BN}(\text{KAN}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|\rightarrow 256}(h_1))) \\ \hat{\alpha}_i = \tanh(\text{KAN}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|+512\rightarrow 1}(h_2)) \quad 1 \leq i \leq N_c \\ \hat{\beta}_i = \text{gumbel}_{0.2}(\text{KAN}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|+512\rightarrow m_i}(h_2)) \quad 1 \leq i \leq N_c \\ \hat{\mathbf{d}}_i = \text{gumbel}_{0.2}(\text{KAN}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|+512\rightarrow D_i}(h_2)) \quad 1 \leq i \leq N_d \end{array} \right.$$

KAN-CTGAN Generator

Figure 3.1: Comparison between the original CTGAN and KAN-CTGAN generator architectures.

As in the original CTGAN, the PacGAN framework[126] is employed to mitigate mode collapse, grouping 10 samples per *pac* during training. A schematic comparison of the original CTGAN discriminator and its KAN-based variant is shown below, and the code is in Appendix A.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} h_0 = r_1 \oplus \dots \oplus r_{10} \oplus \text{cond}_1 \oplus \dots \oplus \text{cond}_{10} \\ h_1 = \text{drop}(\text{leaky}_{0.2}(\text{FC}_{10|\text{cond}|+10\rightarrow 256}(h_0))) \\ h_2 = \text{drop}(\text{leaky}_{0.2}(\text{FC}_{256\rightarrow 256}(h_1))) \\ \mathcal{C}(\cdot) = \text{FC}_{256\rightarrow 1}(h_2) \end{array} \right.$$

Original CTGAN Discriminator

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} h_0 = r_1 \oplus \dots \oplus r_{10} \oplus \text{cond}_1 \oplus \dots \oplus \text{cond}_{10} \\ h_1 = \text{drop}(\text{SiLU}_{0.2}(\text{BN}(\text{KAN}_{10|\text{cond}|+10\rightarrow 256}(h_0)))) \\ h_2 = \text{drop}(\text{SiLU}_{0.2}(\text{BN}(\text{KAN}_{256\rightarrow 256}(h_1)))) \\ \mathcal{C}(\cdot) = \text{KAN}_{256\rightarrow 1}(h_2) \end{array} \right.$$

KAN-CTGAN Discriminator

Figure 3.2: Comparison between the original CTGAN and KAN-CTGAN discriminator architectures.

Here, r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{10} are the 10 real or generated samples as required by the PacGAN framework, *drop* refers to the use of dropout, and $\mathcal{C}(\cdot)$ denotes the output critic (i.e., discriminator), implemented as a fully connected layer with a single scalar output in the original implementation, and with KAN layers in KAN-CTGAN.

To ensure comparability, the training procedure replicates that used by Xu et al.[124], including the use of the Wasserstein GAN loss with gradient penalty, the Adam optimizer, and a learning rate of $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$. All models used to generate synthetic tabular data were trained for 100 epochs.

KANLinear, used in both the generator and discriminator of KAN-CTGAN, as well as in all models that will follow in this section, comes from the open-source implementation *Efficient KAN*[243]³. This implementation aims to improve the computational and memory efficiency of the original KAN proposed by Liu et al.[128], previously introduced in Section 1.4. The original KAN architecture requires the expansion of all intermediate variables to apply learnable activation functions along the edges of the network, a process that can be expensive in terms of both time and memory. Blealtan[243] observed that all such activation functions in KAN can be expressed as linear combinations of a fixed set of basis functions, which are the B-splines. Thanks to this observation, he reformulated the computation so that the input is first transformed through these basis functions and subsequently combined linearly. This reformulation enables the entire computation to be expressed through standard matrix multiplications, which, as usual in neural networks, can support both forward and backward propagation.

Another source of inefficiency addressed by *Efficient KAN* is the regularization scheme. The original KAN implementation used L1 regularization directly on the activations computed for each input sample, involving non-linear operations and added computational costs. In contrast, *Efficient KAN* replaces this with a more conventional L1 regularization applied directly to the learnable weights. However, this change comes with a trade-off. In fact, the original activation-based L1 regularization played a crucial role in encouraging sparsity, a central property for the interpretability claims of the original KAN framework. Nonetheless, for practical purposes such as the generation of synthetic tabular data, as in the case of this thesis, the improved efficiency of *Efficient KAN* makes it a far more viable solution.

Thanks to the incorporation of KAN layers in KAN-CTGAN, the users can decide two additional hyperparameters that directly affect how the activation functions are modeled: the grid size and the spline order. The grid size determines how many intervals the input domain is divided into (i.e., the number of knots). A larger grid size increases the resolution of the learned functions, enabling finer local variations. In this implementation, the default value is set to 5. The spline order defines the degree of the B-spline basis functions. For instance, an order of 0 corresponds to piecewise constant functions, order 1 to

³The full implementation is available at https://github.com/Blealtan/efficient-kan/blob/master/src/efficient_kan/kan.py

piecewise linear, and higher orders yield increasingly smooth transformations. The default spline order used in KAN-CTGAN is 3.

The complete implementation of KAN-CTGAN is available at the GitHub link present in this footnote⁴.

3.1.2 KAN-TVAE

KAN-TVAE follows the same design philosophy adopted for KAN-CTGAN, in fact, the overall structure of the original TVAE remains unchanged, but every multilayer perceptron is replaced by a KANLinear layer. To be consistent with the notation introduced by Xu et al.[124], the decoder is denoted by $p_\theta(\mathbf{r}_j | z_j)$ and the encoder by $q_\phi(z_j | \mathbf{r}_j)$. The model is trained by minimizing the evidence lower-bound (ELBO) loss, as described in Equation 1.3.

In the decoder network $p_\theta(\mathbf{r}_j | z_j)$, the goal is to reconstruct the data from a latent representation. It outputs a joint distribution over $2N_c + N_d$ ⁵ variables, corresponding to the reconstruction of continuous and discrete features in the dataset. For each continuous variable i , the network predicts a mean $\tilde{\alpha}_{i,j}$ and a standard deviation δ_i , with $\hat{\alpha}_{i,j} \sim \mathcal{N}(\tilde{\alpha}_{i,j}, \delta_i)$. Moreover, for each continuous feature, a mode indicator $\hat{\beta}_{i,j}$ is generated via softmax, as well as discrete variables $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{i,j}$, which are modeled as categorical distributions using softmax outputs, exactly as in CTGAN. The variables $\hat{\alpha}_{i,j}$, $\hat{\beta}_{i,j}$, $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{i,j}$ are treated as random variables, and the decoder models the joint distribution through $p_\theta(\mathbf{r}_j | z_j)$, where \mathbf{r}_j is the vector of reconstructed outputs. The parameters of the decoder, including the weight matrices (for the original MLPs), the B-splines activation functions (in KAN-TVAE), and δ_i , are denoted by θ and trained via gradient descent. A comparison of the TVAE and KAN-TVAE decoder is provided below in Figure 3.3, where $\alpha_{i,j}$ and $\beta_{i,j}$ are latent variables modeled respectively as Gaussian and categorical PMF. The code of the KAN-TVAE decoder can be found in Appendix B

The encoder $q_\phi(z_j | \mathbf{r}_j)$, on the other hand, maps the input vector \mathbf{r}_j into a latent representation by predicting a mean μ and a standard deviation vector σ . These parameters are used to model the Gaussian posterior $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma I)$, from which z_j is sampled and subsequently passed to the decoder. Figure 3.4 shows the comparison between the original encoder and the KAN-TVAE encoder, and the encoder class can be found in Appendix B.

As in KAN-CTGAN, KAN-TVAE also has two additional hyperparameters for the grid size and spline order, which are set to 3 and 5, respectively, as default. Similar to the original TVAE, KAN-TVAE is trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 1e-3.

The complete implementation of KAN-CTGAN is available at the GitHub link present in this footnote⁶.

⁴https://github.com/cris1618/KAN_CTGAN/blob/main/Code/KAN_CTGAN_code.py.

⁵The decoder outputs $2N_c$, and not simply N_c , number of variables, because for each continuous feature it produces both a mean $\tilde{\alpha}_{i,j}$ and a standard deviation δ_i , ending up with $2N_c$ variables.

⁶https://github.com/cris1618/KAN_CTGAN/blob/main/Code/KAN_TVAE_code.py.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} h_1 = \text{ReLU}(\text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(z_j)) \\ h_2 = \text{ReLU}(\text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(h_1)) \\ \tilde{\alpha}_{i,j} = \tanh(\text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow 1}(h_2)) \\ \hat{\alpha}_{i,j} \sim \mathcal{N}(\tilde{\alpha}_{i,j}, \delta_i) \\ \hat{\beta}_{i,j} \sim \text{softmax}(\text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow m_i}(h_2)) \\ \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{i,j} \sim \text{softmax}(\text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow |D_i|}(h_2)) \\ p_{\theta}(\mathbf{r}_j | z_j) = \prod_{i=1}^{N_c} \mathbb{P}(\hat{\alpha}_{i,j} = \alpha_{i,j}) \prod_{i=1}^{N_c} \mathbb{P}(\hat{\beta}_{i,j} = \beta_{i,j}) \prod_{i=1}^{N_d} \mathbb{P}(\hat{\alpha}_{i,j} = \alpha_{i,j}) \end{array} \right. \begin{array}{l} 1 \leq i \leq N_c \\ 1 \leq i \leq N_d \end{array}$$

Original TVAE Decoder

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} h_1 = \text{SiLU}(\text{KAN}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(z_j)) \\ h_2 = \text{SiLU}(\text{KAN}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(h_1)) \\ \tilde{\alpha}_{i,j} = \tanh(\text{KAN}_{128 \rightarrow 1}(h_2)) \\ \hat{\alpha}_{i,j} \sim \mathcal{N}(\tilde{\alpha}_{i,j}, \delta_i) \\ \hat{\beta}_{i,j} \sim \text{softmax}(\text{KAN}_{128 \rightarrow m_i}(h_2)) \\ \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{i,j} \sim \text{softmax}(\text{KAN}_{128 \rightarrow |D_i|}(h_2)) \\ p_{\theta}(\mathbf{r}_j | z_j) = \prod_{i=1}^{N_c} \mathbb{P}(\hat{\alpha}_{i,j} = \alpha_{i,j}) \prod_{i=1}^{N_c} \mathbb{P}(\hat{\beta}_{i,j} = \beta_{i,j}) \prod_{i=1}^{N_d} \mathbb{P}(\hat{\alpha}_{i,j} = \alpha_{i,j}) \end{array} \right. \begin{array}{l} 1 \leq i \leq N_c \\ 1 \leq i \leq N_d \end{array}$$

KAN-TVAE Decoder

Figure 3.3: Comparison between the original TVAE and KAN-TVAE decoder architectures.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} h_1 = \text{ReLU}(\text{FC}_{|\mathbf{r}_j| \rightarrow 128}(\mathbf{r}_j)) \\ h_2 = \text{ReLU}(\text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(h_1)) \\ \mu = \text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(h_2) \\ \sigma = \exp\left(\frac{1}{2} \text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(h_2)\right) \\ q_{\phi}(z_j | \mathbf{r}_j) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma \mathbf{I}) \end{array} \right.$$

Original TVAE Encoder

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} h_1 = \text{SiLU}(\text{KAN}_{|\mathbf{r}_j| \rightarrow 128}(\mathbf{r}_j)) \\ h_2 = \text{SiLU}(\text{KAN}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(h_1)) \\ \mu = \text{KAN}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(h_2) \\ \sigma = \exp\left(\frac{1}{2} \text{KAN}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(h_2)\right) \\ q_{\phi}(z_j | \mathbf{r}_j) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma \mathbf{I}) \end{array} \right.$$

KAN-TVAE Encoder

Figure 3.4: Comparison between the original TVAE and KAN-TVAE encoder architectures.

3.1.3 Hybrid_CTGAN & Hybrid_TVAE

In order to evaluate alternative variants of the full substitution of MLP layers with KANLinear layers, as done in KAN-CTGAN and KAN-TVAE, the implementation and testing of Hybrid-CTGAN and Hybrid-TVAE were also conducted. These hybrid models replace only the first hidden layer of CTGAN and TVAE with a KANLinear, while retaining standard MLPs for the remaining layers. Two are the motivations behind this design choice. First, to enable richer representation learning at the initial stage of the network, where capturing patterns might be most valuable, and second, to reduce computational overhead compared to using KANs throughout the entire architecture.

In the code implementation, the architecture is modular and allows for replacing any specific MLP layer with a KANLinear layer. However, for the purpose of this thesis, the focus is solely on the configuration in which only the first hidden layer is substituted. The rest of the CTGAN and TVAE architectures remain unchanged, including all hyperparameters and training procedures. Below, the architectures of the generator and discriminator of Hybrid-CTGAN (Figure 3.5) and the encoder and decoder of Hybrid-TVAE (Figure 3.6) are illustrated in the same schematic format and notation introduced earlier for KAN-CTGAN and KAN-TVAE. The corresponding code can be found in Appendix C.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} h_0 = z \oplus \text{cond} \\ h_1 = h_0 \oplus \text{SiLU}(\text{BN}(\text{KAN}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|\rightarrow 256}(h_0))) \\ h_2 = h_1 \oplus \text{ReLU}(\text{BN}(\text{FC}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|+256\rightarrow 256}(h_1))) \\ \hat{\alpha}_i = \tanh(\text{FC}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|+512\rightarrow 1}(h_2)) \\ \hat{\beta}_i = \text{gumbel}_{0.2}(\text{FC}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|+512\rightarrow m_i}(h_2)) \\ \hat{\mathbf{d}}_i = \text{gumbel}_{0.2}(\text{FC}_{|\text{cond}|+|z|+512\rightarrow |D_i|}(h_2)) \end{array} \right. \quad \begin{array}{l} 1 \leq i \leq N_c \\ 1 \leq i \leq N_c \\ 1 \leq i \leq N_d \end{array}$$

Hybrid-CTGAN Generator

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} h_0 = r_1 \oplus \dots \oplus r_{10} \oplus \text{cond}_1 \oplus \dots \oplus \text{cond}_{10} \\ h_1 = \text{drop}(\text{SiLU}_{0.2}(\text{BN}(\text{KAN}_{10|\text{cond}|+10\rightarrow 256}(h_0)))) \\ h_2 = \text{drop}(\text{leaky}_{0.2}(\text{FC}_{256\rightarrow 256}(h_1))) \\ \mathcal{C}(\cdot) = \text{FC}_{256\rightarrow 1}(h_2) \end{array} \right.$$

Hybrid-CTGAN Discriminator

Figure 3.5: Comparison of Hybrid-CTGAN Generator and Discriminator, where only the first MLP layer is replaced by KANLinear.

3.1.4 Gen_KAN_CTGAN & Disc_KAN_CTGAN

The GAN framework, as described throughout this thesis, is structured as an adversarial game between the generator and discriminator. The generator’s ob-

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} h_1 = \text{SiLU}(\text{KAN}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(z_j)) \\ h_2 = \text{ReLU}(\text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(h_1)) \\ \tilde{\alpha}_{i,j} = \tanh(\text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow 1}(h_2)) \\ \hat{\alpha}_{i,j} \sim \mathcal{N}(\tilde{\alpha}_{i,j}, \delta_i) \\ \hat{\beta}_{i,j} \sim \text{softmax}(\text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow m_i}(h_2)) \\ \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{i,j} \sim \text{softmax}(\text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow |D_i|}(h_2)) \\ p_{\theta}(\mathbf{r}_j | z_j) = \prod_{i=1}^{N_c} \mathbb{P}(\hat{\alpha}_{i,j} = \alpha_{i,j}) \prod_{i=1}^{N_c} \mathbb{P}(\hat{\beta}_{i,j} = \beta_{i,j}) \prod_{i=1}^{N_d} \mathbb{P}(\hat{\alpha}_{i,j} = \alpha_{i,j}) \end{array} \right. \begin{array}{l} 1 \leq i \leq N_c \\ 1 \leq i \leq N_c \\ 1 \leq i \leq N_c \\ 1 \leq i \leq N_d \end{array}$$

Hybrid-TVAE Decoder

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} h_1 = \text{SiLU}(\text{KAN}_{|\mathbf{r}_j| \rightarrow 128}(\mathbf{r}_j)) \\ h_2 = \text{ReLU}(\text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(h_1)) \\ \mu = \text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(h_2) \\ \sigma = \exp(\frac{1}{2} \text{FC}_{128 \rightarrow 128}(h_2)) \\ q_{\phi}(z_j | \mathbf{r}_j) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma \mathbf{I}) \end{array} \right.$$

Hybrid-TVAE Encoder

Figure 3.6: Comparison of Hybrid-TVAE Encoder and Decoder, where only the first MLP layer is replaced by KANLinear.

jective is to synthesize data that can "fool" the discriminator, ideally to the point where the discriminator can no longer distinguish between real and synthetic data, and on the other hand, the discriminator's objective is to distinguish clearly between the two types of input data.

Motivated by this adversarial design, two additional CTGAN variants were developed: GenKAN-CTGAN and DiscKAN-CTGAN. In GenKAN-CTGAN, only the generator adopts KANLinear layers, while the discriminator remains unchanged from the original CTGAN. Conversely, in DiscKAN-CTGAN, only the discriminator is modified to use KANLinear layers, with the generator retaining the standard MLP-based architecture. The intuition behind these variants is to explore whether introducing KANs asymmetrically (i.e., to only one component of the CTGAN) can unbalance the adversarial dynamics in a beneficial way. This setup may either enhance the modeling capacity of one side or lead to a more stable equilibrium.

Since the generator and discriminator used in GenKAN-CTGAN and DiscKAN-CTGAN are identical to those already presented in Figure 3.1 and 3.2, and their code is also provided in Appendix A, no additional schematic representation is necessary.

3.2 Benchmarking

The KAN-based models introduced in the previous sections were evaluated using three widely used benchmarking criteria, as outlined in Section 2.4: Statistical Fidelity, Computational Efficiency, and Machine Learning Utility. To assess the first two aspects, Statistical Fidelity and Computational Efficiency, the benchmarking framework proposed by Xu et al.[124], known as SDGym[245], was employed. This framework was originally introduced in the same paper as CTGAN and TVAE[124], ensuring proper comparison with these two models, which is the focus of this thesis. However, SDGym does not natively support the evaluation of Machine Learning Utility. Therefore, a custom evaluation pipeline was implemented based on the Train on Synthetic, Test on Real (TSTR) paradigm.

The baseline models used for comparison are the original CTGAN and TVAE, as the primary objective of this thesis is to investigate how substituting MLPs with KANLinear layers affects synthetic data quality in these well-established architectures. The datasets used in this benchmarking process, along with detailed descriptions of the evaluation metrics, are provided in the following subsections.

3.2.1 Datasets

For the evaluation of Statistical Fidelity and Computational Efficiency, the default datasets provided by the SDGym framework were used (See Table 3.1). Due to limitations in computational and memory resources, only a reduced portion of each dataset was utilized. Specifically, SDGym provides a *limited_dataset_size* parameter, which was set to *True* such that only 100 rows (randomly sampled) and the first 10 columns of each dataset were used for benchmarking. To ensure a more robust assessment of statistical fidelity, the evaluation was repeated 10 times, and the Quality Score (explained in the next subsection) was then averaged across these 10 repetitions on random subsets of the data.

Table 3.1: Default datasets from SDGym used in this study. For all benchmarks, only 100 rows and 10 features were used due to hardware limitations.

Dataset Name	Abbreviation	# Rows / Features
Adult	AD	100 / 10
Alarm	AL	100 / 10
Census	CE	100 / 10
Child	CH	100 / 10
Expedia Hotel Logs	EH	100 / 10
Insurance	IN	100 / 10
Intrusion	IT	100 / 10
News	NE	100 / 10
Coverttype	CO	100 / 10

On the other hand, the eight datasets chosen for the evaluation of Machine Learning Utility were selected to balance those suited for regression tasks and those suited for classification tasks. Several of these datasets overlap with those used by SDGym (Table 3.1) to maintain consistency in evaluation, while others were replaced to ensure a more balanced representation of both task types. All datasets are publicly available, having been sourced from the UCI Machine Learning Repository or Kaggle. Table 3.2 lists the datasets used for this evaluation, along with their associated task type and characteristics.

Table 3.2: Datasets used for the Machine Learning Utility evaluation. The *# Class* column is populated only for classification tasks.

Dataset Name	Abbreviation	Task Type	# Class	# Rows	# Features
Adult	AD	Class.	2	48842	14
Alarm	AL	Class.	3	102319	15
Beijing	BE	Reg.	–	43824	13
Bike	BK	Reg.	–	17379	17
Covtype	CO	Class.	7	581012	55
Credit	CR	Class.	2	32581	12
Energy	EN	Reg.	–	19735	29
News	NE	Reg.	–	39644	61

Before being passed to the Synthetic Data Generators (i.e., CTGAN, TVAE, and their KAN-based variants), all datasets underwent a preprocessing stage in which missing values were removed and dataset-specific cleaning was applied. For the Alarm dataset (AL), the columns *DateTime*, *ProcessID*, and *AssetID* were removed as they contained identifiers and timestamps not directly relevant to the generation process. Moreover, the target column *AlarmSeverityName* was filtered to retain only three classes: *1 – High*, *2 – Medium*, and *3 – Low*. In the Beijing dataset (BE), the *No* column was discarded because it represented an index rather than a predictive feature. For the Bike dataset (BK), the *instant* and *dteday* columns were removed for similar reasons. Due to memory constraints, only the first 100,000 rows of the Covtype (CO) were retained for the synthetic data generation and Machine Learning Utility evaluation. In the Energy dataset (EN), the *date* column was removed, while in the News dataset (NE), the *url* column was excluded as it only contained web links without predictive values.

3.2.2 SDGym

SDGym is a benchmarking framework for synthetic data generators introduced by Xu et al.[124] in the CTGAN and TVAE introductory paper. It allows for measuring how the synthetic data differs from the real data, and for the scope of this thesis (i.e., to evaluate Computational Efficiency and Statistical Fidelity), the focus was on five features of the overall SDGym evaluation: Train Time, Sample Time, Peak Memory Use, Synthesizer Size, and Quality Score. Train Time refers to the amount of time needed to fit the real data in the synthetic data

generator (i.e., training phase), which is the most computationally expensive part, while Sample Time is the amount of time needed to generate new synthetic data once the synthetic data generator it has already been trained with the real data in the preceding phase. Peak Memory Use refers to the maximum memory the model training utilized in MB, and Synthesizer Size is an estimate of the final size of the trained model, also in MB.

The Quality Score is an aggregate metric provided by the SDMetrics Quality Report[246], designed to assess the overall statistical similarity between real and synthetic data. It is computed as the arithmetic mean of two principal components: Column Shapes and Column Pair Trends.

The Column Shapes metric evaluates the extent to which the marginal distribution of each individual column in the synthetic dataset matches the corresponding column in the real data. For numerical columns, similarity is measured using the KS-Complement, defined as:

$$KS - Complement = 1 - D_{KS}(F_R, F_S) \quad (3.1)$$

where D_{KS} is the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic measuring the maximum absolute difference between the empirical cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) F_R (real) and F_S (synthetic). This yields a value between 0 and 1, with higher scores indicating stronger similarity.

For categorical and boolean columns, similarity is quantified using the TV-Complement, computed from the Total Variation Distance (TVD) between the real and synthetic category distributions:

$$\delta(R, S) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} |R_\omega - S_\omega| \quad (3.2)$$

where Ω is the set of all possible categories in the column, and R_ω, S_ω represent the frequency of category ω in the real and synthetic datasets, respectively. The TV-Complement is then defined as $1 - \delta(R, S)$, again producing a value between 0 and 1, where higher is better. Finally, the Column Shapes score is computed by averaging the individual per-column similarity scores across both numerical and categorical columns.

The Column Pair Trends component evaluates how well pairwise relationships between features are preserved in the synthetic data compared to the real dataset. This component considers both numerical-numerical and combinations involving categorical or boolean variables. For numerical-numerical column pairs, the Correlation similarity metric is used. Given a pair of columns A and B , the Pearson correlation coefficient is computed separately for the real dataset R and the synthetic dataset S , resulting in two values $R_{A,B}$ and $S_{A,B}$. The similarity score is then defined as:

$$score = 1 - \frac{|S_{A,B} - R_{A,B}|}{2} \quad (3.3)$$

This score ranges from 0 to 1, where higher values indicate better preservation of linear relationships between variables. While SDMetrics supports both

Pearson and Spearman correlation, the Pearson correlation was used in this study.

For categorical-categorical pairs (or mixed-type pairs, where a numerical column is discretized into bins), the Contingency Similarity metric is employed. For a pair of columns A and B , contingency tables are computed on both the real and synthetic datasets, normalized to represent empirical joint distributions. Then, the Total Variation Distance (TVD) between these distributions is calculated as:

$$\delta(R, S) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\alpha \in A} \sum_{\beta \in B} |S_{\alpha, \beta} - R_{\alpha, \beta}| \quad (3.4)$$

where α and β are the possible categories in columns A and B , and R, S refer to the real and synthetic frequencies for those categories. The final similarity score is defined as the TV-Complement described above:

$$score = 1 - \delta(R, S) \quad (3.5)$$

As with the Column Shapes component, the per-pair similarity scores are averaged across all column pairs to obtain the overall Column Pair Trends score. The overall Quality Score is computed as the mean of the Column Shapes and Column Pair Trends scores:

$$QualityScore = \frac{ColumnShapes + ColumnPairTrends}{2} \quad (3.6)$$

The Quality Score provides an interpretable indicator (in the range $[0, 1]$) of the statistical fidelity of the synthetic data relative to the real data. However, it captures only distributional similarity and does not reflect the performance of synthetic data in downstream machine learning tasks. Therefore, a custom benchmark framework was developed to assess Machine Learning Utility, as described in the following subsection.

3.2.3 Custom Benchmarks for ML Utility

To assess the machine learning utility of the synthetic datasets generated by the KAN-based models, a custom benchmarking pipeline was developed. This framework aims to evaluate how well synthetic data can support predictive modeling by comparing the performance of machine learning models trained on synthetic data to those trained on real data. The core evaluation strategy follows the widely used Train on Synthetic, Test on Real (TSTR) paradigm.

In the context of regression tasks (i.e., for datasets associated with regression tasks), the evaluation proceeds by first splitting the real dataset into a training and test set using repeated holdout evaluation, in order to reduce the influence of a particular data split on performance estimation. Several commonly used regression models (XGBoost, Random Forest, SVM, and Linear Regression) are then trained separately on the real training data (used as a reference benchmark), and on synthetic datasets generated by each of the models under study

(See section 3.1). After training, all models are evaluated on the same real test set to ensure consistency and comparability. Their performance is measured using two standard regression metrics: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean Squared Error (MSE). For each model and dataset, the average values of these metrics are computed across multiple repeats to account for variance and sampling instability.

While these raw metrics already provide useful insight, they are not always directly comparable across different generators. For this reason, the benchmarking pipeline includes a scoring transformation that normalizes the differences between synthetic-trained and real-trained performance. In particular, two normalized scores are calculated: one for MAE and one for RMSE (derived from MSE). For both, the absolute difference between the synthetic and real model performance is computed, and then scaled by the original real metric value. These differences are then subtracted from one, yielding similarity scores that approach 1 when synthetic-trained models perform similarly to real-trained ones:

$$MetricScore = 1 - \frac{|R_M - S_M|}{R_M} \quad (3.7)$$

where R_M denotes the average performance of models trained on real data for metric M (MAE or RMSE), and S_M the corresponding performance from models trained on synthetic data.

The overall score is then calculated as the average of the MAE and RMSE similarity scores:

$$OverallScore = \frac{MAEScore + RMSEScore}{2} \quad (3.8)$$

The *OverallScore* ranges theoretically from negative infinity to one, where values near 1 indicate that the synthetic data supports learning predictive patterns almost as effectively as real data.

For classification tasks, the evaluation framework mirrors the regression pipeline in structure, but it adopts classification-appropriate models and metrics. Specifically, four widely used classifiers were employed: Logistic Regression, Random Forest, Linear SVC, and XGBoost Classifier. Each model was trained on both real and synthetic datasets using repeated random holdouts, as in the case of the evaluation for regression tasks.

To assess predictive performance, four standard classification metrics were used: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-score. After collecting these metrics for all models and generators, a normalized score was computed for each metric using Equation 3.7.

The overall classification utility score was then computed by averaging the individual normalized scores across all four metrics:

$$OverallScore = \frac{AccScore + PrecScore + RecScore + F1Score}{4} \quad (3.9)$$

The code implementing this benchmarking pipeline is publicly available at: [Code on GitHub](#) . The classification procedures are encapsulated in the functions *evaluate_all_models_classification* and *visualize_class_score*, while the analogous regression counterparts are *evaluate_all_models* and *visualize_reg_score*.

Chapter 4

Results

As outlined in Chapter 3, the evaluation framework for this thesis was designed to assess three core aspects of synthetic data quality: *Statistical Fidelity*, *Computational Efficiency*, and *Machine Learning Utility*. The present chapter reports the results obtained through this framework, with each benchmark corresponding to a dedicated section. Detailed descriptions of the evaluation metrics and procedures can be found in Chapter 3.

4.1 Statistical Fidelity & Computational Efficiency

This section presents the results of the benchmarking process for evaluating statistical fidelity and computational efficiency across all synthesizers and datasets. As previously discussed in Chapter 3, the *Quality Score* quantifies how closely the synthetic data reproduces the statistical characteristics of the real dataset, while the *Training Time*, *Sampling Time*, *Peak Memory Usage*, and *Synthesizer Size* capture the computational cost of using each model. All these metrics were computed using the SDGym[245] benchmarking framework.

Quality Scores were calculated from 10 random samples of the datasets described in Section 3.2.1. The values reported in the following tables are the mean and standard deviation across these iterations. Higher Quality Scores indicate better statistical alignment, while lower training and sampling times, memory usage, and model size reflect greater computational efficiency. The tables below present these metrics for each generator, evaluated separately on each dataset.

Table 4.1: Comparison of training time, memory usage, synthesizer size, sampling time, and quality score for custom synthesizers on the *adult* dataset.

Synthesizer	Train Time (s)	Peak Mem (MB)	Synth Size (MB)	Sample Time (s)	Quality Score
CTGAN	26.75	2.85	1.04	0.1413	0.7875 \pm 0.0204
TVAE	9.81	2.11	0.29	0.1381	0.7443 \pm 0.0062
KAN-CTGAN	54.55	18.67	8.86	0.1543	0.7768 \pm 0.0179
KAN-TVAE	18.79	4.61	1.85	0.1478	0.6746 \pm 0.0155
HYBRID_KAN_CTGAN	35.31	6.15	2.76	0.1460	0.7820 \pm 0.0097
Disc_KAN_CTGAN	46.39	2.82	1.04	0.1405	0.7404 \pm 0.0276
Gen_KAN_CTGAN	35.82	18.64	8.86	0.1521	0.8043 \pm 0.0188
HYBRID_KAN_TVAE	11.98	2.61	0.89	0.1415	0.7079 \pm 0.0106

Table 4.2: Comparison of training time, memory usage, synthesizer size, sampling time, and quality score for custom synthesizers on the *alarm* dataset.

Synthesizer	Train Time (s)	Peak Mem (MB)	Synth Size (MB)	Sample Time (s)	Quality Score
CTGAN	25.59	2.39	0.80	0.1397	0.4228 \pm 0.0145
TVAE	8.80	1.12	0.26	0.1367	0.3864 \pm 0.0612
KAN-CTGAN	52.78	15.20	6.63	0.1524	0.4252 \pm 0.0084
KAN-TVAE	17.63	4.30	1.60	0.1476	0.3846 \pm 0.0023
HYBRID_KAN_CTGAN	34.00	4.91	2.16	0.1442	0.4324 \pm 0.0171
Disc_KAN_CTGAN	44.92	2.39	0.81	0.1379	0.4080 \pm 0.0072
Gen_KAN_CTGAN	34.16	15.19	6.63	0.1509	0.4419 \pm 0.0102
HYBRID_KAN_TVAE	11.03	2.52	0.85	0.1404	0.3769 \pm 0.0032

Table 4.3: Comparison of training time, memory usage, synthesizer size, sampling time, and quality score for custom synthesizers on the *census* dataset.

Synthesizer	Train Time (s)	Peak Mem (MB)	Synth Size (MB)	Sample Time (s)	Quality Score
CTGAN	26.99	2.95	1.12	0.1429	0.6564 \pm 0.0246
TVAE	10.22	2.46	0.30	0.1382	0.7870 \pm 0.0041
KAN-CTGAN	54.84	24.71	9.64	0.1530	0.7150 \pm 0.0113
KAN-TVAE	19.49	4.68	1.94	0.1497	0.6814 \pm 0.0147
HYBRID_KAN_CTGAN	35.60	6.56	2.97	0.1466	0.7103 \pm 0.0159
Disc_KAN_CTGAN	46.64	2.94	1.12	0.1415	0.6845 \pm 0.0174
Gen_KAN_CTGAN	36.21	24.68	9.64	0.1544	0.7021 \pm 0.0295
HYBRID_KAN_TVAE	12.49	2.62	0.89	0.1428	0.7258 \pm 0.0314

Table 4.4: Comparison of training time, memory usage, synthesizer size, sampling time, and quality score for custom synthesizers on the *child* dataset.

Synthesizer	Train Time (s)	Peak Mem (MB)	Synth Size (MB)	Sample Time (s)	Quality Score
CTGAN	24.77	2.50	0.84	0.1352	0.8801 \pm 0.0178
TVAE	7.02	1.12	0.25	0.1300	0.8705 \pm 0.0111
KAN-CTGAN	52.02	15.66	6.76	0.1481	0.8940 \pm 0.0130
KAN-TVAE	15.89	4.13	1.57	0.1398	0.8137 \pm 0.0152
HYBRID_KAN_CTGAN	33.19	5.21	2.29	0.1393	0.8802 \pm 0.0155
Disc_KAN_CTGAN	44.28	2.50	0.84	0.1361	0.8398 \pm 0.0231
Gen_KAN_CTGAN	33.64	15.64	6.77	0.1470	0.9021 \pm 0.0163
HYBRID_KAN_TVAE	9.15	2.42	0.85	0.1327	0.8111 \pm 0.0123

Table 4.5: Comparison of training time, memory usage, synthesizer size, sampling time, and quality score for custom synthesizers on the *insurance* dataset.

Synthesizer	Train Time (s)	Peak Mem (MB)	Synth Size (MB)	Sample Time (s)	Quality Score
CTGAN	24.95	2.55	0.87	0.1368	0.7184 ± 0.0219
TVAE	7.50	1.11	0.26	0.1314	0.6313 ± 0.0103
KAN-CTGAN	52.32	16.12	7.08	0.1489	0.7321 ± 0.0147
KAN-TVAE	16.43	4.31	1.61	0.1417	0.4919 ± 0.0270
HYBRID_KAN_CTGAN	33.39	5.34	2.35	0.1404	0.7203 ± 0.0170
Disc_KAN_CTGAN	44.31	2.54	0.87	0.1365	0.6812 ± 0.0229
Gen_KAN_CTGAN	33.93	16.11	7.09	0.1481	0.7448 ± 0.0233
HYBRID_KAN_TVAE	9.63	2.45	0.85	0.1340	0.5958 ± 0.0102

Table 4.6: Comparison of training time, memory usage, synthesizer size, sampling time, and quality score for custom synthesizers on the *intrusion* dataset.

Synthesizer	Train Time (s)	Peak Mem (MB)	Synth Size (MB)	Sample Time (s)	Quality Score
CTGAN	26.23	2.47	0.87	0.1458	0.6424 ± 0.0187
TVAE	10.43	1.44	0.28	0.1444	0.6601 ± 0.0120
KAN-CTGAN	53.36	16.31	7.44	0.1569	0.6926 ± 0.0233
KAN-TVAE	19.52	4.45	1.72	0.1545	0.6304 ± 0.0296
HYBRID_KAN_CTGAN	34.67	5.22	2.33	0.1496	0.7052 ± 0.0146
Disc_KAN_CTGAN	45.48	2.47	0.87	0.1451	0.6818 ± 0.0340
Gen_KAN_CTGAN	35.18	16.31	7.44	0.1566	0.6444 ± 0.0290
HYBRID_KAN_TVAE	12.49	2.64	0.87	0.1475	0.6020 ± 0.0055

Table 4.7: Comparison of training time, memory usage, synthesizer size, sampling time, and quality score for custom synthesizers on the *news* dataset.

Synthesizer	Train Time (s)	Peak Mem (MB)	Synth Size (MB)	Sample Time (s)	Quality Score
CTGAN	16.53	2.29	0.80	0.1452	0.8934 ± 0.0110
TVAE	13.44	1.51	0.29	0.1484	0.8714 ± 0.0041
KAN-CTGAN	43.39	14.81	6.82	0.1575	0.8925 ± 0.0048
KAN-TVAE	22.93	4.51	1.74	0.1590	0.8594 ± 0.0067
HYBRID_KAN_CTGAN	24.99	5.47	1.99	0.1506	0.8883 ± 0.0093
Disc_KAN_CTGAN	35.73	2.28	0.80	0.1457	0.8823 ± 0.0176
Gen_KAN_CTGAN	24.88	14.82	6.82	0.1550	0.9018 ± 0.0097
HYBRID_KAN_TVAE	15.37	2.69	0.89	0.1511	0.8517 ± 0.0062

Table 4.8: Comparison of training time, memory usage, synthesizer size, sampling time, and quality score for custom synthesizers on the *covtype* dataset.

Synthesizer	Train Time (s)	Peak Mem (MB)	Synth Size (MB)	Sample Time (s)	Quality Score
CTGAN	18.19	2.37	0.85	0.1429	0.8332 ± 0.0193
TVAE	15.08	1.91	0.31	0.1479	0.9104 ± 0.0026
KAN-CTGAN	44.62	15.28	7.24	0.1567	0.8416 ± 0.0177
KAN-TVAE	24.40	4.70	1.83	0.1578	0.8968 ± 0.0079
HYBRID_KAN_CTGAN	26.47	5.63	2.04	0.1484	0.8342 ± 0.0135
Disc_KAN_CTGAN	37.08	2.38	0.85	0.1443	0.8074 ± 0.0125
Gen_KAN_CTGAN	26.65	15.28	7.24	0.1565	0.8522 ± 0.0124
HYBRID_KAN_TVAE	17.21	2.76	0.90	0.1496	0.8924 ± 0.0057

4.2 ML Utility

This section reports the results of the third benchmark category: Machine Learning (ML) Utility. As detailed in Section 3.2.3, this evaluation uses a Train-on-Synthetic-Test-on-Real (TSTR) framework to quantify how well predictive models trained on synthetic data perform when tested on real data. A higher ML Utility score (ranging from $-\infty$ to 1) indicates greater similarity in predictive power between the synthetic-trained and real-trained models. This implies that the synthetic data can effectively substitute real data in downstream machine learning tasks, one of the primary motivations for using synthetic data in practical applications.

Two sets of experiments were conducted: one for regression tasks and one for classification tasks. The following tables summarize the TSTR scores obtained by each synthesizer across multiple datasets (See Table 3.2).

Table 4.9: ML Utility scores (TSTR-based) for regression tasks across four datasets: Energy (EN), News (NE), Beijing (BE), and Bike (BK). The scores represent the similarity in predictive performance between models trained on synthetic versus real data (See Section 3.2.3).

Synthesizer	EN	NE	BE	BK
CTGAN	0.59	0.84	0.48	-0.84
TVAE	0.86	0.10	0.56	0.29
KAN-CTGAN	0.58	0.37	0.42	-1.47
KAN-TVAE	0.87	-0.22	0.69	0.63
HYBRID_KAN_CTGAN	0.55	0.66	0.46	-1.54
Disc_KAN_CTGAN	0.48	0.86	0.51	-3.05
Gen_KAN_CTGAN	0.60	0.98	0.50	-0.69
HYBRID_KAN_TVAE	0.84	0.52	0.49	0.29

Table 4.10: ML Utility scores (TSTR-based) for classification tasks across four datasets: Adult (AD), Alarm (AL), Covtype (CO), and Credit (CR). The scores represent the similarity in predictive performance between models trained on synthetic versus real data (See Section 3.2.3).

Synthesizer	AD	AL	CO	CR
CTGAN	0.96	0.98	0.76	0.91
TVAE	0.97	0.99	0.73	0.93
KAN-CTGAN	0.95	0.97	0.79	0.91
KAN-TVAE	0.95	0.99	0.87	0.92
HYBRID_KAN_CTGAN	0.94	0.95	0.77	0.85
Disc_KAN_CTGAN	0.96	0.86	0.76	0.90
Gen_KAN_CTGAN	0.94	0.97	0.69	0.91
HYBRID_KAN_TVAE	0.97	0.99	0.80	0.93

Chapter 5

Discussion & Conclusion

This chapter addresses the research questions initially introduced in Section 1.5 and discusses the results in light of those questions. The primary goal of this thesis was to explore the use of Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs) as a replacement for classic MLPs within established synthetic data generators (i.e., CTGAN and TVAE), and to evaluate their impact on Statistical Fidelity, Machine Learning Utility, and Computational Efficiency. The three central research questions were:

1. Do KAN-based variants of CTGAN and TVAE retain or improve fidelity and utility compared to their MLP-based counterparts?
2. Can KANs effectively model the complex joint distributions characteristic of real-world tabular datasets?
3. What trade-offs arise in terms of training time, stability, and architectural complexity when using KANs instead of MLPs?

The discussion that follows is structured to answer each of these questions in light of the empirical results presented in Chapter 4. Then, the current work’s limitations will be acknowledged, along with proposed directions for future research.

5.1 Question 1: Fidelity and Utility Compared to MLP Counterparts

From the assessment of Statistical Fidelity, it emerges that, except for the case of the *Census* and *Covtype* datasets, KAN-based models generally yielded higher average Quality Scores compared to their vanilla MLP-based counterparts. Out of the eight datasets evaluated, *Gen_KAN_CTGAN* achieved the best Quality Score in five cases (*Adult* 4.1, *Alarm* 4.2, *Child* 4.4, *Insurance* 4.5, and *News*

4.7), *HYBRID_KAN_CTGAN* in one case (*Intrusion* 4.6), and *TVAE* was the best performing models for two dataset (*Census* 4.3 and *Covtype* 4.8).

These results suggest that KAN-based architectures can not only retain, but in several cases improve statistical fidelity compared to their MLP-based counterparts, CTGAN and TVAE. A plausible explanation for this improvement lies in the intrinsic nature of KANs themselves. As thoroughly discussed in Section 1.4, KANs rely on learnable B-spline activations, which are significantly more flexible than the linear transformations used in traditional MLPs. In KANs, there are no global weight updates, but localized function adaptation thanks to B-splines. Therefore, I hypothesize that this local adaptability may contribute to a more accurate modeling of complex feature distributions, which in turn leads to synthetic data that better preserves the statistical structure of the original dataset. Particularly noteworthy is that the *Gen_KAN_CTGAN* variant achieved the highest Quality Score in five of the datasets. This model replaces only the generator component of the CTGAN with KAN layers while leaving the discriminator architecture untouched. Thus, the generator may play a more critical role in determining the statistical fidelity of synthetic data than the discriminator. Even though this introduces a mismatch in capacity and structure between the generator and discriminator, potentially disrupting GAN equilibrium, the empirical results suggest that the improved representational power of the generator outweighs such concerns. However, this hypothesis remains speculative and needs further investigation. A deeper theoretical analysis of the interaction between KAN-enhanced generators and standard discriminators (and vice versa) would provide more accurate answers, making it a valuable direction for future work.

As for the second part of Question 1, namely, whether KAN-based models retain or improve Machine Learning utility, the results presented in Chapter 4 reveal some interesting patterns. In the case of regression tasks (Table 4.9), at least one of the KAN-based models consistently outperformed both CTGAN and TVAE across all datasets. *KAN-TVAE* achieved the highest ML utility scores¹ in three out of four datasets, while *Gen_KAN_CTGAN* led in the remaining one. The classification results (Table 4.10) show a more balanced scenario. In three out of four datasets, the original TVAE model performed on par with certain KAN-based variants (i.e., *HYBRID_KAN_TVAE* and *KAN-TVAE*). In the remaining case, however, *KAN-TVAE* outperformed all other models.

In regression tasks, the variation in ML utility scores among different models is substantially greater than in classification settings. This discrepancy primarily stems from the nature of the evaluation metrics. For regression, the ML utility score is computed using Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), both of which span a theoretically unbounded range from zero to infinity. Consequently, even small deviations in model performance can translate into significant changes in the normalized score, including negative values when the difference between real and synthetic metrics is substantial. In the ML utility scores for the *Bike* dataset, this is particularly evident, where

¹See Section 3.2.3 for the explanation of how the ML utility scores are computed.

some models achieved negative scores (see Table 4.9).

By contrast, classification metrics such as Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1 Score are all constrained to the range $[0, 1]$, inherently limiting variability and making performance comparisons more stable (Table 4.10).

Despite this variability, KAN-based models, especially *KAN-TVAE* and *Gen_KAN_CTGAN*, demonstrated superior ML utility across most regression datasets. Notably, *Gen_KAN_CTGAN* achieved an almost perfect score of 0.98 on the *News*, which, with its 61 features, presents a particularly high-dimensional and complex learning challenge (Table 3.2). Thus, the representational flexibility of KANs might offer distinct advantages in capturing inter-column dependencies in complex tabular data. Interestingly, *KAN-TVAE*, which performed best on three out of four regression datasets, performed the worst on the *News* dataset. This divergence may indicate that the CTGAN framework, when paired with a KAN-based generator, is more suited for high-dimensional data than the TVAE architecture. The results imply that the choice of underlying generative framework (CTGAN vs. TVAE) interacts non-trivially with the inclusion of KAN layers, particularly under increasing data complexity. Nonetheless, observing a single dataset is insufficient to draw conclusive results, and this could be another intriguing area for future research.

These patterns reinforce the hypothesis that KANs, through their use of locally adaptive B-spline activations, enhance the model’s ability to present subtle distributional characteristics and inter-column correlations, which are not captured by the assessment of traditional statistical fidelity metrics. Since ML utility scores reflect how well predictive performance is preserved when training on synthetic rather than real data, the observed improvements in KAN-based models may indicate better retention of these critical dependencies. However, as will be further noted in Section 5.3, this interpretation should be treated with caution, as the Train-on-Synthetic-Test-on-Real (TSTR) framework relies on the heuristic assumption that similar performance implies similar information content in the input datasets. An assumption that, while useful, lacks formal mathematical demonstration.

In the classification tasks, performance differences between models were generally narrower. This, as discussed earlier, may partly result from the bounded nature of the evaluation metrics. Nevertheless, in more challenging scenarios, such as the *Covtype* dataset, which comprises 55 features, KAN-based models, particularly *KAN-TVAE*, once again outperformed their MLP-based counterparts. Even though the CTGAN framework appeared to be more suited for high-dimensional datasets in regression tasks, here *KAN-TVAE* achieved the best performance. This still supports the broader trend that KANs may offer particular advantages in high-dimensional or structurally complex datasets, even when working with classification objectives. While for lower-dimensional datasets, the results in Table 4.10 show that using standard TVAE is just as good as the KAN-based counterparts, but with the advantage, as will be discussed in the next section, of being much more computationally efficient.

5.2 Question 2 & 3: Modeling and Computational Efficiency

Building upon the observations from the previous section, which highlighted the superior performance of KAN-based models, particularly in high-dimensional settings, it is reasonable to argue that these architectures are capable of modeling complex joint distributions in real-world tabular data. The consistently high statistical fidelity scores and strong ML utility performance across a variety of datasets provide empirical evidence in support of this claim. However, it is important to stress that this conclusion is based entirely on empirical evaluation across the eight benchmark datasets presented in Table 4.9. While these datasets are diverse and representative of real-world tabular challenges, they do not constitute exhaustive proof of generalizability. Furthermore, the ability of KANs to model complex distributions has not yet been formalized through theoretical analysis. At present, there is no mathematical framework that rigorously proves that KANs can approximate joint probability distributions more effectively than MLPs under general conditions. Therefore, while the results suggest that KANs offer enhanced modeling capacity, this remains a hypothesis supported by experimental outcomes rather than a universally established property.

While certain KAN-based models demonstrated improvements in statistical fidelity and machine learning utility, these gains come at a computational cost. One of the major trade-offs introduced by the KAN architecture, as also noted in the original KAN paper by Liu et al.[128], is increased time and space complexity. The use of learnable B-splines as activation functions, which replace linear weights in MLPs, significantly increases the number of parameters in the network. This added complexity results in longer training times, greater memory consumption, and larger model sizes when KANs are used in place of MLPs within the CTGAN and TVAE frameworks.

The results presented in Chapter 4 clearly show that models using KAN layers, particularly *KAN-CTGAN* and *KAN-TVAE*, have approximately double the training time compared to their MLP-based counterparts across all tested datasets (see Tables 4.1 through 4.8). Similar trends are visible in terms of peak memory usage and final synthesizer size. In fact, *KAN-CTGAN* and *Gen_KAN-CTGAN* consumed more than six times the memory and storage space compared to the standard CTGAN implementation across the eight tested datasets.

Interestingly, however, *Gen_KAN-CTGAN* maintained relatively efficient training times, significantly lower than *KAN-CTGAN* or *Disc_KAN-CTGAN*, while still achieving in many cases the best performances (see Section 5.1). This suggests that using KANs only in the generator (and not in the discriminator) might offer a viable middle ground, improving representational power without fully incurring the overhead associated with a complete KAN-based architecture.

The computational efficacy metrics discussed above (i.e., training time, mem-

ory usage, and model size) are directly measurable (time and MB) and objectively interpretable, unlike the metrics previously used to measure statistical fidelity and ML Utility. Therefore, these highlight that KAN-based synthetic data generators, while potentially enhancing the modeling capacity of synthetic data generators, introduce significant computational burdens that must be taken into account when employing such models in real-world scenarios.

5.3 Limitations

One of the primary limitations of this thesis concerns the availability of computational resources, which restricted the ability to test the models on larger and more complex datasets when evaluating statistical fidelity through SDGym. Training the synthetic data generators was made feasible by access to a GPU cluster, but certain evaluation procedures were still constrained. In fact, during the assessment of statistical fidelity using the SDGym framework (see Section 3.2.2), I was unable to run the evaluation on full-sized datasets. Instead, I had to downsample each dataset to include only 10 features and 100 rows (as outlined in Table 3.1). This reduction in data complexity likely affects the generalizability of the reported Quality Scores. Nonetheless, this effect was mitigated by evaluating the average Quality Score and relative standard deviations using ten different random samples from each dataset. The modeling ability of synthetic data generators may differ when evaluated on more realistic, full-scale datasets. Thus, further research using complete datasets would be necessary to confirm the robustness of these findings.

Another general limitation, shared with many recent studies on synthetic data generation (see Chapter 2), is the reliance on the Train-on-Synthetic-Test-on-Real (TSTR) framework for evaluating machine learning utility. This approach involves training a model separately on both real and synthetic data, and then testing both models on the same real test set. If the model trained on synthetic data achieves performance similar to the model trained on real data, the utility score is considered high. This evaluation paradigm is based on the heuristic assumption that similar predictive performance indicates that the synthetic data captures the same underlying structure and statistical relationships as the real data. While this assumption often holds in practice, it is important to recognize that there is no formal mathematical guarantee supporting it. It is theoretically possible that two datasets with different distributions could yield similar model performance by chance.

Moreover, TSTR assumes that the downstream tasks remain identical between the real and synthetic datasets, including the target variable and its relationship to the features. In this study, that assumption holds true because all synthetic datasets were generated to closely mimic the structure of the original data (and manually checked for that purpose), preserving column type and target labels. Nonetheless, for general-purpose synthetic data generators that may modify or drop task-relevant features, TSTR could give misleading results. Thus, although TSTR provides a practical and interpretable way to

assess ML utility, its results must be interpreted with caution. A higher utility score does not definitively prove that the synthetic data retains important correlations from the real dataset. The development of more theoretically grounded task-independent evaluation methods for machine learning utility remains an important direction for future research.

A more practical limitation of this study concerns the number and type of baseline models used for comparison. The primary objective was to evaluate KAN-based models relative to their original MLP-based counterparts, namely CTGAN and TVAE. While this made for a clean and controlled experiment design, it limited the scope of the conclusions. In fact, it remains unclear how KAN-based architectures would compare to other state-of-the-art tabular generative models beyond CTGAN and TVAE (e.g., models discussed in Chapter 2). Expanding the comparison to a broader range of models could provide stronger evidence for (or against) the utility of KANs in synthetic data generation.

Furthermore, the introduction of KAN layers brought with it a range of new hyperparameters (as discussed in Chapter 3), including, for example, spline degree and number of knots. In this work, a single configuration was selected and used across all experiments to ensure fair comparison. This, however, may not reflect the full potential of KAN-based models. A more exhaustive hyperparameter optimization process could reveal further improvements or limitations of this architecture.

Lastly, a crucial aspect of synthetic data generation, particularly in privacy-sensitive domains, is the extent to which the generated data protects the privacy of the original dataset. This study did not include any formal assessment of privacy guarantees or risks associated with KAN-based models. Therefore, this represents an important area of future investigation.

5.4 Implications and Future Works

Despite the limitations discussed in the previous section, the findings of this thesis remain valuable when interpreted with appropriate awareness. The KAN-based models introduced here can offer practical benefits to researchers and practitioners seeking to generate high-quality synthetic tabular data, particularly when statistical fidelity and machine learning utility are the main priorities. One of the most important considerations before deploying these models in real-world settings is their computational cost. As shown in Chapter 4, and then discussed in Chapter 5, models that fully replace MLP layers with KANs, such as *KAN-CTGAN* and *KAN-TVAE*, consistently exhibit approximately double the training time, significantly higher peak memory usage, and a much larger model size (in MB). These characteristics may render them unsuitable for low-resource or time-sensitive environments. However, if the application permits a higher computational budget and the goal is to maximize the quality of synthetic data, trying out KAN-based models could be beneficial, most of all on datasets with high dimensionality or complex feature interactions.

Therefore, the KAN-based architectures proposed here should not be viewed

as universal replacements for traditional architectures like CTGAN and TVAE, but rather as powerful alternatives to consider when fidelity and utility are specially important. Their integration into the broader synthetic data landscape adds diversity and flexibility, expanding the set of available tools for practitioners.

From a usability standpoint, the models developed in this thesis are made publicly available via the *KAN-synth* Python package[247], which includes all pretrained model architectures along with evaluation utilities. User can easily benchmark the performance of these models on their won datasets using the same custom evaluation functions described in Section 3.2.3. The full code-base and documentation are available at: https://github.com/cris1618/KAN_synth.

As discussed throughout this final chapter, several promising directions for future research emerge from this study. One of the most immediate extensions involves evaluating the privacy-preserving capabilities of KAN-based models. Although this thesis focused primarily on fidelity and utility, privacy is a critical concern in real-world applications of synthetic data. Techniques such as membership inference attacks, differential privacy, or attribute inference (as outlined in Chapters 1 and 2) could be employed to assess whether KAN-based models unintentionally leak sensitive information.

Another avenue of interest lies in the interpretability of KANs. As highlighted by Liu et al.[128], one of the theoretical advantages of KANs over traditional MLPs is their enhanced transparency. A more systematic investigation, possibly combining visualization techniques with mathematical analysis, could help to improve our understanding of how synthetic data is generated and which features are prioritized during training.

A more theoretical limitation acknowledged in Section 5.3 is the evaluation methodology for Machine Learning Utility. While this study employed the widely used TSTR (Train on Synthetic, Test on Real) framework, its reliance on heuristic assumptions rather than formal guarantees calls for the development of more theoretically grounded evaluation metrics. Therefore, designing robust utility benchmarks remains an open research question in the field.

Finally, expanding the benchmarking scope to include more diverse state-of-the-art synthetic data generators, such as the diffusion-based ones discussed in Chapter 2, would help contextualize the performance of KAN-based models more comprehensively. Furthermore, exploring hyperparameter tuning for KAN-specific components (e.g., spline degree, knot spacing) may uncover configurations that offer better trade-offs between accuracy and efficiency, which could be another interesting topic for future studies.

5.5 Conclusion

The primary objective of this thesis was to assess whether substituting standard MLPs with Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KANs) in the architectures of CTGAN and TVAE could improve the quality of synthetic tabular data. Based on

the experimental results presented in Chapter 4 and the subsequent discussion, it can be concluded that KAN-based models in many cases enhance statistical fidelity and machine learning utility compared to their MLP counterparts, at the cost, however, of reduced computational efficiency. In particular, this work introduced and evaluated six KAN-based models derived from the original CTGAN and TVAE architectures developed by Xu et al.[124]. In addition to this empirical evaluation, the thesis contributes a general overview of the tabular synthetic data generation landscape, synthesizing foundational concepts and recent innovations into a concise review. Furthermore, all the models developed in this study have been made publicly available as part of the *KAN-synth* Python package[247], to provide a practical and accessible tool for researchers and practitioners interested in synthetic data generation.

Beyond the core contributions of this thesis, it is worth ending with a reflection on the broader context in which this work is situated. We live in an era that defies historical comparison, a time in which the boundaries of intelligence itself could be redefined. For the first time in history, we are coexisting with entities that might challenge our position at the apex of intellectual capability. Tools based on artificial intelligence, particularly large language models like ChatGPT, exhibit remarkable competence across domains that were once the exclusive realm of human cognition (e.g., mathematics, physics, languages, etc.). Yet this competence does not equate to human-like intelligence. These models operate as vast probabilistic engines. They are, at the time of writing, powerful mimics, highly optimized to imitate human reasoning without truly understanding it. If intelligence were simply the ability to recall and recombine information at scale, we might already have ceded our intellectual superiority. But clearly, it is something more, and what "more" is remains an open, and increasingly urgent, question.

Still, the implications of such systems extend beyond philosophical debates. Consider, for example, the main theme of this thesis, synthetic data. These data are not drawn directly from the physical world, but generated by models trained on previous data. If synthetic data eventually reaches a point where it is indistinguishable from real data, we may enter a recursive loop in which synthetic data is used to train models that then generate more synthetic data. The real could become obsolete, or at least secondary.

Thus, at the limit where real data can be completely replaced by synthetic data, will human-generated data still have value? Will humans still have value?

*"chi vuol esser lieto, sia:
di doman non c'è certezza."*

Appendix A

KAN-CTGAN

```
class ResidualKAN(Module):
    "KAN residual layer"
    def __init__(self, i, o,
                 grid_size=5,
                 spline_order=3,
                 scale_noise=0.1,
                 scale_base=1.0,
                 scale_spline=1.0,
                 base_activation=torch.nn.SiLU,
                 grid_eps=0.02,
                 grid_range=[-1,1]):
        super().__init__()
        self.kan = KANLinear(i, o,
                             grid_size=grid_size,
                             spline_order=spline_order,
                             scale_noise=scale_noise,
                             scale_base=scale_base,
                             scale_spline=scale_spline,
                             base_activation=base_activation,
                             grid_eps=grid_eps,
                             grid_range=grid_range)
        self.bn = BatchNorm1d(o)
        self.act = torch.nn.SiLU() # Different from CTGAN,
        # Preserving suggestion from KAN original paper

    def forward(self, x):
        out = self.kan(x)
        out = self.bn(out)
        out = self.act(out)
        return torch.cat([out, x], dim=1)
```

Listing A.1: Definition of ResidualKAN class.

```

class GeneratorKAN(Module):
    """
    Generator for the CTGAN using Kolmogorov-Arnold Layers (KAN)
    instead of the standard Residual blocks and Linear layers.
    """
    def __init__(self, embedding_dim, generator_dim, data_dim,
                 grid_size=5, spline_order=3,
                 scale_noise=0.1, scale_base=1.0, scale_spline=1.0,
                 base_activation=torch.nn.SiLU,
                 grid_eps=0.02, grid_range=[-1, 1]):
        """
        Arguments:
        - embedding_dim (int): Input dimension (noise + conditional
          vector).
        - generator_dim (list or tuple of int): List of hidden
          layer sizes.
        - data_dim (int): Output dimension, i.e. the number of
          synthetic features.
        - grid_size, spline_order, etc.: Hyperparameters for the
          KAN layers.
        """
        super(Generator_KAN, self).__init__()
        dim = embedding_dim
        seq = []
        for item in list(generator_dim): # generator_dim = (256,
            256), so the loop runs twice. h0 and h1.
            # Use ResidualKAN
            seq += [ResidualKAN(dim, item,
                                grid_size=grid_size,
                                spline_order=spline_order,
                                scale_noise=scale_noise,
                                scale_base=scale_base,
                                scale_spline=scale_spline,
                                base_activation=base_activation,
                                grid_eps=grid_eps,
                                grid_range=grid_range)]

            dim += item
        # Last KANLayer for the output of dimension data_dim
        seq.append(KANLinear(dim, data_dim)) # h2
        self.seq = Sequential(*seq)

    def forward(self, input_):
        """
        Apply the KAN-based generator to the input.
        """
        data = self.seq(input_)
        return data

```

Listing A.2: Definition of GeneratorKAN class.

```

class DiscriminatorKAN(Module):
    """
    Discriminator for the CTGAN using KAN layers instead of MLP
    layers.
    """
    def __init__(self, input_dim, discriminator_dim, pac=10,
                 grid_size=5, spline_order=3, scale_noise=0.1,
                 scale_base=1.0,
                 scale_spline=1.0, base_activation=torch.nn.SiLU,
                 grid_eps=0.02, grid_range=[-1,1]):
        super(Discriminator_KAN, self).__init__()
        # Compute the effective input dimension after applying the
        # pac trick (as in the original CTGAN discriminator)
        dim = input_dim * pac
        self.pac = pac
        self.pacdim = dim
        seq = []

        # Now use KAN linear layers instead of standard linear
        # layers
        for item in list(discriminator_dim):
            seq += [
                KANLinear(dim, item, grid_size=grid_size,
                          spline_order=spline_order,
                          scale_noise=scale_noise,
                          scale_base=scale_base,
                          scale_spline=scale_spline,
                          base_activation=base_activation,
                          grid_eps=grid_eps,
                          grid_range=grid_range),
                torch.nn.SiLU(0.2), # Better for KAN, LeakyReLU
                replaced
                Dropout(0.5)
            ]
            dim = item

        # The final layer output a single value
        seq += [
            KANLinear(dim, 1, grid_size=grid_size,
                      spline_order=spline_order,
                      scale_noise=scale_noise,
                      scale_base=scale_base,
                      scale_spline=scale_spline,
                      base_activation=base_activation,
                      grid_eps=grid_eps,
                      grid_range=grid_range)
        ]
        self.seq = Sequential(*seq)

        # Calculate Gradient Penalty (Exact same as in the original
        # implementation)
    def calc_gradient_penalty(self, real_data, fake_data, device='
    cpu', pac=10, lambda_=10):
        """Compute the gradient penalty."""
        alpha = torch.rand(real_data.size(0) // pac, 1, 1, device=
        device)
        alpha = alpha.repeat(1, pac, real_data.size(1))

```

```

alpha = alpha.view(-1, real_data.size(1))

interpolates = alpha * real_data + ((1 - alpha) * fake_data
)

disc_interpolates = self(interpolates)

gradients = torch.autograd.grad(
    outputs=disc_interpolates,
    inputs=interpolates,
    grad_outputs=torch.ones(disc_interpolates.size(),
        device=device),
    create_graph=True,
    retain_graph=True,
    only_inputs=True,
)[0]

gradients_view = gradients.view(-1, pac * real_data.size(1)
).norm(2, dim=1) - 1
gradient_penalty = ((gradients_view) ** 2).mean() * lambda_

return gradient_penalty

def forward(self, input_):
    """Apply the Discriminator to the 'input_'."""
    assert input_.size()[0] % self.pac == 0
    return self.seq(input_.view(-1, self.pacdim))

```

Listing A.3: Definition of DiscriminatorKAN class.

Appendix B

KAN-TVAE

```
class DecoderKAN(Module):
    """Decoder for the KAN-TVAE using Kolmogorov-Arnold Layers(KAN)
    instead of the standard Residual blocks and Linear layers.

    This Decoder uses KANLinear to map [mu, log(sd^2)] (Mean and
    log
    of standard deviation squared from the latent space, i.e.
    output
    of the encoder) -> x of dimension data_dim.

    Args:
        embedding_dim (int):
            Size of the input vector.
        decompress_dims (tuple or list of ints):
            Size of each hidden layer.
        data_dim (int):
            Dimensions of the data.
        grid_size, spline_order, etc. (int):
            Hyperparameters for the KAN layers.
    """

    def __init__(self, embedding_dim, decompress_dims, data_dim,
                 grid_size=5, spline_order=3, scale_noise=0.1,
                 scale_base=1.0, scale_spline=1.0, base_activation=
                 torch.nn.SiLU,
                 grid_eps=0.02, grid_range=[-1, 1]):
        super(DecoderKAN, self).__init__()
        dim = embedding_dim
        seq = []
        for item in list(decompress_dims):
            seq += [KANLinear(
                dim, item,
                grid_size=grid_size,
                spline_order=spline_order,
                scale_noise=scale_noise,
                scale_base=scale_base,
                scale_spline=scale_spline,
                base_activation=base_activation,
```

```

        grid_eps=grid_eps,
        grid_range=grid_range
    ), torch.nn.SiLU()] # Use SiLU activation for KAN
    dim = item

    seq.append(KANLinear(dim, data_dim))
    self.seq = Sequential(*seq)
    self.sigma = Parameter(torch.ones(data_dim) * 0.1)

def forward(self, z):
    """Decode the passed input z"""
    return self.seq(z), self.sigma

```

Listing B.1: Definition of DecoderKAN class.

```

class EncoderKAN(Module):
    """Encoder for the KAN_TVAE using Kolmogorov-Arnold Layers (KAN)
    instead of the standard Residual blocks and Linear layers.

    This Encoder uses KANLinear to map  $x \rightarrow [\mu, \log(\text{sd}^2)]$  (Mean,
    and log
    of standard deviation squared).

    Args:
        data_dim (int):
            Dimensions of the data.
        compress_dims (tuple or list of ints):
            Size of each hidden layer.
        embedding_dim (int):
            Size of the output vector.
        grid_size, spline_order, etc. (int):
            Hyperparameters for the KAN layers.
    """

    def __init__(self, data_dim, compress_dims, embedding_dim,
                 grid_size=5, spline_order=3, scale_noise=0.1,
                 scale_base=1.0, scale_spline=1.0, base_activation=
                 torch.nn.SiLU,
                 grid_eps=0.02, grid_range=[-1, 1]):
        super(EncoderKAN, self).__init__()

        # Single KAN with final output size = 2 * embedding_dim
        dim = data_dim
        seq = []
        for item in list(compress_dims):
            seq += [KANLinear(dim, item,
                              grid_size=grid_size,
                              spline_order=spline_order,
                              scale_noise=scale_noise,
                              scale_base=scale_base,
                              scale_spline=scale_spline,
                              base_activation=base_activation,

```

```

        grid_eps=grid_eps,
        grid_range=grid_range)]

    dim = item

    self.seq = Sequential(*seq)
    self.kan_fc1 = KANLinear(dim, embedding_dim) # Optionally
        add KAN hyperparameters
    self.kan_fc2 = KANLinear(dim, embedding_dim)

    def forward(self, x):
        """Encode the passed input x."""
        # x: [batch, data_dim]
        feature = self.seq(x) # [batch, 2*embedding_dim]
        # Splits the outpt into two equal parts along the feature
        dimension
        # Since out has shape [batch, 2*embedding_dim], the
        following code
        # will return a tuple of two tensors, each of shape [batch,
        embedding_dim]
        mu = self.kan_fc1(feature)
        logvar = self.kan_fc2(feature)
        std = torch.exp(0.5 * logvar)
        return mu, std, logvar

```

Listing B.2: Definition of EncoderKAN class.

Appendix C

Hybrid-CTGAN & Hybrid-TVAE

```
class HybridGenerator(Module):
    """
    CTGAN Generator with a single KAN block at layer 'kan_layer_idx',
    the rest remain as standard CTGAN Residuals.
    """
    def __init__(self, embedding_dim, generator_dim, data_dim,
                 kan_layer_idx=0, grid_size=5, spline_order=3,
                 scale_noise=0.1, scale_base=1.0, scale_spline=1.0,
                 base_activation=torch.nn.SiLU,
                 grid_eps=0.02, grid_range=[-1, 1]):
        """
        Arguments:
        - embedding_dim (int): Input dimension (noise + conditional
            vector).
        - generator_dim (list or tuple of int): List of hidden
            layer sizes.
        - data_dim (int): Output dimension, i.e. the number of
            synthetic features.
        - kan_layer_idx (int): Index of the hidden layer to swap in
            KAN for.
        - grid_size, spline_order, etc.: Hyperparameters for the
            KAN layers.
        """
        super(HybridGenerator, self).__init__()
        layers = []
        dim = embedding_dim
        for i, item in enumerate(generator_dim):
            if i == kan_layer_idx:
                layers.append(ResidualKAN(dim, item,
                                          grid_size=grid_size,
                                          spline_order=spline_order,
                                          scale_noise=scale_noise,
                                          scale_base=scale_base,
```

```

        scale_spline=scale_spline
        ,
        base_activation=
            base_activation,
        grid_eps=grid_eps,
        grid_range=grid_range))

        dim += item
    else:
        layers.append(Residual(dim, item))
        dim += item
    layers.append(nn.Linear(dim, data_dim))
    self.net = nn.Sequential(*layers)

def forward(self, x):
    """
    Apply the simple Residual.
    """
    return self.net(x)

```

Listing C.1: Definition of HybridGenerator class.

```

class HybridDiscriminator(Module):
    """
    CTGAN Discriminator with exactly one KANLinear block,
    everything else stays as standard Linear + LeakyReLU + Dropout.
    """
    def __init__(self, input_dim, discriminator_dim, pac=10,
                 kan_layer_idx=0, grid_size=5, spline_order=3,
                 scale_noise=0.1, scale_base=1.0,
                 scale_spline=1.0, base_activation=torch.nn.SiLU,
                 grid_eps=0.02, grid_range=[-1,1]):
        super(HybridDiscriminator, self).__init__()
        # Compute the effective input dimension after applying the
        # pac trick (as in the original CTGAN discriminator)
        dim = input_dim * pac
        self.pac = pac
        self.pacdim = dim
        layers = []

        for i, out_dim in enumerate(discriminator_dim):
            if i == kan_layer_idx:
                layers.append(nn.Sequential(
                    KANLinear(
                        dim, out_dim,
                        grid_size=grid_size,
                        spline_order=spline_order,
                        scale_noise=scale_noise,
                        scale_base=scale_base,
                        scale_spline=scale_spline,
                        base_activation=base_activation,
                        grid_eps=grid_eps,
                        grid_range=grid_range

```

```

        ),
        nn.SiLU(0.2), # Better for KAN
        nn.Dropout(0.5)
    ))
    else:
        layers.append(
            nn.Sequential(
                nn.Linear(dim, out_dim),
                nn.LeakyReLU(0.2),
                nn.Dropout(0.5)
            )
        )
    dim = out_dim

# Final plain linear to a logit
layers.append(nn.Linear(dim, 1))
self.seq = nn.Sequential(*layers)

# Calculate Gradient Penalty (Exact same as in the original
# implementation)
def calc_gradient_penalty(self, real_data, fake_data, device='
cpu', pac=10, lambda_=10):
    """Compute the gradient penalty."""
    alpha = torch.rand(real_data.size(0) // pac, 1, 1, device=
device)
    alpha = alpha.repeat(1, pac, real_data.size(1))
    alpha = alpha.view(-1, real_data.size(1))

    interpolates = alpha * real_data + ((1 - alpha) * fake_data
    )

    disc_interpolates = self(interpolates)

    gradients = torch.autograd.grad(
        outputs=disc_interpolates,
        inputs=interpolates,
        grad_outputs=torch.ones(disc_interpolates.size(),
        device=device),
        create_graph=True,
        retain_graph=True,
        only_inputs=True,
    )[0]

    gradients_view = gradients.view(-1, pac * real_data.size(1)
    ).norm(2, dim=1) - 1
    gradient_penalty = ((gradients_view) ** 2).mean() * lambda_

    return gradient_penalty

def forward(self, input_):
    """Apply the HybridDiscriminator to the 'input_'."""
    assert input_.size()[0] % self.pac == 0
    return self.seq(input_.view(-1, self.pacdim))

```

Listing C.2: Definition of HybridDiscriminator class.

```

class HybridEncoder(Module):
    """TVAE Ecoder with a single KAN block at layer 'kan_layer_idx
    ',
    the rest remain as standard TVAЕ Linear Layers.

    Args:
        data_dim (int):
            Dimensions of the data.
        compress_dims (tuple or list of ints):
            Size of each hidden layer.
        embedding_dim (int):
            Size of the output vector.
        kan_layer_idx (int): index of KAN layer.
        grid_size, spline_order, etc. (int):
            Hyperparameters for the KAN layers.
    """

    def __init__(self, data_dim, compress_dims, embedding_dim,
                 kan_layer_idx=0, grid_size=5, spline_order=3,
                 scale_noise=0.1,
                 scale_base=1.0, scale_spline=1.0, base_activation=
                 torch.nn.SiLU,
                 grid_eps=0.02, grid_range=[-1, 1]):
        super(HybridEncoder, self).__init__()
        self.kan_layer_idx = kan_layer_idx

        # Swapping KAN layer when needed
        layers = []
        dim = data_dim
        for i, out_dim in enumerate(compress_dims):
            if i == kan_layer_idx:
                layers += [
                    KANLinear(dim, out_dim,
                              grid_size=grid_size,
                              spline_order=spline_order,
                              scale_noise=scale_noise,
                              scale_base=scale_base,
                              scale_spline=scale_spline,
                              base_activation=base_activation,
                              grid_eps=grid_eps,
                              grid_range=grid_range),
                    nn.SiLU() # SiLU for KAN
                ]
            else:
                layers += [
                    Linear(dim, out_dim),
                    ReLU()
                ]
            dim = out_dim

        self.seq = Sequential(*layers)
        # Final VAE heads unchanged
        self.fc_mu = Linear(dim, embedding_dim)
        self.fc_logvar = Linear(dim, embedding_dim)

    def forward(self, x):
        """Encode the passed input x."""

```

```

h = self.seq(x)
mu = self.fc_mu(h)
logvar = self.fc_logvar(h)
std = torch.exp(0.5*logvar)
return mu, std, logvar

```

Listing C.3: Definition of HybridEncoder class.

```

class HybridDecoder(Module):
    """TVAE Decoder with a single KAN block at layer 'kan_layer_idx',
    the rest remain as standard TVAe Linear layers.

    Args:
        embedding_dim (int):
            Size of the input vector.
        decompress_dims (tuple or list of ints):
            Size of each hidden layer.
        data_dim (int):
            Dimensions of the data.
        kan_layer_idx (int): index of KAN layer.
        grid_size, spline_order, etc. (int):
            Hyperparameters for the KAN layers.
    """

    def __init__(self, embedding_dim, decompress_dims, data_dim,
                 kan_layer_idx=0, grid_size=5, spline_order=3,
                 scale_noise=0.1,
                 scale_base=1.0, scale_spline=1.0, base_activation=
                 torch.nn.SiLU,
                 grid_eps=0.02, grid_range=[-1, 1]):
        super(HybridDecoder, self).__init__()
        self.kan_layer_idx = kan_layer_idx
        # Swapping KAN layer when needed
        layers = []
        dim = embedding_dim
        for i, out_dim in enumerate(decompress_dims):
            if i == kan_layer_idx:
                layers += [
                    KANLinear(dim, out_dim,
                              grid_size=grid_size,
                              spline_order=spline_order,
                              scale_noise=scale_noise,
                              scale_base=scale_base,
                              scale_spline=scale_spline,
                              base_activation=base_activation,
                              grid_eps=grid_eps,
                              grid_range=grid_range),
                    nn.SiLU() # SiLU for KAN
                ]
            else:
                layers += [

```

```

        Linear(dim, out_dim),
        ReLU()
    ]
    dim = out_dim

    # Final projection to data_dim
    layers.append(Linear(dim, data_dim))

    self.seq = Sequential(*layers)
    self.sigma = Parameter(torch.ones(data_dim) * 0.1)

def forward(self, z):
    """Decode the passed input z"""
    x_recon = self.seq(z)
    return x_recon, self.sigma

```

Listing C.4: Definition of HybridDecoder class.

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